

The OCEM Journal of
**Management, Technology
& Social Sciences**

Multi Disciplinary Peer Reviewed Journals

Volume 2

Issue 2

January 2023

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The OCEM Journal of Management & Social Sciences (Multi-Disciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal)

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Gratitude

Research Management Cell of OCEM is grateful to Mr. Binod Babu Paudel in correcting gramatical errors and suggesting to RMC for the betterment of journal publication. He is a reputed English educator of Chitwan district. He has involved in many educational institutions including our organization. We wish his bright future. Importantly we are very thankful to our principal Professor Er. Hari Prasad Bhandari for his continuous support and inspiration. All the reviewers are also thankful for their feedback and suggestion. All other supporting hands are also thankful for their contribution to publish this journal articles.

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Acknowledgement of Engineering Department

Concept, capability and confidence would help professionals practice with high morale and professional integrity. Oxford College of Engineering and Management, one of the leading technical institutions, shares challenging opportunities through appropriate blending of the nation's requirements with young generations' wildlings. Innovation and creativity are nurtured by reinventing and revitalizing engineering services for nation-building when ethical values and social services are milestones. It is only achievable if the learning-teaching environment is research evidence-based and the study's outcome directly applies to infrastructure development through high-end technology, safety and glocalization.

For this system, the OCEM research department has taken the great initiative of publishing the research journal. We extend our sincere appreciation to our research head, who is bringing peer-reviewed journals into our hands. We believe this journal will soon be one of the most significant journals in the academic sector.

Challenges of today's engineering education are emergent, necessitating calls for its reformation to empower future engineers to function optimally as innovative leaders in national and international contexts. These challenges: keeping pace with technological dynamism; high attrition; and, most importantly, quality teaching/learning require multifaceted approaches. And this platform will open all the doors to faculties to leverage quality evidence-based teaching.

Nevertheless, linkages to equivalent global perspectives are presented from Nepal. Acknowledgement of Engineering Department Assoc. Prof. Bhim Bhandari BE Co-ordinator Oxford College Of Engineering and Management Gaindakot-2, Nawalparasi.

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Performance Analysis of Students in Nawalparasi Based on SEE Results in 2078 BS

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Received: November 15, 2022

Revised: December 17, 2022

Accepted: January 01, 2023

Published: January 29, 2023

How to cite this paper:

Adhikari, B.P & Kafle, S.C (2022).

Performance analysis of students in Nawalparasi based on SEE results in 2078 BS.

The OCEM Journal of Management, Technology & Social Sciences, 2(2), 1-14

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Originality: This paper is original and has not been published anywhere else

Paper type: Research Paper

J.E.L. Classification: I (2), I (29)

Abstract

The primary objective of this study was to examine students' gender-wise performance in different subjects of SEE results, the average grade point of each subject, and the total grade points of all subjects in the SEE exam in 2078 in Nawalparasi district. The data for this study was obtained from the 2078 BS SEE exam results using secondary data collection methods. The data analysis technique of this study was descriptive statistics where correlation analysis, arithmetic mean, Mann-Whitney U test and Chi-square test of independence were used for data analysis. The study included the exam results of 13139 students from both private and public schools in Nawalpur district. There were 6654 male students (50.6%) and 6485 female students (49.4%) in the sample. The results indicated that the majority of the SEE participants students (97.9%) were between 13 to 21, and 34.7% were 16 years which is the maximum observed percentage of students. In 2078 BS, only 1.1% of students over the age of 21 participated in the SEE exam, according to the results.

The results importantly show a significant association between the gender of students in Grade Point Average (GPA) of the SEE results in 2078 BS. The majority of the students had poor results in the SEE-2078 exam, as 56.3% of students secured less than 2.39 GPA, whereas no one obtained 4 GPA out of 4. Finally, the results indicate that the total grade point (TGP) of girls (2.53) is higher than boys in compulsory Nepali compared to male (2.59) students in the SEE results of 2078 BS in Nawalparasi district. The implication of this study would be beneficial to the Education Department of Secondary Education Examination (SEE), educators, researchers, policymakers, and parents to improve the overall GPA in SEE results.

Keywords: Educational assessment, Grade Point Average (GPA), SEE results, Students Performance Analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

Students' final result scores are important indicators of their performance in an educational setting (Gottfried et al., 2015). Research has shown that students who score well on final exams and other assessments have better academic outcomes, such as higher grades and greater success in postsecondary education (Dillon, 2017). On the other hand, students who score poorly on final exams are more likely to struggle academically and may be at risk of failing or dropping out of school (Gottfried et al., 2015). Several factors can influence students' final result scores, including their cognitive abilities, motivation, and study habits (Dillon, 2017). Students who have strong cognitive skills and are motivated to learn are more likely to perform well on final exams (Gottfried et al., 2015).

Additionally, students who develop good study habits, such as setting aside dedicated time for studying and reviewing material regularly, are more likely to succeed academically (Dillon, 2017). Hence, students' final result scores are key indicators of their performance in an educational setting. However, many factors impact the final score of an exam.

The school board exam certificate for the 10th class was named by School Level Certificate (SLC) before 2070 BS; however, it is now held in class 12. The 10th board exam is named by School Exit Examination (SEE in 2076). After implementing the Education Act 2073, the Higher Secondary Education Council was eliminated, and the National Examination Board became operational. The area of work has been determined so that the related school permit, scholarship, and school management work being edited by the Higher Secondary Education Council is now being managed at Local Level. The curriculum creation, development and equivalence determination work is also being operated by the Curriculum Development Center for Class ten (SEE). Examinations and activities related to classes eleven and twelve (SLCE) have been included under the National Examination Board's (NEB) jurisdiction. In addition, the responsibility of conducting the class ten examination at the provincial level and guiding the examination of the entire school education has been included within the scope of the NEB (National Examination Board, 2076). According to the Act's provision, the NEB's main work,

established to conduct, manage, and upgrade school education examinations, focuses on developing the examination system. The examination defines the National Education Board as a self-governing and organized body with unbroken succession.

After inspecting the SEE exam in Nepal, a few minor problems were identified. Even the teachers have complained about some of the question papers of SEE exams that should be reviewed. The government of Nepal has been continuously spending a large amount of the national budget on SEE exams all over Nepal; however, the results are not satisfactory constantly. The teachers are involved in political parties at all levels and are always busy serving the political leadership and unions and avoiding their fundamental tasks. At the same time, the politicians are actively involved in making student cadres participate in the protest, and election, throwing stones and burning tyres (Paudel, 2021).

The failure of leaders to recognize good and bad teachers is another big problem in current education. The local governments look aloof as far as the education system is concerned. They haven't yet presented quality policies for improving the education sector. They could have worked on making school-level education more practical, but even in their second tenure; they did nothing to improve education. The political power-sharing among students and teachers at different levels is causing harm to the entire education system. The next problem is that the people working in the education sector are using it as a source of income instead of making it a learning and academic hub. Likewise, the student unions and officials supposed to reform the education sector are ignorant and indifferent to the student's problems. The final impact of the abovementioned problems is weak grades in Math, Science, optional subjects, and overall grades (Paudel, 2021).

Objectives

The primary objective of this study is to examine the association between different subjects of SEE results, the average grade point of each subject, and the total grade points of all subjects in the SEE exam in 2078 in Nawalparasi district. The specific objectives are:-

- To analyze the results of demographic participation in the See exam of 2078 in Nawalparasi district
- To analyze the secondary data of SEE results of Nawalparasi district in 2078 based on gender
- To analyze the secondary data of SEE results of Nawalparasi district in 2078 based on age
- To find the association between the demographic and GPA of the SEE exam of 2078

Research questions

- What is the gender participation percentage in the 2078 BS SEE exam in Nawalparasi district?
- What is the age-wise participation in the SEE exam of 2078 in Nawalparasi district?
- What is the association between the age of students and their performance in the SEE results in 2078?
- What is the gender-wise performance difference in each subject of SEE in 2078 BS?

2. METHODS AND MATERIALS

The secondary data was used in this study, where numerical data of SEE results were requested from the SEE Board Sanuthimi Kathmandu by submitting an official request letter of Oxford College of Engineering and Management, Gaidakot-2, Nawalpur of Nepal. The research paradigm of this study is a quantitative research design because it gives crucial facts from numerical data. Through statistical analysis, we can derive important facts and valuable insights from purely numerical data, provide more accurate and reliable data, support analysis with clarity, and be more helpful (Cohen et al., 2011). The data analysis technique of this study is a descriptive statistical analysis where correlation analysis, arithmetic mean, one-way ANOVA analysis (Kruskal–Wallis one-way analysis of variance) and Chi-square analysis test were used for data analysis. The analysis further focuses on comparing gender wise performance of students. The independent variables are the grade point average of each subject grade points of compulsory and optional subjects of SEE. This study has followed the quantitative method to analyze the secondary data of SEE results of 2078 BS at Nawalparasi district.

These authors followed all the secondary data's ethical issues during the analysis phase (Creswell & Plano Clark 2007).

3. RESULTS

What are the association between different subjects, the average grade point of each subject, and the total grade points of all subjects in the SEE exam in 2078 in Nawalparasi district, Nepal?

The results of this study have summarized the comparative analysis of SEE results of 2078 in Nawalparasi district, Nepal. The results section has focused on analyzing each compulsory subject's average GPA comprising gender and age of SEE students. This section has also analyzed the results of absent, failed, below and good and above and good level.

Demographic analysis

What is gender-wise participation in the SEE exam of 2078 in Nawalparasi district?

Figure 1: Gender-wise student distribution in SEE 2078

The number of male students was 6654 (50.6%), and for females was 6485 (49.40%). The total number of schools (both Private and Public) in the Nawalpur district from which students have participated in the SEE board exam was 13140.

What is the age-wise participation of SEE examinees in 2078 in Nawalparasi district?

Student of different ages was attending in SEE exam; the age structure of students attending in SEE exam is shown in the bar diagram with error bars as below-

Age structure

Figure 2: Age of the SEE participants of 2078 BS at Nawalparasi district

The results show that the majority of the SEE participant students (97.9%) were between 13 to 21, and 34.7% were aged 16 years, the maximum observed percentage of students for a specific age. The results indicate that above the age of 21, only 1.1% of students participated in the SEE exam in the 2078 BS. On an individual basis, the age of the most SEE students in 2078, BS was 16 years (30%), followed the 15 years (29.4%), 17 years (14.6%), 14 years (10.8%), 18 years (7.8%), 19 years (3%), 13 years (1.8%) and 20 years (1.1%). The age percentage of other students was below 1%, so lower than 1% was excluded from the analysis.

Average GPA Age-wise

Figure 3. Age-wise average GPA of SEE students in Nawalparasi district

The results indicate that the average GPA of SEE students in the 2078 BS in Nawalparasi district is nearly the same for students of different ages. However, there are few students beyond the age of 13 to 21 years, the average GPA for students aged 42 and 55 was the highest and lowest for those aged 32 (see Figure 3). If we consider only the students between 13 to 21 years, 13 years students secured the highest score, it is almost the same for the age group 14 to 16 years, and it decreases up to 21 years (see Figure 3).

What is the gender-wise performance difference in each subject of SEE in 2078 BS?

Table 1. The analysis of gender-wise GPA Table 2. Mann Whitney U test for equality of mean GPA.

Passed	12729	Sex	Number of Students	Mann-Whitney U	Z	P- Value
Absent or fail	413					
Mean	2.29	Female	6485	19504148.5	-3.593	<0.01
Standard deviation	0.60	Male	6654			
Variance	0.37	Other	1			
95% CI of Mean	2.38-2.30	Total	13140			

The results indicate that among 13140 students registered to attain the SEE exam in 2078 BS, 12729 got the result, and the remaining students were absent or failed in at least one subject. The mean GPA of students who got the result is 2.29 with a standard deviation of 0.37, at a 95% confidence level, and the mean GPA of students is 2.28 to 2.30 (see Tables 1 & 2). Among the total student, one student mentioned another gender was omitted from the study as it may be a manual error, or even if it is correct, it does not have any significant effect on the data. The results show that the mean sample GPA of boys and girls students differs. To test whether it is the same in the population too, at first normality of GPA is tested for two genders, and it is found Non-Normal for both groups, so the data is required to carry the Mann-Whitney U test. Unless the data is normal for both groups, a t-test for the difference between two independent means cannot be carried out (Sainani, 2012). A significant difference between male and female students' average GPA on the SEE results in 2078 BS is seen as the p-value for Mann-Whitney U test is less than 0.01.

What is the association between the age of students and their performance in the SEE results in 2078?

Table 3. Categorical result analysis for students of 2078 BS

Results	Number of students	Percentage
Absent	411	3.1
Up to 2.39 (poor)	7402	56.3
2.40 to 3.99 (Good)	5327	40.5
4 (Excellence)	0	0
Total	13140	100.0

Table 4. Gender-wise performance of all SEE students of 2078 BS

Sex	Missing	Below good level (Below 2.4)	Good Level (2.4 to 3.99)	Total
Female	177 (1.3%)	3752 (28.7%)	2556 (19.5%)	6885 (49.4%)
Male	234 (1.82%)	3650 (27.8%)	2770 (21.1%)	6654 (50.6%)
Total	411 (3.1%)	7402 (56.3%)	5326 (40.5%)	13140 (100%)

The majority of the students had poor results in the SEE-2078 exam, as 56.3% of students secured less than a 2.39 GPA, whereas no one obtained a 4 GPA out of 4. The results indicate that the student's performance on the SEE Exam of 2078 BS has been presented except for one omitted other-gender student (see Table 3). The results show that the percentage of male and female students securing below and above good level is nearly the same. The results show a statistically insignificant association between the gender of the student and their performance in the SEE exam; it was significant while testing the Chi-Square test for whether there was a significant association between gender and SEE students' performance (p-value = 0.003). Somewhat male have better results than female students (see Table 4).

What is the gender-wise performance difference in each compulsory subject of SEE in 2078 BS?

Table 5. Age-wise performance of SEE students

Age group	GPA Group			Total
	Absent or fail	Below Good level	Above Good level	
Below 13 years and age missing	2 (0.02%)	53 (0.40%)	72 (0.55%)	127 (0.97%)
13 years to 21 years	359 (2.73%)	7277 (55.38%)	5249 (39.95%)	12885 (98.06%)
Above 21 years	46 (0.35%)	76 (0.78%)	6 (0.05%)	128 (0.97%)
Total	407 (3.10%)	7406 (56.36%)	5327 (40.54%)	13140 (100%)

Table 5. Mean GPA of students in major eight subjects

Grade in Compulsory subjects	Mean	Standard Deviation
COMP.ENGLISH	2.46	0.80
COMP.NEPALI	2.53	0.66
COMP. MATHEMATICS	1.36	0.83
COMP. SCIENCE	2.11	0.76
COMP. SOCIAL STUDIES	2.37	0.75
COMP. HEALTH, POP & ENV	2.58	0.798
COMP. SANSKRIT LANGUAGE	1.78	0.90
COMP.SANSKRIT LANGUAGE	2.67	0.82

The results show that out of 13140 students, 12885 (98.06%) belong to the age group 13 to 21 years, and most of their results are below a reasonable level. However, those above a good GPA contributed more from the same age group. The results indicate that compulsory Sanskrit language has the highest GPA (2.67), whereas the lowest was in Compulsory Maths (1.36). Similarly, the second highest GPA was in Health, and Physical Education (2.58), while the second lowest was in Compulsory Science (2.11 (see Table 5).

Table 6. Gender-wise performance in eight compulsory subjects

Sex	Values	GPA in English	GPA in Nepali	GPA in Math	GPA in Science	GPA in Social Studies	GPA in HPE	GPA in the Sanskrit Language	GPA in Falit Jyotish
Female	Mean	2.42	2.59	1.31	2.08	2.35	2.58	1.74	2.66
	N	6477	6477	6484	6479	6478	6477	6478	6476
	SD	0.813	0.657	0.777	0.734	0.743	0.778	0.864	0.806
Male	Mean	2.5	2.48	1.42	2.14	2.39	2.58	1.82	2.7
	N	6632	6631	6653	6633	6632	6631	6634	6631
	SD	0.802	0.655	0.873	0.777	0.756	0.779	0.932	0.839
Total	Mean	2.46	2.53	1.36	2.11	2.37	2.58	1.78	2.68
	N	13111	13110	13139	13114	13112	13110	13114	13109
	SD	0.809	0.659	0.829	0.757	0.75	0.778	0.9	0.823

Table 7 compares the student's performance in each of the eight subjects, with red in average GPA indicating higher than others, green for less and yellow for the same. The results indicate that the total grade point of girls is higher than that of boys (2.53) in compulsory Nepali compared to male students (2.59) in the SEE results of 2078 BS in Nawalparasi district. It was also found that female grade points were lower than male students in the rest of the compulsory subjects (see Table 7). But the total grade points of HPE of both boys and girls was the same (2.58). The results further indicate that the total grade points for Maths (1.31) were the lowest of all other subjects. The results confirm that male students got higher total average grade points in all subjects than female students except Nepali (see Table 6).

Table 7. Mann-Whitney U Test on the mean rank of different compulsory subjects

Subject	Sex	Number of Students	Mann Whitney U	P- Value
Comp. English	Male	6478	20113754.5	< 0.0
	Female	6632		
	Total	13110		
Comp. Nepali	Male	6478	18860390.5	< 0.0
	Female	6631		
	Total	13109		
Comp. Math	Male	6485	20249652.5	< 0.0
	Female	6653		
	Total	13113		
Comp. Science	Male	6480	20501505	< 0.0
	Female	6633		
	Total	13113		
Comp. Social Studies	Male	6479	20653074.5	< 0.0
	Female	6632		
	Total	13111		
Comp. H.P.E	Male	6478	2146429	0.774
	Female	6631		
	Total	13109		
Comp. Sanskrit Language	Male	6479	20577118	< 0.0
	Female	6634		
	Total	13113		
Comp. Falit Jyotish	Male	6477	20835753.5	0.03
	Female	6631		
	Total	13108		

The results indicate that the mean rank results indicate the mean of the eight compulsory subjects' Total grade points for each of the eight subjects of SEE results in 2078 BS. At a 5% significance level, the mean GPA of students is significantly different for males and females for Compulsory HPE (P-value =0.774). At a 1% significance level, it is significantly different from Compulsory Falit Jyotish (P-value = 0.03). In the rest subjects, there is no significant difference in mean GPA between the two genders (See Table 7).

4. DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The main findings of this study have been presented in tabulated form (see Table 2). The results indicate that the number of male students was 6654, and the number of females was 6485. The total number of schools in the Nawalpur district was 13140 in the SEE Board Exam of 2078 B.S. The results indicate that most of the SEE participants students were between 13 to 21 and 16 years, the maximum observation percentage

of students. The results on an individual basis indicate that the age of the most SEE students in 2078, BS, was 16 years, followed the 15 years, 17 years, 14 years, 18 years, 19 years, 13 years, and 20 years. The majority of the students had poor results in the SEE-2078 exam, as 56.3% of students secured less than a 2.39 GPA, whereas no one obtained a four-by-four GPA. The results indicate that the student's performance of the SEE results of 2078 BS has been presented except for one omitted unknown gender student. The results show that the percentage of male and female students securing below and above good level is nearly the same. The results showed a statistically insignificant association between gender and their performance in the SEE exam; it was significant while testing the Chi-Square test for whether there was a significant association between gender and SEE students' performance (p -value = 0.003).

The results indicate that 12885 (98.06%) participants belonged to the age group 13 to 21 years, and most of their results are below a reasonable level. Compulsory Maths has the most negligible average GPA compared to the highest value of the Compulsory Sanskrit Language(2.67) (see Table 6). Similarly, the results indicate that Health and Population have the second highest mean value (2.58), following the second lowest mean value of compulsory Science (1.36%). Additionally, the third highest mean value of Compulsory Nepali (2.53), whereas the third lowest mean value, are recorded in compulsory Science (2.11). The study of Liang, Choon and Bing (2010) supported this study's results, who found compelling evidence of a sizeable number of mathematics teachers in the participating secondary schools who could hardly produce better grades in Mathematics subject at the secondary level. The current high demand for mathematics teachers is also a possible reason for poor mathematics GPA in Nawalparasi district. The lack of government supervision to examine the teachers' teaching capability is the leading cause of weak results in Mathematics. Other possible causes of lower GPA in Mathematics are teachers' negligence in teaching mathematics, incapability of mathematics teachers, students' negligence to SEE exam, and parents' immaturity and negligence towards their children's education.

As stated in the Nepalese education act, the Ministry of Education regulates the overall education system, from curriculum development to school establishment in seven provinces. Various other regulatory bodies are designated to oversee the education

system at different levels, including the Secondary Education Examination (SEE) Board, which conducts and regulates the examination of grade ten. The National Examination Board (NEB) regulates the conduction and regulation of the Ministry of Education, which governs the overall education system from curriculum development to school establishment in seven provinces. Various other regulatory bodies are designated to oversee the education system at different levels, including the Secondary Education Examination (SEE) Board, which conducts and regulates the examination of grade ten. But there is a high difference between the declared law and practice in the Nepalese educational department from the central to the local level. All levels of government do not have cooperation and coordination to supervise school-level academic quality in Nepal.

The current study has supported the studies of Backstrom (2021) and Salem et al. (2014), who found that the gender of students significantly affected their academic performance of students. Students with a cumulative GPA of 3.0 or greater significantly differed from those with a GPA of less than 3.0 female students. Factors such as gender has been shown to significantly affect medical student GPA as a whole batch as well as when they were tested for gender.

RECOMMENDATION

After completing the research, the researchers have the following recommendations

- The local education department of Nawalparasi district needs to revise the regional education policy to improve SEE results.
- The school administration needs to supervise teachers' classroom teaching activities and the consistency of classroom presentations.
- Mathematics teachers need to change their classroom instruction strategies and teaching pedagogy.
- Mathematics and other teachers need to follow the memorization and writing strategy to improve the overall results in the SEE exam in Nawalparasi district.
- The whole school mechanism has to be revised to improve the overall results of SEE in Nawalparasi district.

- The Ministry of Education Department needs to formulate an incentive policy to motivate subject teachers to improve their overall GPA.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT FROM THE FIRST AUTHOR

I would like to recognize the love and affection of my wife, Nilam Adhikari, including my two sons, Dhruva Adhikari and Rabi Adhikari and daughter Rina Adhikari in the writing of this article. My family kept telling me courageously that you are a writer." It was very inspiring for my article writing. My honorable principal Prof. Er. Hari Prasad Bhandari always inspires me. I want to express my sincere thanks to the BBA department and my editor Dr Deb Raj Dhakal (Dean of Management Pokhara University), for editing my article. I would also like to acknowledge the help of all OCEM advisor committee faculty members for their continuous help and support while writing this article. I would recognize my decent colleagues and my students, especially Miss Sujayana Piya and Miss Susmita Gurung, for their support of our research.

REFERENCES

- Backstrom, P. (2021). School Composition, Disruptive Classroom Behaviour and Student Results: A Study of Mechanisms of Peer Effects. *Nordic Studies in Education*, 41(2), 167–184.
- Creswell, J.W. and Plano Clark, V.L. (2007). *Designing and Conducting Mixed Methods Research*. 3rd ed. Thousand Oaks Sage Publications.
- Dillon, J. (2017). The importance of student performance in education. *Educational Research and Reviews*, 12(4), 173-179.
- Gottfried, A. E., Fleming, J. S., & Gottfried, A. W. (2015). A review of the role of parental involvement in education. *Educational Psychology Review*, 27(1), 1-24.
- Liang, C. B., Choon, T. P., & Bing, Y. V. (2010). *Constructing An Exemplary Mathematical Justification Why Is It So Hard for Mathematics Teachers?* Retrieved from <https://repository.nie.edu.sg>, accessed on 19^{Dec.} 2022.

National Examination Board (2076). *NEB Library*. [online] National Examinations Board. Available at: <http://www.neb.gov.np/pages/details/welcome> [Accessed 28 Oct. 2022].

Paudel, J. (2021). Teacher Education in Nepal: Problems and Prospects with Brief Historical development. *Delhi Business Review*, 22(2), 39–48.

Sainani, K. L. (2012). Dealing With Non-normal Data. *PM&R*, 4(12), 1001–1005.

Salem, R. O., Al-Mously, N., Nabil, N. M., Al-Zalabani, A. H., Al-Dhawi, A. F., & Al-Hamdan, N. (2014). Various Factors Affecting Students' Performances in a Saudi Medical School. *International Journal of Educational and Pedagogical Sciences*, 0.0(8). Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2654728>, accessed on 19 Dec 2022.

AUTHOR'S CONTRIBUTIONS

This work was carried out in collaboration between both authors. Author BPA designed the study, managed the literature searches, wrote the protocol and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. Authors SCK performed the statistical analysis of the study. Both authors read and approved the final manuscript.

The Impact of Dimensions of E-learning on the Successful Implementation and Development of Digital Pedagogy in Nepalese Higher-level Educational Institutions

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Received: November 16, 2022

Revised: December 18, 2022

Accepted: January 02, 2023

Published: January 29, 2023

How to cite this paper:

Adhikari, B.P (2022). The Impact of Dimensions of E-learning on the Successful Implementation and Development of Digital Pedagogy in Nepalese Higher-level Educational Institutions

The OCEM Journal of Management, Technology & Social Sciences, 2(2), 15-55

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Originality: This paper is original and has not been published anywhere else

Paper type: Research paper

J.E.L. Classification: 100,C(1),C(18)

Abstract

The dimensions of E-learning are technology, governance, awareness of E-learning, attitude toward e-learning, and e-content development, which are supported by seventeen sub-factors of the vital measurements of E-learning pedagogy. The primary objective of this study was to examine the impact of the dimensions of E-learning on the successful implementation and development factors of digital pedagogy in higher education in Nepal. The quantitative research method and the survey study were applied to collect this study's data. The results indicate a significant association between social media for E-learning, the benefits of E-learning, using E-learning applications and technology, and the effective tools for teaching and the impact of E-learning dimensions for the successful implementation and development factors of digital pedagogy ($p < 0.05$).

But the results indicate no association between the E-content and open educational resources, the effectiveness and challenges of E-Learning, E-contents and open educational resources, and the benefits of E-learning for students, E-learning practice, roles of E-learning in capacity building, effective E-learning methods, E-learning methodologies and good practices, sources of E-learning, and optimization of learner efficiency and productivity, and the impact of the dimensions of E-learning for the successful implementation and development of digital pedagogy ($p > 0.05$). The implication of this study would be beneficial to policymakers, researchers, academicians, educators, and college leaders in such a way to provide first-hand information about the areas to be focused on for successful implementation and development factors on E-learning pedagogy in the Nepalese higher education sector.

Keywords: *Development factors, E-learning dimensions, digital pedagogy, successful implementation*

1. INTRODUCTION AND RESEARCH MOTIVATION

Higher-level educational institutions are responsible for preparing the next generation of leaders, scientists, politicians, scholars, educators, and researchers. They must drive innovation and growth (Goradia, 2019). The democratization of knowledge and expanding access to higher education requires higher-level institutions to review their pedagogical practices constantly. Future practices must be based on updated technology to successfully implement and develop digital pedagogy (Adhikari, Kafle, Liu & K.C. 2021). These practices ensure that they remain updated with developments in teaching practice and technology and provide their learners with the best possible guidance and support. Inaction would be irresponsible to learners, faculty, staff, and society in general, as these stakeholders depend on the innovations originated at higher-level institutions to create improved living conditions for everyone (Goradia 2019; Mahboobi 2021). The term E-learning was first used in the 1990s and was first used to refer to asynchronous and synchronous learning, specifically, online discussion groups. Asynchronous learning is also called on-demand or anytime learning, where synchronous learning is run synchronously with students and instructors attending from different locations (Jacobsen et al. 2017).

The transition to digital pedagogy systems has posed challenges for educators who have used to traditional education delivery systems (Mahboobi, 2021). For example, educators must adapt to new digital delivery methods to provide high-quality education in an online environment. Online learning needs to be created within a curriculum design framework that focuses on practical pedagogical principles to avoid a poor-quality learning experience. It is further supplemented by understanding what makes online learning work for students better and more successful (Adhikari et al., 2021). E-learning helps the learning environment in a different, more efficient, and attractive way. E-learning would be beneficial to overcome obstacles of time, space, and geography, providing learning opportunities for anyone, anytime, anywhere, and in any mode (Mahboobi, 2021).

This study's primary objective was to examine E-learning dimensions for the successful implementation and development of digital pedagogy in Nepalese higher education institutions. Further, E-learning supports students in developing their interests based

on their educational potential, arranging the desired contents and knowledge for their learning styles, and improving the quality of their learning in diverse ways (Perera et al., 2020). E-learning improves learners' performance and creates a student-centred learning environment where students work collaboratively, construct their knowledge, and enhance problem-solving and higher-order thinking skills (Gewirtz 2020). This study's implications would benefit higher-level educational institutions, researchers, students, scholars, policymakers, and educators to gain deep knowledge of E-learning to implement and develop digital pedagogy successfully. The possible critical factors for implementing and developing digital pedagogy are E-learning content, technology, governance, and attitudes toward E-learning (Adhikari., 2021; Mahboobi, 2021).

I have work experiences as an educator and researcher in Nepal's secondary and higher education institutions for more than 30 years. I have been engaged in more than thirty international conferences, seminars, and universities to present my papers. But I gained limited knowledge of effective E-learning pedagogy and factors for the successful implementation and development of digital pedagogy in Nepalese higher-level educational institutions. While guiding my faculty members, I faced many professional pedagogical hurdles. I am still looking for new ideas for the critical influencing factors to modernize digital pedagogy in higher education institutions in Nepal. Currently, the world is captured in my P.C., so it is time to find influencing factors for the successful implementation and development of digital pedagogy in Nepal.

I have an MBA degree from Nepal, an Executive EMBA from City of London College (<https://www.clclondon.ac.uk>), a Master of Research (U.K.), a PhD from East London University in educational studies and teacher education (U.K.), the next PhD degree from the University of Eastern Finland (Finland).

I have gained the work experience of more than 30 years working as an educator, researcher, and educational manager. So, I am interested in pursuing a career as an educator. This study paper will give me the knowledge and skills necessary to reach my goal. My prior experience and the fact that the degree from an international university will be completed through different research skills within three years have motivated me to write this paper. This study paper is very attractive to my career development. Another advantage of completing my PhD degree is that I could continue studying as

a full-time member of E-learning pedagogy. The study will help me foreground my interest in E-learning and allow me to apply the skills and knowledge in my future profession. Sometimes I could learn in class from my current place of residence. This study paper on the education program is an excellent paper that will provide me with the skills and knowledge necessary to reach my final career goals.

2. RESEARCH TOPIC, THEORETICAL CONTENT, AND RELEVANCE

The research topic of this study is decided as the impact of the dimensions of E-learning on the successful implementation and development factors of digital pedagogy in Nepalese higher-level educational institutions. There are distinct traditions in educational theory that derive from different perspectives about the nature of learning itself. Although learning theory is often presented as a large set of competing accounts for the same phenomena, it is more accurate to think of theory as a set of compatible explanations for an extensive range of different phenomena (Adhikari et al. 2021; Goodyear 2007). Here, this study follows the framework of Mahboobi (2021), which considers the different insights into E-learning success and incorporates the factors derived in this study based on the current situation in Nepal. The framework shows five critical dimensions of E-learning. Technology, governance, awareness, attitude toward e-learning, and e-content development, followed by seven sub-factors, are the vital dimensions of E-learning.

2.1 The theoretical framework of this study

The theoretical foundation of this study is based on professional competence (awareness), technology, governance, and attitude toward E-learning and E-content development (Adhikari et al. 2021; Mahboobi 2021).

2.2.1 Awareness (Professional Competence)

The key influencing factor in implementing and developing E-learning pedagogy is embedded in technology pedagogy training, learning management systems, pieces of training, computer skills and competence, and massive online courses training (Surry,

Ensminger & Haab 2005; Cheawjindakarn, Suwannatthachote & Theeraroungchaisri 2012). Furthermore, creating online content and courses, computer literacy, communication and collaboration tools, social media information literacy, data visualization, office Suit, media literacy, and operating system are the subfactors of awareness (Goodyear,2007; Mahboobi 2021).

2.2.2 Technology

Technical support, internet access, and E-learning tools are the critical sub-factors of technology factors (Ouajdouni, Chafik & Boubker 2021). The dimensions of technology are embedded in computer and software architecture and engineering, design research, human-computer interaction, learning psychology, program evaluation, project management, social interactions, and system thinking. These dimensions can support E-learning's successful implementation and development in higher-level educational institutions (Lewin, Cranmer & McNichol, 2018; Ronghuai Huang et al. 2019).

2.2.3 Governance

Planning, formal governance structure, collaboration and partnership, and organizational commitment are the sub-factors of e-learning governance (Ronghuai Huang et al. 2019). The practical implementation of e-learning is bound to technology. Technology is the top component for the realization of E-learning infrastructure. The E-learning strategy without adequate technology may fail to achieve the mission. The Information Technology's infrastructure, access to the Internet, speed of connectivity, learning management system, and learning websites must be considered. Reliability, richness, consistency, and effectiveness are the crucial indicators of quality technology in E-learning pedagogy (Perera et al. 2021; Selim 2007).

2.2. 4 Attitude toward E-learning

It was found that the attitudes of instructors and students toward using E-learning are the most significant dimensions for adopting and developing effective E-learning. The attitudes toward E-learning affect the intentions of users. To better implement E-learning programs, instructors need to embrace them, and the leadership and management need

to support them, arguing that in any new system, changes may face a challenge like resistance to change (Adhikari et al. 2021; Mahboobi, 2021; Mässing 2017).

2.2.5 E-content developments

Electronic content is becoming famous for its flexibility of time and pace of learning. E-content can be delivered through various electronic media supporting different subjects and almost all disciplines. E-contents can be shared and used by learners with diverse needs, backgrounds, experiences, and skills by providing access to students and instructors on campus, at home, and in other resource centres (Figaredo 2020; Mahboobi 2021). The conceptual framework of this study is based on the five factors that may support the successful implementation and development of effective digital pedagogy (see Figure 1).

Dimensions of E-learning

Figure 1. Conceptual framework of the study (Mahboobi 2021)

The dimensions of E-learning impacted the successful implementation and development of digital pedagogy in higher-level educational institutions(Mahboobi 2021)

2.3 Literature review related studies on successful implementation and development of E-learning in higher-level educational institutions

Table 1. Summary of the previous studies on influencing factors for the successful implementation and development of E-learning

Sources	Applied methods	Findings	Focus
Pipithsu Ksunt (2010)	The survey study method	The influencing E-learning success factors are in six different categories (information quality, system quality, service quality, attitude toward learning method, attitude toward cost-effectiveness, and type of public universities)	E-learning success factors
Hannen (2022)	The qualitative research study	Pedagogical, I.T. system, learner, and organizational factors are critical success factors of E-learning.	E-learning in the university context
Jaoua et al. (2022)	The survey study method	The e-learning system, e-learning readiness, interactivity, and resistance to change were four factors for an effective e-learning system.	Context of COVID-19 Pandemic in Higher Educational Institutions
Rizana et al. (2020)	A systematic literature review protocol	The success of e-learning implementation was users' satisfaction, actual usage, and continuance usage.	Users' perspective on E-learning in higher education
Jaber (2016)	A mixed-method approach	The perceived ease of use rather than the idea of perceived usefulness affected the implementation and development of E-learning.	Uses of E-learning in higher education institutions
Al-Adwan et al. (2021)	The survey study method	The quality factors, including the instructor, technical system, support service, educational systems, and course content quality, had a direct positive influence on students' satisfaction, perceived usefulness, and system use	A structural equation modelling approach to E-learning
Peiris & Hansson (2018)	The survey study method	The results indicate that commitment from all the stakeholders, having relevant resources, backup policies/strategies, guidelines, collaboration with both local and international ICT organizations, and the development of the educators professionally were summarized as the factors in the successful implementation and development of E-learning	Successful and sustainable e-learning

Sources	Applied methods	Findings	Focus
Deliwe (2021)	Case study method	The results indicated the importance of finances, regular discussions, and engagements with champions/experts and researchers in e-learning pedagogy are critical factors in implementing and developing successful E-learning.	Users' satisfaction, actual usage, and continuance usage
Igai & Yunus (2022)	A systematic review of the literature	The study result showed that impacts were the most discussed and examined aspect of studies regarding E-learning in formal education during the COVID-19 pandemic.	E-Learning users in formal education
Adhabi & Anozie, (2017)	Literature review along with qualitative interview method	The results indicated having relevant resources, backup policies/strategies, and guidelines, collaborating with local and international ICT organizations, and developing the educators professionally. Several other authors have written about essential factors for successful and sustainable e-learning.	Implementation of small-scale ICT development projects for E-learning
Mahboobi (2021)	Review of literature	<p>Awareness: Technology pedagogy training, LMS training, computer skills and competence, and use and access to MOOCs are crucial.</p> <p>Technology: Technical support, Access to the Internet, and e-learning tools.</p> <p>Governance: Planning, formal governance structure, Collaboration and partnership, and commitment</p> <p>Attitude: Control of teaching and content, learning environment, Pedagogy and teaching style, and localization</p> <p>E-content development: - Design, development, and support unit</p>	E-learning factors success
Basak et al. (2021)	Review of literature	Resource: -Technological, ethical, institutional, pedagogical, managerial, social interaction, and evaluation factors were critical success factors for E-learning.	
Sela & Sivan, (2009)	Literature review	The results found two types of e-learning success factors: the first one's must-have factors (useful and easy-to-use e-learning tools, marketing, management support, the right organizational culture, and the existence of a real need for the organization). The second one is nice to have factors (time to learn, support, mandatory learning, and incentives).	E-learning factors in perspective success students'

Sources	Applied methods	Findings	Focus
Setyo et al. (2018)	Qualitative interview method	The results indicated that this school's high-academic performance culture indirectly contributed to the students' e-learning success factors (the student's motivation, e-learning self-efficacy, prior knowledge of the e-learning technical competency, and students' interaction and collaboration).	E-learning success factors based on school culture
Setyo et al. (2018)	The survey study method	The results indicated enabling technology, organizational context, curriculum development, instructional design, and delivery are E-learning success factors.	E-learning success factors based on an academic perspective
Broadley (2007)	The survey study method	The results showed that critical success factors of E-learning are ICT infrastructure, ICT leadership, support and training initiatives, and the teachers' ICT capacity	Implementation of E-learning factors in Australia
Ouajdouni et al. (2021)	The survey study method	System quality, instructor quality, social influence, learner computer anxiety, perceived usefulness, E-Learning system use, E-learner satisfaction, and E-learning system success are success factors in E-learning in higher-level educational institutions.	Factors of E-learning system success
Aparicio , Bacao & Oliveira (2016).	The quality interview method	<p>Pedagogical factors: Instructor characteristics, course educational quality, pedagogical strategy, social interaction, learning community, evaluation, and assessment</p> <p>I.T. System factors: System quality, user satisfaction, content/ information quality, service quality, and ease of use/ interface design</p> <p>Learner factors: Student characteristics, motivation/ intention to use, perceived usefulness, and loyalty to the system</p> <p>Organizational factors: Institutional/ management support, organizational impact, availability of (human) resources, established learning culture, and institutional-administrative affairs</p>	E-learning success factors

2.4 Learning Theories

The instruction is the systematic development of a course design to reach intended and expected learning outcomes in the framework of instructional design processes. Learning theories seek to understand human behaviours in learning processes. Technological innovation's introduction to education has highly influenced the mode

of learning. Learning theory will help this author understand how higher-level students learn through digital pedagogy. It involves multiple disciplines, including psychology, sociology, neuroscience, and education. Behaviourism, cognitivism, and social constructivism are three popular learning theories of E-learning (Cifuentes 2021). Thus, learning theories are being developed in conjunction with technological developments in socio-political domains. This is not to say that learning theory offers instructional designers answers to design problems but instead offers clarity, direction, and focus throughout the instructional design process. (Yildirim 2010).

Behaviourism

Behaviourism focuses on how people behave, as its name implies, and evolved from a positivist worldview related to cause and effect. In simple terms, action produces a reaction. In education, behaviourism examines how students perform while learning. More specifically, behaviourism focuses on observing how students respond to certain stimuli that, when repeated, can be evaluated, quantified, and eventually controlled for everyone. The emphasis in behaviourism is on that which is observable and not on the mind or cognitive processes. In sum, it cannot be studied if we cannot observe it (Picciano 2017). Behaviourism led to the development of learning taxonomies because it emphasized the study and evaluation of multiple steps in the learning process. Behaviourists repeatedly study learning activities to deconstruct and define the elements of learning (Cifuentes, 2021).

Cognitivism

Cognitivism has been considered a reaction to behaviourists' rigid emphasis on predictive stimulus and response. Cognitive theorists promoted the concept that the mind has a vital role in learning and sought to focus on what happens between the occurrence of environmental stimulus and student response. They saw the mind's cognitive processes, such as motivation and imagination, as critical learning elements that bridge environmental stimuli and student responses (Harasim 2012; Picciano 2017). The future of cognitivism is exciting as more advanced online software evolves into adaptive and personalized learning applications that seek to integrate artificial intelligence and learning analytics into instruction (Picciano 2017).

Social Constructivism

The work of several education theorists has parallel work to behaviourism and cognitivism. Their emphasis on social constructionism was to describe and explain teaching and learning as complex interactive social phenomena between teachers and students (Cifuentes 2021). Picciano (2019) posited that learning is problem-solving and that the social construction of solutions to problems is the basis of the learning process. Siochrú (2018) described the learning process as establishing a zone of proximal development in which the teacher, the learner, and a problem to be solved exist. The teacher provides a social environment in which the learner can assemble or construct with others the knowledge necessary to solve the problem. Picciano (2019) 's approach to integrating computer technology into problem-solving can be easily applied to many facets of instructional design.

Research objective and question

The primary objective of this study is to examine the impact of different dimensions of E-learning on the successful implementation and development of digital pedagogy in higher-level educational institutions. The primary objective is subdivided into specific objectives to examine the association between the attitudes and experiences of higher-level students and the factors on successful implementation and development factors of digital pedagogy.

Primary research question

What is the association between different dimensions of E-learning and the impact on digital pedagogy's successful implementation and development factors?

3. RESEARCH METHOD AND MATERIALS

Research methodology is the overall story of the methodological section where principles of people's worldview, research methods, a sample population of this project, data collection methods, research tools, data analysis methods, reliability and validity of the collected data, and ethical issues of the research project (Creswell & Plano Clark 2011).

Ontological and epistemological assumptions of this study

A framework must consider how philosophy fits into the design of the quantitative method. This author likes to apply Crotty's (1998) conceptualization to position philosophy within a quantitative methodology. Paradigm (beliefs: epistemology, ontology), theoretical lens (social science theories), methodological approach (integrated methods approach), and methods (the survey) of data collection. Postpositivist worldview, Constructivist worldview, Participatory worldview and Pragmatist worldview are four applicable worldviews (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011). All these four worldviews have the same components but take different stances on these components. Worldviews differ in the nature of social reality (Ontology), how people gain knowledge of what they know (epistemology), the role values play in research (axiology), the process of research (methodology), and the language of research (rhetoric) are different elements of the four worldviews. Methods of data collection help inform the problems under study. This study has followed Positivist worldviews typically associated with a quantitative approach.

The Positivism worldview focuses on the consequences of research. The primary importance of the question asked rather than the methods to inform the problems under the positivism study. Thus, it is pluralistic and oriented toward what works and practices are required (Cohen et al. 2011). In a postpositivist study, the investigators work from the top down, from theory to hypothesis to data, to add or contradict the theory (Creswell & Plano Clark 2011).

Design of Quantitative Method

Based on this author's published journal articles (Adhikari et al. 2021), this author believed that the method section is the most concrete, specific part of this research study, which presents essential steps in designing quantitative methods for a research study, specifically focusing on survey designs. This design reflects postpositivist philosophical assumptions, as discussed in the previous section. For example, determinism suggests that examining the relationships between and among variables is central to answering questions and hypotheses through surveys (Creswell 2009). Reducing a parsimonious set of variables, tightly controlled through design or statistical analysis, provides measures for testing a theory in quantitative methods. Objective data results from

empirical observations and measurements were considered in this study. The validity and reliability of instrument scores have led to meaningful data interpretations in this study (Cohen, Manion & Morrison 2007).

The survey study method

A survey design provides a quantitative or numeric description of a population's trends, attitudes, or opinions by studying a population sample. The researcher can generalize or make claims about the population from sample results. In experiment research, investigators may also identify and generalize a sample population to a particular population (Creswell 2009). This survey study examines the theory of E-learning dimensions that describes the successful implementation and development of digital pedagogy in Nepalese higher-educational institutions. The independent variables were professional competence, technology, governance, and attitude toward e-learning and e-content development, which impact digital's successful implementation and developmental factors. The independent variables were defined as the dimensions of E-learning. The dependent variable was the impact on the dimensions of E-learning's successful implementation and development factors. (Creswell & Plano Clark 2011; Cohen et al. 2011).

The survey method was used because it is economical, easy to manage, covers a larger sample population, and can be administered remotely via online, mobile devices, mail, email, and telephone. Additionally, the survey has become a popular data collection tool because it collects systematic data cheaply and quickly (Groves et al. 2009). A survey study further provides a quantitative or numeric description of a population's trends, attitudes, or opinions by studying a population sample and includes cross-sectional studies using questionnaires for data collection, with the intent of generalizing from an example to a population (Cohen et al. 2011).

This study followed the Five Likert scale type of the survey instrument indicating measurement scales of strongly disagree, disagree, no idea, agree, and strongly agree. The measurements of the survey instrument were technology, governance, awareness, the attitude of students and instructors, and e-content development with different sub-measurements (Cohen et al. 2011). The survey questionnaire was administered based on the reviewed literature on the E-learning dimensions (see Appendix 1).

Quantitative data collection and instrumentation

Initially, the sample population of this study was requested to permit this author to go through the data collection procedures. After permission was accepted, this author corresponded to all higher-level student service units using personal email to contact them. The follow-up emails were sent again and again until the higher-level institutions made a reply. When the response was received, this author requested the research department of higher-level institutions for the ethical approval of accessing their students. After their approval, this author sent an email to student associations for further procedures of the data collection process. In some cases, this author also called higher-level institutions' research departments to build rapport with student groups for the data collection procedures (Creswell 2009).

Most of the sample higher-level institutions are located in Chitwan and Nawalparasi districts, Nepal, so this author was able to go on a field visit to facilitate the data collection process. The overarching objective of this study was to examine the impact of the dimensions of E-learning on the successful implementation and developmental factors of digital pedagogy in Nepal. The design of this study was a cross-sectional survey of higher-level students aged 20 and older randomly selected from higher-level educational institutions in Nepal. The total population was based on the Chitwan and Nawalparasi higher-level institutions. The Oxford College of Engineering and Management, Gaidakot-2, Nawalparasi, Birendra Multiple Campus, Bharatpur, Valley State College, Bharatpur, International College, Parsa, and Shaheed Smriti Multiple Campus, Ratnanagar, Chitwan were the total sample institutions. The total sample population was three hundred (N = 3000). The sampling frame estimated a representative sample size of two hundred and forty (N = 240) higher-level students. The random sample was used to select the sample population of this study because this sampling method can give equal opportunity to everyone to participate in the research activity (Etikan 2017). Similarly, the survey was proposed as a research instrument for this study.

Data analysis techniques

This author goes through a similar set of quantitative data analysis steps, which prepares the data for analysis, explores the data, analyzes the data, represents the analysis,

and validates and interprets the data. These steps simultaneously unfold linearly in quantitative research (Punch & Oancea 2014).

Quantitative data analysis preparation and exploring the data for analysis

In the quantitative study, this author began the data analysis by converting the data into valuable numbers, sorting the data by assigning a numeric value to each response, clearing data entry errors from the database, and creating special variables needed for this study. After clearing all inserted data in Excel, this author transferred all numerical data into Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). This study further explored the quantitative data analysis involved visually inspecting the data and conducting a descriptive statistical analysis. The factors reduction method was used to find the principal components from each survey instrument's variables, reduce the number of variables, and find the relationship between group variables. Data analysis focused on naming group variables as principal components for further data analysis. After representing each Principal Component (P.C), the variables of each P.C were recorded in different subscales and calculated the means and Standard Deviations. Cronbach's Alpha value was calculated to find the reliability of the collected data. The minimum accepted value of Alpha was fixed ($\text{Alpha} > .60$).

Further, the analysis of this study examined the association between the dependent and independent variables. The choice of the statistical test was based on the research question. The Binary Logistic Regression (BLR) model was used to find the association between the independent and dependent variables. The significance value was determined ($p < 0.05$) to indicate the association between the dependent and independent variables.

4. RESULTS

What is the association between different dimensions of E-learning and the impact on digital pedagogy's successful implementation and development factors?

The data analysis was based on the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy (KMO), total variances, mean, STD, Alpha values, and BLR analysis. The mean value of all subscales was less than (3), indicating that all participants normally disagree with having a neutral perspective on the claims. The results show that the alpha values of

all subscales were more than .600, indicating that the data acquired was correct and logically ideal for analysis (see Table 1). The KMO table has presented the result for interpreting data sufficiency for factor analysis, which should be more than 0.600 for the sample to be adequate for factor analysis if the scale's tabulated values are greater than 0.6, which was sufficient for analysis (see Table 1).

Table 1. The values of mean, S.D., KMO and Variances

Subscales	Mean	STD	KMO	Variances
Roles of E-learning in capacity building	2.58	1.13	.889	42.23%
E-learning practices and actions	2.66	1.07	.747	.903 8.85%
Using social media for E-learning	2.91	.833	.545	7.09%
Benefits of E-learning for students	2.80	1.15	.818	51.46%
Students' perspectives on E-learning	2.84	.993	.724	.808 17.86%
E-learning management system	2.86	.990	.812	43.53%
Student's viewpoints on the E-learning system	2.69	.944	.619	.816 16.09%
Effective E-learning methods	2.60	1.05	.880	41.91%
E-learning methodologies and good practices	2.65	.968	.851	7.17%
Sources of E-learning	2.62	.920	.807	.907 5.47%
Optimization of learner efficiency and productivity of E-learning	2.95	1.13	.712	4.94%
Developing effective E-learning	2.83	.965	.827	38.52%
Reimagining the role of technology in education	2.75	.915	.713	8.21%
Essential Roles of the Learning Development Team	2.63	.889	.733	.868 7.08%
Flexible E-learning Framework	2.74	1.10	.622	6.98%
E-content and open educational resources	2.78	.873	.834	33.04%
The Effectiveness and Challenges of Online Learning	2.82	.943	.739	6.51%
E-contents and open educational resources	2.66	.922	.764	.866 5.85%
Benefits of E-learning for students	2.75	.906	.679	5.04%
Effective tools for teaching	2.76	1	.661	4.71%
Use of E-learning tools	2.77	1.21	.637	4.36%

4.1.1 Professional competence of learners

What is the association between the professional competence of learners and the successful implementation and development factors of digital pedagogy?

Creating online content and courses, computer literacy, communication and collaboration tools (Skype, Google Drive), Social Media (Facebook, Twitter), information literacy, data visualization, office Suit (M.S. Office, G Suit), media literacy, and operating systems (M.S. Windows, Linux) are the main factors of professional awareness of for the implementation and development of E-learning pedagogy (Mahboobi 2021).

Table 2. Summary of block 1 model (N = 240)

Model	Chi-square	df	Sig.	Cox and Snell's R Square	Nagelkerke's R square	-2log-likelihood
Omnibus tests of model coefficients	6.632	3	.085	.027	.064	126.198
Hosmer and Lemeshow test	22.646	8	.004			

The results indicate that the Chi-square was 6.632, and no associated significance level was more than 0.05. The present model shows a decrease in deviance from the base model. The Hosmer and Lemeshow test results show that the Chi-square value was 22.646, where the associated significance level was less than 0.05. The present model shows a decrease in deviance from the base model. Therefore, this model is a better fit compared to the base model (Block 0). The effect size shown by Cox and Snell & R Square value was .027, and Nagelkerke's & R-square value was .064 indicating a better fit. According to Camp man (2017), Nagelkerke's & R Square modified the Cox and Snell R square mathematics to potentially allow the value to reach 1; thus, Nagelkerke's & R-square was used in this study.

Table 3. Classification Table (N = 240)

Classification Table				
Observed	Predicted			Percentage Correct
	QNO 1a. Have you ever been involved in E-learning?			
	Yeah	No		
QNO 1a. Have you ever been involved in E-learning?	Yeah	221	0	100.0
	No	19	0	.0
Overall Percentage				92.1

The results of the classification table show that the overall model gives 92.10 percent correct prediction. As shown in Table 1, out of 240 participants, 221 chose the (Yes) option, and 19 chose (No) the second option, those involved in E-learning practices. Thus, it predicts 92.1 percent of participants were involved in E-learning (see Table 3).

Table 4. Binary logistic regression analysis to predict the professional competence of learners on digital pedagogy (N = 240)

Independent variables	B	SE	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95% C.I. for EXP (B)	
							Lower	Upper
Independent variables	.313	.250	1.570	1	.210	1.368	.838	2.232
E-learning practices	-.117	.230	.257	1	.613	.890	.576	1.397
Social media for E-learning	-.550	.2614.43	4.43	1	.035	.577	.346	.962
Constant	-2.620	.275	90.833	1	.000	.073		

The variables in the equation table show their estimated B, standard error, Wald statistics, degree of freedom, significance level and exponential. The squared ratio of the estimated coefficient to its standard error is Wald statistics and is used to examine the significance of parameters. As tabulated, the significant value of the independent variable is less than 0.05; the parameters are significant. The odds value of 1.368 is greater than that of other variables. The results indicate a significant association between social media for E-learning and the impact of the dimensions of E-learning pedagogy, indicating a negative impact on the successful implementation and development of digital pedagogy ($p < 0.05$, $B = -.550$, odds = .577). The result highlights no association between E-learning practices, roles of E-learning in capacity building and successful implementation and development factors of digital pedagogy in Nepalese higher-level educational institutions ($p > 0.05$).

4.1.2 E-learning systems success

What is the association between the E-learning system's success factors and the successful implementation and development factors of digital pedagogy?

E-learning system success factors are technical system quality, information quality, service quality, support system quality, learner quality, instructor quality, and perceived usefulness for higher-level students. Four constructs were found to be the determinants of e-learning use: educational system quality, support system quality, learner quality, and perceived usefulness (Al-Fraihat, Joy, Masa'deh & Sinclair 2020).

Table 5. Summary Table of block 1 models (N = 240)

Model	Chi-square	df	Sig.	Cox and Snell's R Square	Nagelkerke's R square	-2log-likelihood
Omnibus tests of model coefficients	11.141	2	.004	.045	.107	121.689
Hosmer and Lemeshow test	17.770	8	.023			

The results indicate that the Chi-square value was 11.141, and the associated significance level is less than 0.05. The results show that the present model shows a decrease in deviance from the base model. Hosmer and Lemeshow's test results show that the Chi-square was 17.770, and the associated significance level was less than 0.05. The present model shows a decrease in deviance from the base model. Therefore, this model was a better fit compared to the base model. The results show the effect size shown by Cox and Snell & R Square value was .045, and Nagelkerke's & R-square value was .107, indicating a better fit (see Table 5).

Table 6. Binary logistic regression analysis to predict E-learning systems success factor on digital pedagogy (N = 240)

Independent variables	B	SE	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95% C.I. for EXP(B)	
							Lower	Upper
Benefits of E-learning for students	.701	.286	5.992	1	.014	2.015	1.150	3.531
Using E-learning applications' technology	-.545	.257	4.482	1	.034	.580	.350	.960
Constant	-2.748	.302	83.016	1	.000	.064		

The results show a significant association between the benefits of E-learning for students and the impact of digital pedagogy's implementation and development factors ($p < 0.05$, $B = .701$, odds = 2.015). Furthermore, the results show the positive impact on digital pedagogy's successful implementation and development factors (see Table 6). Again, the results show an association between the using E-learning applications' technology and the impact of successful implementation and development factors of digital pedagogy ($p < 0.05$, $B = -.545$, odds = .580). The results further indicate a negative impact on successful implementation and development factors of digital pedagogy in Nepalese higher-level educational institutions (see Table 6).

4.1.3 E-learning system quality

What is the association between the E-learning system quality and the successful implementation and development factors of digital pedagogy?

A strong relationship between organizational factors (top management support and change management) and E-learning system quality has never been known. In addition, the quality factors (course content quality, system quality and service quality) positively and significantly affect students' satisfaction with e-learning system quality (Badrul Huda Khan 2005). Therefore, educational institutions seeking to achieve greater benefits from E-learning systems should pay considerable attention to the quality factors and organizational factors during the design and implementation process of their systems because of the important role of these factors in enhancing e-learning system quality and e-learning service quality (AlMulhem 2020).

Table 7. Summary table of block 1 models (N = 240)

Model	Chi-square	df	Sig.	Cox and Snell's R Square	Nagelkerke's R square	-2log-likelihood
Omnibus tests of model coefficients	4.527	2	.104	.019	.044	128.304
Hosmer and Lemeshow test	14.979	8	.044			

The results confirm that the Chi-square value was 4.527, and no associated significance level is less than 0.05. The Hosmer and Lemeshow test indicates the Chi-square value was 14.979, and the associated significance level was less than 0.05. The present model shows a decrease in deviance from the base model. Therefore, this model was a better fit compared to the base model. The results also indicate that the effect size shown by Cox and Snell & R Square value was .019, and Nagelkerke's & R-square value was .044 indicating a better fit in the present model.

Table 8. Binary logistic regression analysis to predict instructor quality in E-learning Teaching on E-learning pedagogy (N = 240)

Independent variables	B	SE	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95% C.I. for EXP(B)	
							Lower	Upper
E-learning management system	.425	.259	2.706	1	.100	1.530	.922	2.540
Students' viewpoints on the E-learning system	.303	.256	1.396	1	.237	1.354	.819	2.237
Constant	-2.565	.263	94.977	1	.000	.077		

The results show no association between the E-learning management system, student viewpoints and successful implementation and development factors of digital pedagogy in Nepalese higher-level educational institutions ($p > 0.05$) (see Table 8).

4.1.4 Individual support in E-learning pedagogy

What is the association between individual support in E-learning pedagogy and the successful implementation and development factors of digital pedagogy?

Information about courses, guidance concerning the choice of courses and programmes, financial questions, loans, grants, guidance on practical matters, dispatch of printed and other physical learning materials, registration/information/user identity, passwords, introduction to online learning techniques, initial follow-up, technical support, teaching/tutoring, academic support, organization of learning, social support, assessment, practical support, economy, follow-up, technical support, resources/library, learning group support, local learning support, local administrative support, local technical support, local social/practical support, diploma/accreditation, counselling on further study, counselling on job opportunities and University Alumni services are the critical student support systems in E-learning pedagogy (Khan 2005).

Table 9. Summary of block 1 models (N = 240)

Model	Chi-square	df	Sig.	Cox and Snell's R Square	Nagelkerke's R square	-2log-likelihood
Omnibus tests of model coefficients	3.718	4	.446	.015	.036	129.112
Hosmer and Lemeshow test	15.698	8	.047			

The results show that the Chi-square value was 3.718, and no associated significance level was more than 0.05. The Hosmer and Lemeshow test results show that the Chi-square value was 15.698, and the associated significance level is less than 0.05. The present model shows a decrease in deviance from the base model. Therefore, this model is a better fit compared to the base model. The results show that the The results show that the effect size shown by Cox and Snell & R Square value was .015, and Nagelkerke's & R-square value was .036 indicating a better fit (see Table 9).

Table 10. Binary logistic regression analysis to predict system quality of E-learning pedagogy on E-learning pedagogy (N = 240)

Independent variables	B	SE	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95%C.I. for EXP(B)	
							Lower	Upper
Effective E-learning methods	.415	.260	2.546	1	.111	1.514	.910	2.520
E-learning methodologies and good practices	-.212	.231	.845	1	.358	.809	.514	1.272
Sources of E-learning	.077	.243	.099	1	.753	1.080	.670	1.740
Optimization of learner efficiency and productivity	-.135	.248	.295	1	.587	.874	.537	1.421
Constant	-2.547	.259	96.377	1	.000	.078		

The results show no association between effective E-learning methods, E-learning methodologies and good practices, sources of E-learning, optimization of learner efficiency and productivity, and the impact of the dimensions of E-learning for the successful implementation and development factors of digital pedagogy in higher-level educational institutions in Nepal ($p > 0.05$) (see Table 10).

4.1.5 E-learning governance factor

What is the association between the E-learning governance factor and the successful implementation and development factors of digital pedagogy?

The governance in developing E-learning programs is crucial to the success and demand to remain competitive. Today's top policy of HEIs is to transfer knowledge and skills productively and cost-effectively. The transfer of knowledge and skills innovatively needs clear guidelines and governance essentials to improve learning programs. E-learning governance is the responsibilities and practices implemented to appoint strategic direction, ensure the achievement of objectives, and risk management. Organizational structure, technical platforms, and pedagogical contexts are successful e-learning implementations (Al-Fraihat et al. 2020). It requires a clearly defined governance structure. The roles and responsibilities, organization structure, chief learning/Information officers, and steering committee(s) are essential for a successful e-learning implementation. The organization's commitment, planning, and formal organizational structure are critical governance dimensions (Khan 2005).

Table 11. Summary Table of block 1 models (N = 240)

Model	Chi-square	df	Sig.	Cox and Snell's R Square	Nagelkerke's R square	-2log-likelihood
Omnibus tests of model coefficients	4.138	4	.388	.017	.040	128.692
Hosmer and Lemeshow test	9.105	8	.333			

The results show that the Chi-square value was 4.138, and no associated significance level was more than 0.05. The results further show that Hosmer and Lemeshow test results show the Chi-square value was 9.105, and the associated significance level was less than 0.05. Hence, the present model shows a decrease in deviance from the base model. Therefore, this model is a better fit compared to the base model. The results show that the effect size shown by Cox and Snell & R Square value was .015, and Nagelkerke's & R-square value was .036, indicating a better fit in the present model.

Table 12. Binary Logistic Regression analysis on E-learning governance factor (N = 240)

Independent variables	B	SE	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95%C.I. for EXP(B)	
							Lower	Upper
Developing effective E-learning	-.073	.243	.090	1	.764	.930	.577	1.497
Reimagining the role of technology in education	.375	.237	2.506	1	.113	1.455	.915	2.316
Essential roles of the learning development team	.063	.239	.070	1	.791	1.065	.666	1.704
Flexible E-learning Framework	-.271	.241	1.268	1	.260	.763	.476	1.222
Constant	-2.546	.257	98.09	1	.000	.078		

The results show no association between developing effective E-learning, reimagining the role of technology in education, essential roles of the learning development team, flexible E-learning framework and the impact of the dimensions of E-learning for the successful implementation and development factors of digital pedagogy in Nepalese higher-level educational institutions ($p > 0.05$) (see Table 12).

4.1.6 Attitude factors of E-learning pedagogy

What is the association between the attitude factors of E-learning and the impact of dimensions of E-learning for the successful implementation and development factors of digital pedagogy?

E-learning uses information technologies to deliver information for education and

training, regardless of time restrictions or geographical proximity. It is one of the most significant developments in the information technology industry. In recent years, E-learning has become a popular way of gaining knowledge for many students worldwide because it represents a straightforward, modern, cost-effective solution for universities, lecturers, and students. E-learning systems have been widely used and applied in education in the last 20 years. Unlike most developed countries, where E-learning is both common and widely used, it is still new in developing countries, such as Nepal, it is still a new and emerging pedagogical issue (Jović, Kostic Stankovic & Neskovic 2017).

Table 13. Summary Table of block 1 models (N = 240)

Model	Chi-square	df	Sig.	Cox and Snell's R Square	Nagelkerke's R square	-2log-likelihood
Omnibus tests of model coefficients	22.585	6	.001	.090	.211	110.245
Hosmer and Lemeshow test	13.273	8	.103			

The results show that the Chi-square value was 22.585, and the associated significance level was greater than 0.05. The results further show that in Hosmer and Lemeshow test results, the Chi-square value was 13.273, and the associated significance level was more than 0.05. Hence, the present model did not show a decrease in deviance from the base model. Therefore, this model was a better fit compared to the base model. The results further show that the effect size shown by Cox and Snell & R Square value was .090, and Nagelkerke's & R-square value was .211, indicating a better fit in the present model.

Table 14. Binary logistic regression analysis on attitude factors of E-learning (N = 240)

Independent variables	B	SE	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95% C.I. for EXP(B)	
							Lower	Upper
E-content and open educational resources	.498	.292	2.905	1	.088	1.646	.928	2.919
The Effectiveness and Challenges of E-Learning	-.411	.218	3.538	1	.060	.663	.432	1.017
E-contents and open educational resources	-.022	.251	.008	1	.930	.978	.598	1.601
Benefits of E-learning for students	-.152	.258	.349	1	.555	.859	.518	1.423
Effective tools for teaching	.563	.270	4.336	1	.037	1.755	1.034	2.981
Use of E-learning tools	-.652	.247	6.979	1	.008	.521	.321	.845
Constant	-2.927	.326	80.595	1	.000	.054		

The results show a significant association between the effective tools for teaching and the impact on the successful implementation and development factors of digital, indicating a positive impact on digital pedagogy ($p < 0.05$, $B = .563$, odds = 1.755), indicating a positive impact on digital pedagogy. Similarly, a significant association between the use of E-learning tools and the impact on the successful implementation and development factors of digital, indicating a negative impact on digital pedagogy ($p < 0.05$, $B = -.652$, odds = .521). But the results show no association between the E-content and open educational resources, the effectiveness and Challenges of E-Learning, E-contents and open educational resources, and the benefits of E-learning for students on the impact of the successful implementation and development of digital pedagogy ($p > 0.05$).

Table 15. The wholesome model of regression

Independent variables	B	SE	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp- p(B)	95% C.I. for EXP(B)	
							Lower	Upper
Roles of E-learning in capacity building	-.048	.531	.008	1	.929	.954	.337	2.700
E-learning practices	-.400	.449	.794	1	.373	.670	.278	1.617
Social media for E-learning	-1.365	.603	5.123	1	.024	.255	.078	.833
Benefits of E-learning for students	.786	.469	2.801	1	.094	2.194	.874	5.504
Student's perspectives on using technology	-.976	.454	4.612	1	.032	.377	.155	.918
E-learning management system	1.631	.670	5.927	1	.015	5.108	1.374	18.986
Student's viewpoints on the E-learning system	.675	.418	2.603	1	.107	1.964	.865	4.461
Effective E-learning methods	-.298	.533	.312	1	.577	.743	.261	2.112
E-learning methodologies and good practices	-.849	.623	1.860	1	.173	.428	.126	1.449
Sources of E-learning	-.675	.544	1.536	1	.215	.509	.175	1.480
Optimization of learner efficiency	-.606	.445	1.849	1	.174	.546	.228	1.307
Developing effective E-learning	-1.090	.687	2.516	1	.113	.336	.087	1.293
Reimagining the role of technology in education	.460	.607	.574	1	.449	1.584	.482	5.205
Essential roles of the learning development team	.693	.504	1.892	1	.169	1.999	.745	5.364
Flexible E-learning framework	-.199	.495	.162	1	.687	.819	.311	2.161
E-content and open educational resources	.739	.576	1.644	1	.200	2.093	.677	6.473
The Effectiveness and Challenges of Online Learning	-.489	.453	1.163	1	.281	.614	.252	1.491
E-contents and open educational resources	.297	.459	.419	1	.517	1.346	.548	3.306
Benefits of E-learning for students	-1.207	.586	4.240	1	.039	.299	.095	.944
Effective tools for teaching	.878	.538	2.659	1	.103	2.406	.838	6.911
Use of E-learning tools	-.876	.393	4.964	1	.026	.416	.193	.900
Constant	-5.035	1.011	24.822	1	.000	.007		

The results of classification Table predicts 94.2 percent of participants were involved in E-learning. The results of the wholesome model show a significant association between social media for E-learning, students' perspectives on using E-learning applications and technology, and E-learning management systems for the implementation and development of digital pedagogy ($p < 0.05$).

The results further indicate a significant association between the use of E-learning tools and the benefits of E-learning and the impact of the dimensions of E-learning for the successful implementation and development of digital pedagogy, indicating the negative impact of the successful implementation and development factors of E-learning pedagogy students ($p < 0.05$) (see Table 15).

But the results show no association between the roles of E-learning in capacity building, E-learning practices, benefits of E-learning for students, student's viewpoints on the E-learning system, effective E-learning methods, E-learning methodologies and good practices, sources of E-learning, optimization of learner efficiency and production of E-learning, developing effective E-learning reimagine the role of technology in education, essential roles of the learning development team, flexible E-learning framework, E-content and open educational resources and the effectiveness and challenges of online learning ($p > 0.05$) (see Table 15).

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

5.1 Discussion

This study is embedded in the impact of the dimensions of E-learning for the successful implementation and developmental factors of digital pedagogy in Nepal. This study aimed to examine the opinions and experiences of higher-level students and the impact on the dimensions of E-learning pedagogy for the successful implementation and developmental factors. The quantitative method was proposed to collect the survey data. The reviewed literature indicates that pedagogical factors, organizational factors, I.T. system factors and instructors' characteristics are the critical influencing factors for the successful implementation and development of digital pedagogy in higher-level educational institutions.

Research question 1

What is the association between the professional competence of learners and the successful implementation and development factors of digital pedagogy?

The results highlight a significant association between social media for E-learning and the impact of the dimensions of digital pedagogy ($p > 0.05$). The result of this study is supported by the study of Rennie (2013), who found that social media were an effective tool for the successful implementation and development factors of E-learning because every student would have easy access to outstanding lecturers, resulting in cost savings.

Research question 2

What is the association between the E-learning system's success factors and the successful implementation and development factors of digital pedagogy?

The results show a significant association between the benefits of E-learning for students, using E-learning applications' technology, and the impact of digital pedagogy's successful implementation and development factors. This study is supported by Okoye et al. (2022), who found that the users upheld the emphasis on the lack of different E-learning technological tools and resources, and access to the Internet and digital platforms, as the main challenges to the teaching-learning process.

Research question 3

What is the association between the E-learning system quality and the successful implementation and development factors of digital pedagogy?

The results confirm no association between the E-learning management system, student viewpoints and successful implementation and development factors of digital pedagogy in Nepalese higher-level educational institutions ($p > 0.05$).

Research question 4

What is the association between individual support in E-learning pedagogy and the successful implementation and development factors of digital pedagogy?

The results show no association between individual support in E-learning pedagogy and the successful implementation and development factors of digital pedagogy.

Research question 5

What is the association between the E-learning governance factor and the successful implementation and development factors of digital pedagogy?

The results indicate no association between the E-learning governance factor and the successful implementation and development factors of digital pedagogy.

Research question 6

What is the association between the attitude factors of E-learning and the impact of dimensions of E-learning for the successful implementation and development factors of digital pedagogy?

The results show a significant association between the effective tools for teaching, the use of E-learning tools and the impact on the successful implementation and development factors of digital, indicating a negative impact on digital pedagogy. The current study is supported by Pham et al. (2021), who found that learner characteristics, perceived usefulness, course content, course design, ease of use, effective tools of E-learning, and faculty capacity. The results further show a significant association between use of E-learning tools and the impact of the dimensions on the successful implementation and development factors of digital pedagogy ($p < 0.05$). This study is supported by Al-Adwan et al. (2021), who found that using E-learning tools impacted the successful implementation and development of digital pedagogy.

5.2 Conclusion

The primary purpose of this study was to examine the opinions and experiences of higher-level students on the successful implementation and development factors of digital pedagogy in Nepalese higher-level educational institutions. This study extends the Mahboobi (2021) model by adding new factors to examine how successful implementation and development of digital pedagogy can affect the quality of E-learning systems in higher-level students. The conceptual framework empirically evaluated digital pedagogy's successful implementation and development factors of digital pedagogy in higher-level educational institutions. The findings strongly support E-learning pedagogy's successful implementation and development factors in higher-level educational institutions.

Because not many higher-level students have experience in taking online courses (Adhikari et al. 2021), 240 students from different educational institutions participated in this study, which was conducted to examine their opinions and experiences on online education. Very important information was obtained for the study of impact of the successful implementation and

development factors of the digital education process. For the case of this study, it is expected that examining the experiences and opinions of higher-level students regarding online education might shed light on the literature. Higher-level students stated that online education has both positive and negative aspects. Participants noted that the online learning process is very economical in terms of time and finance, and there is no space limitation which is another crucial advantage. Ferdiansyah et al. (2020) also stated that online education offers wide opportunities in terms of the economy while minimizing problems related to time and space. Higher-level students reported the roles of E-learning in capacity building, E-learning practices, social media for E-learning, benefits, students' perspectives on using E-learning, and E-learning applications and technology in the online education process were inefficient in this respect. The higher-level educators and teachers need to pay much attention to ensure more interaction with students and among students in the online education process. In addition, the participants emphasized the negative aspects of online education by stating that they had difficulties, especially while learning an experimental study. However, the literature has revealed that online education makes learning activities more accessible rather than making it complicated. In particular, some studies have highlighted that online learning environments are motivating and fun in that they offer materials that facilitate learning activities.

Studies state that the above reasons positively affect E-learning (Adhikari et al. 2021; Kaya et al. 2010). All proposed hypotheses in this study were supported, offering significant insights into understanding the effects of dimensions on e-learning quality. The findings demonstrate a strong relationship between organizational factors (top management support and change management) and e-learning system quality, which is key finding of this study. In addition, the results show that quality factors (course content quality, system quality, and service quality) have a positive and significant effect on students' satisfaction with e-learning system quality. Therefore, educational institutions seeking to achieve incredible benefits from e-learning systems should pay considerable attention to the quality factors and organizational factors during the design and implementation process of their E-learning systems because of the critical role of these factors in enhancing e-learning system quality and e-learning service quality.

This study contributes to my understanding of how E-learning is developing in Nepalese higher educational institutions significantly and has optimistic impacts on the success of E-learning pedagogy. A correct pedagogical model of Internet-based E-learning must, as high-quality distance education, be designed and organized to satisfy the support needs of many students. These support measures are handled by different categories of personnel and different media and technologies. They might be general for all or specific according to individual needs; they might be automatic or dependent on human decisions; they might be based on personal contact and personal service or delivered electronically without human intervention.

This study will help policymakers in such a way to provide first-hand information about the areas to be focused on for successful implementation and development factors on E-learning pedagogy in the Nepalese higher education sector. The findings would enable to design, development and implementation of E-learning programs better and would have efficient investments in e-learning. Therefore these factors will save resources in terms of effort, money, and time and enhance the image of higher education institutions in the country or worldwide. It is suggested to emphasize these factors before designing E-learning initiatives or while improving the existing e-learning system. Finally, this study's results would be valuable for the government, school administrators, teachers, and parents to acknowledge the importance of well-equipped facilities and a stable internet connection for effective learning. However, it is recommended that future researchers utilize a larger sample size and include students from various backgrounds to understand this issue better.

BIBLIOGRAPHY AND REFERENCES

- Adhikari, B.P., KC, K.B., Liu, C.-H. and Kafle, S. (2021). *The Impact of COVID Pandemic on Students' E-learning in Nepal's Higher Education Digital Pedagogy*. [online]. Available at: <https://www.journalofmethodology.com/en/publications> [Accessed 10 September 2022].
- Al-Adwan, A. S., Albelbisi, N. A., Hujran, O., Al-Rahmi, W. M., & Alkhalifah, A. (2021). Developing a Holistic Success Model for Sustainable E-Learning: A Structural Equation Modeling Approach. *Sustainability*, 13(16), 1-25

- Al-Fraihat, D., Joy, M., Masa'deh, R., & Sinclair, J. (2020). Evaluating E-learning systems success: An empirical study. *Computers in Human Behavior*, *102*, 67–86.
- Alharbi, B. (2021). Mobile Learning Age: Implications for Future Language Learning Skills. *Psychology and Education Journal*, *58*(2), 862–867.
- Alhomod, S., & Shafi, M. M. (2013). Success factors of E-learning projects: A technical perspective. *Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology*, *12*(2), 247–253.
- AlMulhem, A. (2020). Investigating the effects of quality and organizational factors on university students' satisfaction with e-learning system quality. *Cogent Education*, *7*(1). 1-17
- Aparicio, M., Bacao, F., & Oliveira, T. (2016). Cultural impacts on e-learning systems' success. *The Internet and Higher Education*, *31*, 58-70.
- Basak, S. K., Wotto, M., & Bélanger, P. (2021). *A Framework on the Critical Success Factors of E-Learning*
- Cheawjindakarn, B., Suwannathachote, P. and Theeraroungchaisri, A. (2012). (PDF) *Critical Success Factors for Online Distance Learning in Higher Education: A Review of the Literature*. [online] ResearchGate. Available at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/256186772>. [Accessed 04th September 2022].
- Cifuentes, L. (2021). *A guide to administering distance learning*. Brill.
- Cohen, L., Manion, L., & Morrison, K. (2018). *Research Methods in Education* (8th ed.). New York. Routledge.
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches* (5th ed.). SAGE Publications.
- Creswell, J., & Plano Clark, V. (2007). *Designing and conducting mixed methods research* (1st ed.). Thousand Oaks: Sage.
- Creswell, J.W. (2014). *Research design: qualitative, quantitative & mixed methods approach*. 5th ed. Los Angeles: Sage.
- Deliwe, AP. (2021). *Factors essential for successful and sustainable e-learning*. Editorial Universität
- Denzin, N. K., & Lincoln, Y. S. (1998). *The landscape of qualitative research: Theories and issue*. London: Sage Publications.
- Etikan, I. (2017). Combination of Probability Random Sampling Method with Non-Probability Random Sampling Method (Sampling Versus Sampling Methods). *Biometrics &*

- Biostatistics International Journal*, 5(6). Available at: doi:10.15406/bbij.2017.05.00148. [Accessed 05th September 2022]. Ferdiansyah, S., Supiastutik, & Angin, R. (2020). Thai Students' Experiences of Online Learning at Indonesian Universities in the Time of the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Journal of International Students*, 10(S3), 58–74.
- Figaredo, D. (2020). Data-driven educational algorithms pedagogical framing. *RIED. Revista Iberoamericana de Educación a Distancia* 23(2), 65.
- Goodyear, P. (2007). Representing practitioner experiences through learning design and patterns. *Rethinking pedagogy for a digital age: Designing and delivering e-learning*. [online] Available at: <https://www.academia.edu>. [Accessed 10th September 2022].
- Goradia, T. (2019). Next Generation, Higher Education: Online and blended learning. *The Educational Review, USA*, 2(7). [online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.26855/er.2019.07.003>. [Accessed 09th September. 2022]. Groves, R.M., Fowler, F.J., Couper, M., Lepkowski, J.M., Singer, E. and Tourangeau, R. (2009). *Survey methodology*. 2nd ed. Hoboken, N.J.: Wiley.
- Hannen, C. J. (2022). Success factors for e-learning in business organizations: a qualitative study. Available at <https://run.unl.pt/handle/10362/134025>, [Accessed on 03rd January 2023].
- Harasim, L. (2012). Learning theory and online technologies. London. Routledge/Taylor & Francis.
- Hennink, M., Hutter, I. and Bailey, A. (2020). *Qualitative Research Methods*. 2nd ed. London: Sage Publications. Igai, W. K. A., & Yunus, M. M. (2022a). *A Systematic Review of Perception of E-Learning Users in Formal Education during COVID-19 Pandemic. Creative Education*, 13(06), 1981–1998.
- Implementation in Higher Education: A Review of the Literature*. Available at <https://www.researchgate.net/publication>. [Accessed 10th September 2022].
- Jaber, O. A. (2016). *An Examination of Variables Influencing the Acceptance and Usage of E-Learning Systems in Jordanian Higher Education Institutions*. Available at <https://figshare.cardiffmet.ac.uk>. [Accessed 03rd October. 2022].
- Jacobsen, M., Brown, B., Lock, J., & Jacobsen, M. (2017). *Signature pedagogies for e-learning in higher education and beyond*. Calgary. Available at Eric.ed.gov. <https://web.archive.org/web>
- January, F., Almurad, H. M., Elshaer, I. A., & Mohamed, E. S. (2022). E-Learning Success Model in the Context of COVID-19 Pandemic in Higher Educational Institutions. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(5), 2865.

- Jović, M., Kostic Stankovic, M., & Neskovic, E. (2017). Factors Affecting Students' Attitudes towards E-Learning. *Management: Journal of Sustainable Business and Management Solutions in Emerging Economies*, 22(2), 73. <https://doi.org/10.7595/10.7595/management.fon.2017.0016>
- Karunaratne, T., Peiris, C. & Hansson, H. (2018). Implementing small-scale ICT projects in developing countries – how challenging is it? *International Journal of Education and Development using ICT*, 14(1), Open Campus, The University of the West Indies, West Indies. Available at <https://www.learntechlib.org/p/183556/>. [Accessed 03rd October 2022].
- Khan, B.H. (2005). *Managing E-learning: design, delivery, implementation, and evaluation*. Information Science Pub.
- Lewin, C., Cranmer, S., & McNichol, S. (2018). Developing digital pedagogy through learning design: An activity theory perspective. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 49(6), 1131–1144.
- Lichtman, M. (2013). *Qualitative education research: a user's guide*. London. Sage Publications.
- Mahboobi, S. A. (2021). *Vol. 35 (2022): A new decade for social changes | Technium Social Sciences Journal*. Available at: <https://techniumscience.com/index>[Accessed 11th September. 2022].
- Mahboobi, S.A. (2021). Success Factors for e-learning implementation in Afghan Higher Education institutions.
- Mässing, C. (2017). Success Factors and Challenges for E-learning Technologies in the Namibian Higher Education System: A case study of the University of Namibia. *Undefined*. [online] Available at: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Succes> [Accessed 16th September 2022].
- Okoye, K., Hussein, H., Arrona-Palacios, A., Quintero, H. N., Ortega, L. O. P., Sanchez, A. L., Ortiz, E. A., Escamilla, J., & Hosseini, S. (2022). Impact of digital technologies upon teaching and learning in higher education in Latin America: an outlook on the reach, barriers, and bottlenecks. *Education and Information Technologies*. Available at <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-022-11214>, and accessed on 7th January 2023.
- Ortiz, D. (2007). Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches [Book Review]. *Qualitative Research Journal*, 6(2), 205-207.

- Ouajdouni, A., Chafik, K. and Boubker, O. (2021). *National Center for Biotechnology Information*. [online] Nih.gov. Available at: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>. [Accessed 03 October 2022].
- Pamella, D., Ayanda. (2021). *Factors essential for successful and sustainable e-learning*. Editorial Universitat Politècnica de València. Available at <https://headconf.org>. [Accessed 03rd October 2022].
- Perera, C. J., Zainuddin, Z., Piaw, C. Y., Cheah, K. S. L., & Asirvatham, D. (2020). The Pedagogical Frontiers of Urban Higher Education: Blended Learning and Co-Lecturing. *Education and Urban Society*, 52(9), 1305– 1329.
- Pipithsuksunt, V. (2010). *Examining the Integrated Influence of Quality and Attitude Factors on E-learners' Satisfaction and E-Learning System Success in Thai Public University*. [online] Available at <http://libdcms.nida.ac.th/thesis6/2010/b169586.pdf>. [Accessed 03rd October. 2022].
- Politécnica de València. Available at <https://headconf.org>. [Accessed 03rd October. 2022].
- Priatna, T., Maylawati, D. S., Sugilar, H., & Ramdhani, M. A. (2020). The Key Success Factors of e-Learning Implementation in Higher Education. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (IJET)*, 15(17), 47-50
- Rennie, F. (2013). *e-Learning and Social Networking Handbook Resources for Higher Education*. London. Routledge.
- Rizana, A. F., Hedyanto, U. Y. K. S., Ramadhan, F., & Kurniawati, A. (2020). E-learning success determinants in higher education: A systematic literature review from users' perspective. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, 830(3), 032012.
- Ronghuai Huang, J Michael Spector, Yang, J., and SpringerLink (2019). *Educational Technology: A Primer for the 21st Century*. Singapore: Springer Singapore.
- Saleem, F., Ainasrallah, W., Malik, M.I. and Rehman, S.U. (2022). Factors Affecting the Quality of Online Learning During COVID-19: Evidence from a Developing Economy. *Frontiers in Education*, 7(13), 1-13
- Sela, E., & Y. Sivan, Y. (2009). Enterprise E-Learning Success Factors: An Analysis of Practitioners' Perspective (with a Downturn Addendum). *Interdisciplinary Journal of E-Skills and Lifelong Learning*, 5, 335–343.
- Selim, H.M. (2007). E-learning critical success factors: an exploratory investigation of student perceptions. *International Journal of Technology Marketing*, 2(2), .57-63.
- Setyo, R. C. Y., Suharsono, S., & Purwati, O. (2018). The contribution of school culture to the

learner success factors in e-learning. *Journal on English as a Foreign Language*, 8(2), 149.

Setyo, R. C. Y., Suharsono, S., & Purwati, O. (2018a). The contribution of school culture to the learner success factors in e-learning. *Journal on English as a Foreign Language*, 8(2), 149.

Surry, D.W., Ensminger, D.C. and Haab, M. (2005). A model for integrating instructional technology into higher education. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 36(2), 327–329. Upadhyay, J.P. (2018). Higher Education in Nepal. *Pravaha*, 24 (1), 96–108.

Technium Social Sciences Journal, [online] 18(1), pp.101–116. Available at: <https://ideas.repec.org/a/tec/journal/v18y2021i1p101-116.html> [Accessed 03rd September 2022].

Yildirim, D. (2010). *E-learning in diverse subject-matter contexts. An Explorative Study*. Available at <https://www.db-thueringen.de/servlets/MCRFileNodeServlet/dbt>. [Accessed 03rd October. 2022].

Yip, M. W., & Ng, A. H. H. (2019). Critical success factors of knowledge management implementation in higher learning institutions. *International Journal of Knowledge and Learning*, 13(1), 45

APPENDIX 1. The survey questionnaire's Background information

- a. Have you ever studied the program by e-learning? 1) Yeah 2) N0
- b. Which university have you learned from?
- c. Which area/major have you studied?
- d. Which degree have you ever been studying? 1. Lower bachelor's 2. Bachelor's 3. Master's 4. PhD 5. Postdoc 6. Other
- e. How is your latest grade on E-learning?
- f. Your gender 1. Male 2. Female 3. Other
- g. Your age: 1, Less than 20 Years 2. 20-35 years 3. 36-50 Years 4. 50 More than 50 Years
- h. Are you a full-time student? 1. Full-time 2. Part-time
- i. What is your monthly salary? 1. NRS 10,000 2. NRS 10,001- 20,000 3. NRS 20001-3000 4. NRS 30,001-40,000 5. NRS 40,001-50,000 6. More than NRS 50,000
- j. How do you use the Internet? (You can choose more than one choice)
 1. Dial-Up (Dial-Up at Home)
 2. Internet ADSL (ADSL HIGH SPEED at Home)
 3. INTERNET at School
 4. INTERNET at Work
 5. INTERNET at Any Service Providers
 6. Others
- k. How long are you studying each time you connect? 1. 1 hrs 2. 1-2 hrs 3-5 hrs 4. More than 5 hrs

- l.** How often do you connect to an online class?
 1. Everyday
 2. Alternatively.
 3. 1-2 (one or two days a week)
 4. Connect (Randomly)
- m.** What time do you like to connect?
 1. 00.00 - 03.00
 2. 03.00 - 06.00
 3. 06.00 - 09.00
 4. 09.00 - 12.00.
 5. 12.00 - 15.00
- n.** What do you think that quality in many factors affects your studying by e-learning?
 1. Strongly Agree = 7, Somehow agree = 6, Agree = 5, I do not know= 4, Disagree = 3, Somehow agree = 2, Strongly Disagree = 1

1. Factors of awareness (Professional Competence) (Variables)	1	2	3	4	5
1a. Creating online content and courses is important for e-learning.					
1b. Computer literacy is important for e-learning.					
1c. Communication and Collaboration tools (Skype, Google Drive) are important for e-learning.					
1d. social media (Facebook, Twitter) is important for e-learning.					
1e. Information literacy is important for e-learning.					
1f. Data Visualization is important for e-learning.					
1g. Office Suit is important for e-learning.					
1h. Media literacy is important for e-learning.					
1i. Operating System (M.S. Windows, Linux) is important for e-learning.					
1j. Overall, the e-learning system is helpful in my study					
1k. Overall, the quality of using e-learning is easy to use					
1l. Overall, e-learning affects my self-efficiency					
1m. Without careful planning, the company would spend more money, unappealing products, and failure					
1n. The implementation of e-learning could help the students in doing their assessments more efficient and effective					
1o. In e-learning, students are required to do self-study; due to this, they are required to know using the technology					
2. E-learner satisfaction					
2b. 2a. E-learning is enjoyable					
2c. E-learning gives me self-confidence					
2d. E-learning satisfies my educational needs					

2e. I am satisfied with the performance of the system					
2f. E-learning is pleasant to me					
2g. I am pleased enough with the e-learning system					
3. E-Learning system success					
3a. The system has a positive impact on my learning					
3b. The system has a positive impact on my learning					
3c. Overall, the performance of the system is good					
3d. Overall, the system is successful					
3e. The system is an important and valuable aid to me in the performance of my classwork					
3f. The system helps me to Increase my knowledge					
3g. The system helps me to Increase Self-reliance					
4. Instructor Quality					
4a. I use an e-learning system as recommended by my instructors					
4b. I think an instructor's enthusiasm for using e-learning stimulates my desire to learn					
4c. I receive prompt responses to questions and concerns from my instructors in e-learning					
4d. think communicating and interacting with instructors are important and valuable in e-learning					
4e. Generally, my instructors have a positive attitude to the utilization of e-learning					
5. System quality					
5a. The e-learning system is easy to navigate					
5b. The e-learning system is easy to use					
5c. The e-learning system allows me to find the information I am looking for easily					
5d. The e-learning system is well structured					
5d. The responsible service personnel is always highly willing to help whenever I need support with the e-learning system.					
5e. The responsible service personnel provide personal attention when I experience problems with the e-learning system.					
5f. The responsible service personnel provide services related to the e-learning system at the promised time					
5g. The responsible service personnel have sufficient knowledge to answer my questions regarding the e-learning system.					

Tick the options based on your experience

1= Strongly disagreed 2 = Disagreed 3 = No idea 4 = Agreed 5 = Strongly agreed

6. Individual Impact					
The e-learning system enables me to accomplish tasks more quickly.					
The e-learning system increases my productivity.					
The e-learning system makes it easier to accomplish the task					
The e-learning system is helpful for my job.					
7. Technology Factors (Variables)					
2a. Technical support is important for E-learning					
2b. Access to the Internet is important for E-learning					
2c. e-learning tools are important for E-learning					
2d. Synchronous discussion area is important for E-learning					
2e. Online databases/ knowledge repositories are important for E-learning					
2f. Search engines are important for E-learning					
2g. Multi-user dialogue is important for E-learning					
2h. Virtual reality is important for E-learning					
2i. Forums are important for E-learning					
2j. Learner web-post area is important for E-learning					
2k. Learner online journal is important for E-learning					
2l. Sharing tool is important for E-learning					
2m. Video conferencing is important for E-learning					
2n. Chat is important for E-learning					
2o. Web links manager is important for E-learning					
2p. Ask the expert" area/link is important for E-learning					
2q. Solution/problems area is important for E-learning					
2r. Digital area audio/video capturing is important for E-learning					
2s. One-on-one mentoring is important for E-learning					
8. Governance Factors (Variables)					
	1	2	3	4	5
3a. Strategic planning is important for E-learning					
3b. Formal governance structure is important for E-learning					
3c. Collaboration and partnership are important for E-learning					
3d. Organization Commitment is important for E-learning					
3e. Roles and responsibilities of E-learning are good					
3f. Organization structure of E-learning is good					

3g. Chief Learning Officer on board is responsible for E-learning effectiveness					
hj. Chief Information Officer is responsible for the correct and reliable, and effectiveness					
3i. The E-strategy committee is always active and innovative for the successful implementation and development of digital pedagogy.					
3j. Steering committee is always responsible for the successful implementation and development of digital pedagogy					
3k. Licensing and regulations are essential and responsible for the successful implementation and development of digital pedagogy					
3l. Service-level agreements are essential and responsible for the successful implementation and development of digital pedagogy.					
3m. Service and technical management are essential and responsible for the successful implementation and development of digital pedagogy.					
3n. Information security and risk management are essential and responsible for the successful implementation and development of digital pedagogy.					
3o. Infrastructure management systems are essential and responsible for successfully implementing and developing digital pedagogy.					
3p. Software management is essential and responsible for the successful implementation and development of digital pedagogy					
3q. Network management is essential and responsible for the successful implementation and development of digital pedagogy					
3r. Resource management is essential and responsible for the successful implementation and development of digital pedagogy					
9. Attitude Factors (Variables)	1	2	3	4	5
10. E-content development factors (Variables)					
5a. E-content development is one factor					
5b. Mean Score is another factor					
5c. Design and development are the next factors					
5d. Support Unit is another factor					
5e. E-content is useful / covers the learners' needs					
5f. E-content is personalized / partly constructed by the learner					
5g. E-content is motivating					
5h. E-content provides active and interactive learning, social learning, and communication					
5i. E-content uses authentic materials					
5j. E-content integrates different kinds of feedback					
5k. E-content is integrated into a suitable and reliable learning platform					
5l. E-content is an all-in-one package					

5m. E-content is based on the KISS principle (Keep it simple, stupid)					
5n. E-content is developed from a matrix-approach					
4a. Control of teaching and Content is important for E-learning.					
2b. Learning environment is important for E-learning.					
4c Pedagogy and teaching style are important for E-learning.					
4d localization is important for E-learning.					
4e. If available, I intend to use e-learning tools during the semester					
4f. If available, I intend to use e-learning tools as frequently as possible					
4g. I wouldn't say I like using e-learning tools.					
4g. Using e-learning tools is a foolish idea.					
4h. I believe it will be a good idea to use E-learning tools					
4h. I have a generally favourable attitude towards using e-learning tools					
4h. I have a generally favourable attitude					
4g. If available, I intend to use e-learning tools whenever possible for my coursework					
4h. I wouldn't say I like using e-learning tools.					

APPENDIX 2. Sample population

Interview number	Interviewees	Date	Purpose	Number of Interviews
Interviewees	Tribhuvan University	June- 2023	The attitudes of higher-level instructors and students on the successful implementation and development of digital pedagogy	2
	Kathmandu University	July- 2023		
	Lumbini Boudha University	August-2023	<i>What is the association between E-Learning system governance and digital pedagogy's successful implementation and development of digital pedagogy</i>	1
	Pokhara University	September-2023		
Interviewees	Purbanchal University	October-2023	The attitudes of higher-level instructors and students on awareness of instructors and students and the successful implementation and development of digital pedagogy	1
	Nepal Sanskrit University	November-2023		1
Interviewees	Far Western University	December 2023	The attitudes of higher-level instructors and students on available technological facilities and digital pedagogy's successful implementation and development of digital pedagogy	1
	Agriculture & Forestry Science University	January-2024		1
Interviewees	Mid-Western University	February-2024	The attitudes of higher-level instructors and students on E-content development and digital pedagogy's successful implementation and development of digital pedagogy	1
	B P Koirala Institute of Health Sciences	March- 2024		1
Interviewees	National Academy of Medical Sciences	June-2024	<i>What is the association between attitudes of higher-level instructors and students and the successful implementation and development factors of digital pedagogy?</i>	1
	Patan Academy of Health Sciences	July-2024		
	Far Western University	August 2024	The attitudes of higher-level instructors and students on E-Learning system governance and digital pedagogy's successful implementation and development of digital pedagogy	1
Total interviewees				14

APPENDIX 4. Sample structure

$$n = \frac{z^2 p \cdot q \cdot N}{e^2 (N-1) + z^2 p \cdot q}$$

APPENDIX 5. The sample population of the quantitative study

Sample universities	Address	Number of students	Percentage	Sample students
Tribhuvan University	Bagmati Province	405,341	86.60%	294
Kathmandu University	Bagmati Province	14,709	3.79%	13
Purbanchal University	Province number one	24441	5.72%	20
Nepal Sanskrit University	Province number five	3533	0.80%	3
Pokhara University	Gandaki Province	25290	6.14%	22
Far Western University	Far Western Province	1941	0.44%	2
Agriculture & Forestry Science University	Bagmati Province	1,785	0.40%	1
Mid-Western University	Karnali Province	2623	0.59%	2
Lumbini Buddha University	Lumbini Province	276	0.69	3
B P Koirala Institute of Health Sciences	Province one	950	0.22%	1
National Academy of Medical Sciences	Bagmati Province	654	0.15%	1
Patan Academy of Health Sciences	Bagmati Province	367	0.08%	1
Total number of students		441,461	100%	363

Parents' Satisfaction with the Facilities in Montessori School at Nawalparasi District

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Received: November 17, 2022

Revised: December 19, 2022

Accepted: January 03, 2023

Published: January 29, 2023

How to cite this paper:

Gurung S. & Adhikari, B.P. (2022).
Parents' satisfaction with the facilities in Montessori School at Nawalparasi district

The OCEM Journal of Management, Technology & Social Sciences, 2(2), 56-80

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Oxford College of Engineering and Management

Originality: This paper is original
and has not been published
anywhere else

Paper type: Research paper

J.E.L. Classification: M (3), M (31)

Abstract

The primary objective of this study was to analyze the level of parents' satisfaction with the behaviour and roles of office staffs, receptionists, and roles of teachers. This study has applied the quantitative approach along with the survey method. The survey instrument was used to collect two hundred (N =200) data from the parents of Montessori schools in Gaindakot 1 and 2, Nawalpur. Random sampling was used to select the parents of Montessori schools. The results show positive association between the behaviour and roles of office staff, receptionists, and parents, satisfaction.

Similarly, the results show a negative association between the facilities of Montessori schools, the influence of Montessori quality and behaviour and the roles of Montessori teachers. This study has concluded that there was an association between the quality of Montessori education and parental satisfaction. This study's implications would benefit new researchers, scholars, colleges, local government, Montessori schools, school administrators and owners and investors of private schools in Nepal.

Keywords: *Montessori school, office staff and receptionist, parental satisfaction, roles and behaviour, teachers*

1. INTRODUCTION

This study is about the parent's satisfaction with their children's education at Montessori Schools. Parent satisfaction is based on the activities of behaviour and roles of Office staff and receptionists, teachers, and the facilities to provide a better practical education system, individual care, hands-on learning, independence, and self-directed activities. Access to quality pre-primary education plays an important role in children's growth and development. Several studies reveal that high-quality early education produces long-lasting benefits for children, such as stronger literacy, language and math skills, better attitudes towards school, better relationship with classmates, and later academic success (Omondi, 2013). Globally, the provision of quality pre-primary education remains elusive, especially in developing countries. According to UNICEF (2019), the quality of pre-primary education in Sub-Saharan African countries was inadequately characterized by a shortage of trained teachers, poor funding, poor physical infrastructure, unfavourable child-teacher ratio, and low participation rates.

Parents' satisfaction with the quality of education has been reported to vary with the type of school. Studies indicate that parents are transferring their children from public to private schools due to the perceived low quality of education in public schools regarding good discipline, physical facilities, better teacher performance and higher quality output (Gibbons & Silva, 2011). Koirala (2019) highlights that Nepal's Montessori has not been able to make the learning of children as effective and productive as the Montessori in abroad. He further says that most of the Montessori kindergartens in Nepal do not meet international standards and do not significantly impact children's social, mental and intellectual development.

Based on the article's website, it has a unique topic, and few literature reviews are available in general, as well as those parents who followed the Montessori trend of sending their children to pre-schooling Montessori. Nowadays, parents are too preoccupied with their careers to spend quality time with their children. Parents are increasingly choosing Montessori education to provide their children with a better environment and education. Parents know various learning methods and seek the best Montessori for their children. The Montessori curriculum is unique because it encourages children to maximize their natural talents and interests.

This study has discussed a few major topics related to customer satisfaction. Still, all kinds of literature on parental satisfaction with Montessori education are discussed. They are derived from websites, articles, books, and journals to aid in the citation for the literature review. There are many review studies and sources for literature reviews; each review shows a summarized conclusion. The entire literature review was comparable, and related topics were carried out. Montessori education is the most powerful way of teaching children to friendly learning environment worldwide today (Lewa, 2018).

Montessori education also develops natural teaching growth, using various materials such as hand materials, and understanding basic mathematics and science (Montessori, 2014). According to Chen and Guo (2021), Montessori education includes culturally innovative respect for children, joy, and a prepared environment comprising outdoor and indoor activities and hands-on materials that meet specific learning needs and encourage positive brain development. The Five-point Likert scale measurement scale was used to examine parental satisfaction with Montessori. Similarly, Montessori classrooms were designed to be self-directed environments that aided in developing children's independence. Some classrooms use only Montessori materials, while others supplement Montessori materials with commercially available materials such as puzzles and games (Lillard & Heise 2016).

The study of Pihanperä, Lepistö & Ruokonen (2022) on the literature review of parent satisfaction shows that parents were motivated by the principal's attractiveness, practical knowledge, the attractive classroom environment, and the emphasis on children's long-term outcomes. Modern educators must constantly adjust their work based on their knowledge and overall understanding of children. If the Montessori schooling environment is supportive, all students are more likely to achieve academic success. The principle of children's learning and contributing to the development of an institutional environment has to be understood. This available answer to Montessori teacher's types of culture promotes children's culture. Daily, encouraging individual children through self-determination, positive awareness, and acquiring new skills also influences parental satisfaction in Montessori schools. It predicts parents' satisfaction positively with Montessori services embedded in administrative, teacher teaching qualifications, facilities, and a friendly environment (Miljevic-Riddick et al., 2013).

The implications of this research are crucial for parents, Montessori school owners, researchers, educators, scholars, policymakers, and academicians to foreground the current situation of Pre-schools in Nepal. These effective schools with a positive school climate have concentrated on reaching out to their students' families to develop good cooperation. Montessori schools succeed when a strong and positive relationship is established between students, parents, teachers, and the community (Ebner & Ebner 2022).

The topic of parental satisfaction on Montessori Education in Nawalparasi basically motivated me to show the current parent's beliefs in Montessori education rather than traditional education and understand whether pre-schools have followed the teaching pedagogy based on Montessori education connecting with parental satisfaction. This author wants to know whether Montessori schools are using Facebook pages, YouTube, TikTok, websites, articles, and news are using or not to understand the main reason for parental attraction to Montessori education. The problem of my best friend, whose children attend a Montessori school, inspired me to consider and investigate the parents' satisfaction with Montessori education. As I read and observed the changes in their child's physical, mental, and observed goal objectives, I became more interested in examining parental satisfaction with their educational quality.

Early Childhood Education in Nepal

Early childhood is considered a crucial period of human life which lays the foundation for the future (Kopila 2009). Nonetheless, early childhood education and development (ECED) services are not fully developed within the Nepali context. A key factor is that the geographical structure creates rural and urban divisions that affect the education of young children. According to the Central Bureau of Statistics (2012), "Literacy rates are substantially higher in urban areas (64%) than in rural areas (36%)". So, the school attendance rate for rural areas is also lower than in urban areas, even though every child is entitled to attend school free of charge. The fact that school attendance is not mandated or enforced is a probable explanation for this fact. Traditionally, gender discrimination, illiteracy, the persistence of poverty and traditional social beliefs have also acted as barriers to Nepalese children's educational development (Pant, Nepal 2010); these barriers persist in rural parts of contemporary Nepal.

According to the Department of Education, there are 35,991 Early Childhood Development and Pre-Primary classes in operation (Department of Education 2015). In rural areas, the number of kindergartens is low in government-funded institutions or kindergartens run by the private sector. Only 3,412 Early Childhood Development and Pre-Primary classes are in operation in the Mountain region (Department of Education 2015). Similarly, in the Hill, there are 15,671 and, in the Valley, – 1,989 Early Childhood Development and Pre-primary classes in operation with government support and the private sector (Department of Education 2015). In the Terai area, 14,929 Early Childhood Development and Pre-primary classes are in operation, supported by the government and private sector. However, kindergarten education provided by the government and the private sector creates social gaps as public kindergartens are mainly Nepali-speaking.

In contrast, private kindergarten education is mainly provided via English, highly prized as the language of social mobility. Thus, while in private kindergartens, "the cost of attending is a major barrier to access" (Education International 2010), many parents want their children to learn English and make every effort to enrol their children in private kindergartens. In this article, I discuss the quality of early childhood education and development within the Nepali context, the barriers to its development, and why professionalism within the ECED workforce is a vision that has yet to be realized.

In Nepal, many Montessori Schools are profit motive rather than parents' satisfaction, so parents could not get adequate facilities and prompt responses from teachers and staff. Many children are initially admitted based on the mouth-to-mouth commitments between school administration and parents. Still, parents do not get any consistency between school promise and actual achievement during their children's study in Montessori Schools.

Objectives of this study

The objectives of the study include the following:

- Establish the level of parents' satisfaction with the behaviour and roles of office staff and receptionists.

- Examine if there is a difference in satisfaction with pre-primary education facilities between parents of children in private pre-primary schools.
- Determine if there is a difference in parents' satisfaction with the behaviour and roles of pre-primary education teachers.

Primary research question

1. *What is the association between the facilities of Montessori schools and parents' expectations of their children's education quality?*

Secondary research questions

- 1.1 *What is the association between the behaviour and roles of office staff and reception of Montessori schools and parental satisfaction with their children's education quality?*
- 1.2 *What is the association between the facilities of Montessori schools and parental satisfaction with their children's education quality?*
- 1.3 *What is the association between the behaviour and roles of Montessori teachers and parental satisfaction with their children's education quality?*

The following null hypotheses were tested at a significance level of 0.05:

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in satisfaction with the behaviour and roles of office staff and receptionists

Ho₂: There is no significant difference in satisfaction with pre-primary education facilities between parents of children in private pre-primary schools.

Ho₃: There is no difference in parents' satisfaction with the behaviour and roles of pre-primary education teachers.

Rational of this study

The rationale of this study is based on adding the new literature in the Nawalparasi district to begin the discussion of the Montessori Education quality and facilities. The present condition of Montessori education is still in the beginning phase and needs to improve its quality, facilities, teachers' capability and teaching and learning resources. This study would be a milestone to break through the academic discussion in our society in order to improve the quality, facilities, and teachers' teaching skills and increase teaching and learning resources in Montessori Schools.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This review was based on parent's satisfaction with Montessori school's education regarding the behaviour and roles of office staff and receptionists, the facilities of Montessori schools and the behaviour and roles of Montessori teachers. The key focus of this literature was to analyze the previous findings on the parent's satisfaction regarding Montessori schools. A few topics can be found on various websites where various journals, books, theses, articles, and some reviews can be found. Their views of websites, articles, books, and journals were discovered to assist in the literature review citation. The ten review studies and sources are analyzed; each showing the publication years, objectives, findings, methods used, and convergent results are summarized (see Table 1).

Table 1: finding of the previous study of parents' satisfaction towards Montessori educational quality

Author and publication year	Objectives	Methods used	Findings	Convergence
Parker(2007)	To examine if parents' educational choices correspond to their reasons for selecting Montessori schooling and the impact of family income and ethnicity on their preference for Montessori.	The mixed methods approach	The results indicate that assisting parents in selecting Montessori school options due to practical education, creative mind, friendly environment, and proper care of each child is embedded in parental satisfaction in Montessori schools.	The results highlighted that parents choose Montessori for practical education, creative activities, individual care of their payment-based system, and a friendly environment. Physical activities, feeding systems, safety and security, teacher teaching quality, and play were also found to be areas of satisfaction with the Montessori education system by the researchers.
Schmidt et al. (2009)	To help make Montessori education available to as many children as possible.	Descriptive Research Method	The results highlighted that understanding and assisting the natural process of child development and learning is connected with parental satisfaction. It further indicates that creating Montessori outdoor and indoor areas with hands-on materials that meet specific learning needs and encourage positive brain development is embedded in parental satisfaction.	
Xanthavanij & Eamoraphan (2019)	To identify parental satisfaction with the quality of education. To determine if there was a significant difference between parents' satisfaction with the quality of education according to their demographics.	Conceptual Model	The results show that analyzing parents' satisfaction with the Montessori education system in various areas, such as physical activities, safety and security, the Montessori feeding system, teaching-learning and play materials,	

Author and publication year	Objectives	Methods used	Findings	Convergence
Mustafa (2016)	To identify the relationship between six service quality dimensions and the parents' satisfaction in the community development department (KEMAS) pre-school in Tanjong Malim district.	SEROQUEL Model	The results highlighted that progressing in intelligence, social-emotional development, learning something new, health, and promotion as a learning environment are supportive factors of parental satisfaction.	
Mustafa et al. (2014)	To parents, as well as strengthen their services while facing the challenges in Montessori pre-school.	Integrated framework	The previous study indicates that providing parents' preferred marketing strategies for Montessori using 7p's service for better marketing satisfied the parents in Montessori schools.	
Ackerman (2019)	To support a network of high-quality, full-scholarship, Montessori-inspired pre-schools in underserved communities.	Traditional Montessori approach	The results show that directly teaching knowledge and skill to most children curious about Mathematics and science-related questions and helping with creative work was connected with parents' satisfaction.	
Hiles (2018)	To examine why parents, decide to enrol their children in Montessori schools.	Descriptive Research Method	The results highlighted those motivating parents to Choose Montessori for the appeal of the Montessori activities system, the classroom environment, and the primary focus on long-term child outcomes were related to parents' satisfaction.	
Dahari (2011)	To identify the important factors that contribute most to parents' choice of pre-school for their children.	Descriptive Research Method	The previous study disclosed that assisting parents in selecting a Montessori school based on key factors (privately run institutions, safety and security, and food quality) was embedded with parents' satisfaction.	
Ebner (2022)	They followed their chosen Montessori teaching vocations to examine the joyful paths.	Experimental Research	It was found that encouraging individual children through self-determination, positive awareness, and the acquisition of new skills daily helped satisfy parents in Montessori schools.	
Hu et al. (2020)	To investigate the association between parents' perceptions of home-school partnership and parental satisfaction with pre-school services.	Correlation study	It was discovered that predicting parents' satisfaction positively with Montessori services on different levels (administrative, teacher teaching qualification, facilities, and friendly environment) were related to parental satisfaction in Montessori schools.	

Parker (2007) highlighted that Montessori school options due to practical education, creative mind, friendly environment, and proper care of each child to assist parents in selecting Montessori schools. Similarly, Schmidt (2009) stated that to create a Montessori environment, outdoor and indoor areas must be filled with hands-on materials that meet specific learning needs and encourage positive brain development.

Furthermore, Xanthavanij (2019) indicated the level of parental satisfaction with the system and various areas (physical activities, safety and security, the Montessori feeding system, teaching-learning and play materials, and data analysis) using a five-point Likert scale must be considered. Moreover, Mustafa (2016) stated that to develop children's activities, intelligence, social-emotional development, learning something new, health, and promotion as a learning environment must develop children. Mustafa (2014) highlighted that Montessori uses 7p's service for better marketing to provide parents with preferred marketing strategies. Likewise, Ackerman (2019) found that teaching specific knowledge skills to most children interested in Mathematics and science-related questions supported creative work. Most importantly, Hiles (2018) indicated that the Montessori activities system, classroom environment, and primary focus on long-term child outcomes motivate parents to choose Montessori for various reasons.

However, Dahari (2011) clarified that key factors such as privately run institutions, safety and security, and food quality could help parents choose a Montessori school. Indeed, Ebner (2022) highlighted the significance of encouraging individual children through self-determination, positive awareness, and the acquisition of new skills daily. Hu (2020) found that administrative, teacher teaching qualifications, facilities, and a friendly environment positively predicted parents' satisfaction with Montessori services (see table 1).

3. METHODS AND MATERIALS

'Ontological and epistemological assumptions of this study

A framework must consider how philosophy fits into the design of the quantitative method. This author likes to apply Crotty's (1998) conceptualization to position philosophy within a quantitative methodology. Paradigm (beliefs: epistemology, ontology), theoretical lens (social science theories), methodological approach (integrated methods approach), and methods (the survey) of data collection. Postpositivist worldview, Constructivist worldview, Participatory worldview and Pragmatist worldview are four applicable worldviews (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011). All these four worldviews have the same components but take different stances on these components. Worldviews differ in social

reality (Ontology), how people gain knowledge of what they know (epistemology), and the role values play in research (axiology).

Similarly, the process of research (methodology), and the language of research (rhetoric) are different elements of the four worldviews. Methods of data collection help inform the problems under study. This study has followed Positivist worldviews typically associated with a quantitative approach.

The Positivism worldview focuses on the consequences of research. The primary importance of the question asked rather than the methods to inform the problems under the positivism study. Thus, it is pluralistic and oriented toward what works and practices are required (Cohen et al. 2011). In a postpositivist study, the investigators work from the top down, from theory to hypothesis to data, to add or contradict the theory (Creswell & Plano Clark 2011).

Quantitative method

The quantitative method is a research strategy that quantifies data collection and analysis. It is built on a deductive approach, emphasizing theory testing. It's basically making observations about something unknown, unexplained, or new. It helps to investigate the current theory surrounding the problem of this study (Adhikari 2022). This study has applied the quantitative research method because it is more accurate and reliable as it involves studying and analyzing the data using numbers rather than texts (Eriksson & Kovalainen, 2008). This method tries to identify cause-effect correlations between variables similar to genuine experiments, but there are some significant distinctions between them (Winston-Salem State University, 2022). The participants answered five-point Likert-type questions.

The survey instruments

The survey instrument answered three objectives of this study. The first research question answered the behaviour and roles of office staff and receptionists. Similarly, the facility of the Montessori school was answered by the second research question. Finally, the third research question answered the behaviour and roles of Montessori teachers. The survey collected from parents' responses to achieve the study's fixed objectives. The Montessori schools of Nawalparasi were first contacted by email. In the

second phase, they were requested to provide their contact number when they replied to this author's first email. In the third stage, the permission of schools was requested. They all agreed to meet them and discuss this research's importance.

In the fourth phase, Montessori schools were randomly selected for the further process of data collection. After their selection, this author requested with school administration to provide parents' contact details. When this author got information from schools about parents, parents were sent a consent form to participate in this research. After the parents' acceptance, this author decided to go for the questionnaire distribution. Before sending the questionnaire, five parents were sent the survey questionnaire for pilot survey. After the pilot study, some minor correction was made and sent the questionnaire to parents by email. The total population of parents was unknown, but this author sent 220 questionnaires to the parents, but only 200 questionnaires were returned by the returnees (N =200).

The behaviour and roles of office staff and receptionists, the facilities provided by Montessori schools, and the behaviour and roles of Montessori teachers, and identifying trends and patterns in data will not go so far as to prove the reasons for these observed patterns. This study employs the random sampling method to select the study's sample size. Four Montessori schools were chosen to find teachers, parents, and school staff (e.g., Kakhara Montessori, Smile Kids Montessori Pre-School, S.S. Nike tan Montessori, and Evergreen Montessori). The study's total sample was one thousand (N = 1000). But the total sample population was two hundred (n = 200). Everyone has an equal opportunity to participate in this study. Data were collected from four sampled Montessori schools in Gaindakot 1 and 2. But Montessori children range in age from three to six years old, and this study's data is based on parent satisfaction, which was obtained when parents provided data about their children education in Montessori schools (Blog, 2022).

Data Analysis

This study uses the reduction of the factors dimension method to find the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and similar variables in the survey instrument. PCA is a statistical measurement tool used to determine the strength of a link between two or more

variables. Relationship between and among the few facts are sought and understood in PCA. The Binary Logistic Regression research is used to find the association between the independent and dependent variables.

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was based on the subscales and independent variables of Binary Logistic Regression Analysis. The dependent variable was parents' satisfaction with Montessori educational quality. Questionnaires were used to collect primary data using regression and correlation and then presented using tables created with the data analysis programs Spss and Excel. Furthermore, the study's geographical scope was limited to Gaidakot-1 and 2 areas, only analyzed using regression and correlation, and then presented using tables created with the data analysis programs SPSS and Excel.

Descriptive analytics is the process of identifying trends and relationships in current and historical data. It comes in four varieties. Measures of Frequency Count, Percent, Frequency, and using this to show how frequently a response is given. Measures of Central Tendency (Mean, Median, and Mode, and using this to show how an average or most commonly indicated response), Measures of Dispersion or Variation (Range, Variance, Standard Deviation, and to show how "spread out" the data are), and Measures of Position (Percentile Ranks, Quartile Ranks and to compare scores to a normalized score) were applied in the data analysis phase(Lab, 2018). The KMO values are also presented (see Table 3).

Regression analysis is a statistical method used to show the relationship between two or more than two variables, usually a dependent variable and an independent variable. The analysis was linked to the relationship between the behaviour and roles of office staff and receptionists, the relation between the facilities of Montessori schools, and the relation between the behaviour and roles of Montessori teachers and parents' satisfaction in Montessori schools in this study. The results show that the analysis's first research question has two variables: "the behaviour and roles of office staff and receptionist" as an independent variable and "parents' satisfaction in Montessori schools" as a dependent variable. Similarly, the analysis of the second research question was based on the facilities of Montessori schools" The following question number third has the independent variable being "the behaviour and roles of Montessori teachers", and the

dependent variable is parents' satisfaction in Montessori schools.

Table 2. Research questions, subscales, number of variables in each scale, and regression

Research question	Scales	Subscales	Number of variables	PCA of Regression Analysis
Main research question				REGR 1: The Behaviour and roles of Office staff and receptionist
First question	Five-point Likert type	1. The behaviour and roles of Office staff and receptionist	6	REGR 2: The personal influence of Montessori members
		2. The personal influence of Montessori members	2	REGR 3: The Facilities of Montessori schools
		1. The facilities of Montessori schools	4	REGR 4: The Influence of Montessori quality
		2. The influence of Montessori quality	4	REGR 5: The Behaviour and roles of Montessori teachers
Second question				REGR 6: The duties and responsibilities of Montessori teachers
Third question		1. The behaviour and roles of Montessori teachers	4	
		2. The duties and responsibilities of Montessori teachers	3	

4. MAIN RESULTS

The results of this study were based firstly on the factor reduction method of principal component analysis (PCA). Secondly, the results were based on subscale descriptive analysis to find parents' satisfaction based on the behaviour and roles of office staff and receptionists, Montessori schools' facilities, and teachers' roles and behaviour.

Thirdly, the results were based on gender differences on each of the scales of the PCA. Fourthly, the results were based on determining the impact of the overall roles and activities of Montessori schools on parents' satisfaction. Under the first main research question, three sub-chapters were designed. The quantitative results were analyzed and presented in each subsection. The result confirmed that the percentage of female (57.5%) respondents is higher than that of male respondents (42.5%). Two hundred children (n=200) completed the questionnaire and shared their opinions on parents' satisfaction with Montessori schools.

Table 3. Mean, Standard deviation and Alpha values of the behaviour and roles of office staff and receptionists, Montessori schools' facilities, and teachers' roles and behaviour on parents' satisfaction (N = 200).

Subscale	Mean	Std	Alpha	variances	KMO and Bartlett's Test
The behaviour and roles of office staff/receptionists	2.238	.49439	.765	39.561	
The personal influence of Montessori staff	2.705	.79285	.671	15.653	.778
The facilities of Montessori schools	2.745	.57205	.696	28.508	
The influence of Montessori quality	2.605	.50336	.601	20.819	.641
The behaviour and roles of Montessori teachers	2.515	.59502	.755	43.747	
The duties and responsibilities of Montessori teachers	2.181	.56691	.706	15.632	.725

The results indicated that the mean value of the first subscale, the behaviour and roles of the office staff and receptionist, is (2.23 < 3) of six subscales is lower than the mid-value (3), signifying that respondents disagreed with the statements on the behaviour and roles of office staff and receptionist, staff being available to speak with parents, phone calls answered promptly and respectfully, being satisfied with the office staff/receptionist, assisting them in understanding their child's needs, and being greeted with courtesy and respect when they visited the school.

Similarly, the mean value of the second subscale, the personal influence of Montessori members, is (2.70 < 3) of six subscales, which is lower than the mid-value (3). It includes that respondents disagreed with the statements that all staff members were well educated and treat them as an equal Montessori team member. Furthermore, the mean value of the third subscale, the facilities of Montessori schools (2.74 < 3), was

lower than the mid-value (3). It indicates that respondents disagreed with the statements about classrooms and playgrounds being smartly updated, that they were satisfied with the school facilities in terms of all necessities, that the school's exterior appearance is clean and neat, and that the children's class activities are displayed throughout the schools. Moreover, the mean value of the fourth subscale's influence of Montessori quality on the (2.60 < 3) of six subscales was lower than the mid-value (3), indicating that respondents disagreed with the statement that a transportation helper is available to support children's health needs. Signs direct students to their destinations, and the school's interior are neat and organized. The results show that the mean value of the fifth subscale of six subscales (2.51 < 3) was lower than the mid-value (3), indicating that respondents disagreed with the statement about parents being satisfied with their child's teachers and the principal being available to address their concerns. All of the teachers are certified and child friendly.

After all, the mean value of the sixth subscale (2.18 < 3) was lower than the mid-value (3), indicating that respondents disagreed with the statement that the child's or children's teacher treats parents courteously and respectfully. When parents have concerns about their child or children, they are thoroughly addressed, and the teacher is readily available (see Table 3). The results of the parent's independent t-test indicate that there was no difference between the satisfaction with Montessori schooling gender-wise.

4.1 The behaviour and roles of office staff and receptionist

What is the association between the behaviour and roles of office staff and reception of Montessori schools and parental satisfaction with their children's education quality?

Table 4. Summary table of block 1 models

Model	Chi-square	Df	Sig.	Cox and snell's R Square	Nagelkerke's R square	-2loig-likelihood
Omnibus tests of model coefficients	3.614	2	.164	.018	.024	268.502
Hosmer and Lemeshow test	13.547	8	.094			

The results evaluated the tabulated data of block 1 are included in the model. Two more tables are generated to compare this model with the base model. The omnibus tests of model coefficient and Hosmer and Lemeshow test model table give the value of Chi-

square. It also gives degrees of freedom, associated significance level, Cox and Snell & R Square, Nagelkerke's R Square, and -2 log-likelihood used to examine whether including an additional covariate is significant. The value of Chi-square indicates that change in value of -2LL (log-likelihood) from the base model to the present model. If Chi-square static is positive, it shows a decrease in deviance in the prediction of y from the previous/ base model; if it is negative, it shows an increase in deviance. Since the Chi-square is 3.614 and no associated significance level is more than 0.05, the present model shows a decrease in deviance from the base model. As Hosmer and Lemeshow test, the Chi-square is 13.547, and the associated significance level is more than 0.05. The present model shows a decrease in deviance from the base model.

The second item was 2-lig-likelihood, which examines multiple models and determines which best describes the data. Because this is a single model, no comparison can be drawn. The effect size shown by Cox and Snell & R Square value is .018, and Nagelkerke's & R-square value is .024, indicating a better fit. According to Camp man (2017), Nagelkerke's & R Square modify the Cox and Snell R square mathematics to potentially allow the value to reach 1. That is why Nagelkerke's R-square is used in this study.

Table 5. The binary model to predict parents' satisfaction with Montessori school quality (N =200)

Independent variables	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95% C.I. for EXP(B)	
							Lower	Upper
The behaviour of office staff/receptionists	.138	.147	.881	1	.348	1.148	.861	1.531
The personal influence of Montessori staff	-.239	.146	2.688	1	.101	.788	.592	1.048
Constant	-.329	.145	5.156	1	.023	.720		

The variables in the equation table show its estimated B, standard error, Wald statistics, degree of freedom, significance level and exponential. The squared ratio of the estimated coefficient to its standard error is Wald statistics and is used to examine the significance of parameters. As tabulated, the significant value of the independent variable is less than 0.05; the parameters are significant. As the value of p is greater than .05, the variables are not significant with the dependent variables. The largest odds value among them is 1.148. it did not show significance ($p > 0.05$).

4.2. The facilities of the Montessori schools

What is the association between the facilities of Montessori schools and parental satisfaction with their children's education quality?

Table 6. Summary table of block 1 models

Model	Chi-square	df	Sig.	Cox and snell's R Square	Nagelkerke's R square	-2loig-likelihood
Omnibus tests of model coefficients	49.885	2	.000	.221	.297	222.232
Hosmer and Lemeshow test	14.189	8	.077			

The results indicate that the Chi-square is 49.885, and no associated significance level is less than 0.05. The present model shows a decrease in deviance from the base model. As Hosmer and Lemeshow test, the Chi-square is 14.189, and the associated significance level is less than 0.05. Therefore, this model is a better fit compared to the base model. The effect size shown by Cox and Snell & R Square value is .221, and Nagelkerke's & R-square value is .297, indicating a better fit in the present model.

Table 7. The binary model to predict parents' satisfaction with Montessori school quality (N =200)

Independent variables	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95% C.I. for EXP(B)	
							Lower	Upper
The facilities of Montessori schools	-.983	.193	25.876	1	.000	.374	.256	.546
The influence of Montessori quality	-.773	.178	18.849	1	.000	.462	.326	.654
Constant	-.408	.165	6.134	1	.013	.665		

The results show the significant value of the independent variable is less than 0.05; the parameters are significant. The odds value of .462 is greater than that of other variables. The results show a significant association between the facilities of Montessori schools ($p < 0.05$, $B = -.983$, $odds = .374$) and Montessori facilities ($p < 0.05$, $B = .773$, $odds = .462$), indicating the negative impact on parental satisfaction. The results further show an association between the Montessori quality and parental' satisfaction in Nawalparasi district, Nepal ($p > 0.05$).

4.3. Teachers' roles and behaviour with parents

What is the association between the behaviour and roles of Montessori teachers and parental satisfaction with their children's education quality?

Table 8. Summary table of block 1 models

Model	Chi-square	df	Sig.	Cox and snell's R Square	Nagelkerke's R square	-2log-likelihood
Omnibus tests of model coefficients	17.358	2	.000	.083	.112	254.759
Hosmer and Lemeshow test	10.146	8	.255			

The results show that the Chi-square is 17.358, no associated significance level is less than 0.05, and the present model shows a decrease in deviance from the base model. As Hosmer and Lemeshow test, the Chi-square is 10.146, and no associated significance level is less than 0.05. Therefore, this model is a better fit compared to the base model. The second item was 2-log-likelihood, which examines multiple models and determines which best describes the data. Because this is a single model, no comparison can be drawn. The effect size shown by Cox and Snell's R Square value is .083, and Nagelkerke's R-square value is .112, indicating a better fit.

Table 9. The binary model to predict parents' satisfaction with Montessori school quality (N = 200)

Independent variables	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp- p(B)	95% C.I. for EXP(B)	
							Lower	Upper
The behaviour and roles of Montessori teachers	-.614	.163	14.104	1	.000	.541	.393	
The duties and responsibilities of Montessori teachers	-.184	.151	1.489	1	.222	.832	.618	.746
Constant	-.339	.150	5.119	1	.024	.713		1.118

The results show its estimated B, standard error, Wald statistics, degree of freedom, significance level and exponential. The results confirm the significant value of the independent variable is less than 0.05; the parameters are significant. The results indicate a significant and positive association between the behaviour and roles of Montessori teachers and parental satisfaction ($p < 0.05$, $B = -.614$, odds = .541). The results also highlight no significant association between the duties and responsibilities of Montessori teachers and parental satisfaction in Nawalparasi district, Nepal ($p > 0.05$).

The Wholesome Regression Model

Table 10. Summary of block 1 models

Model	Chi-square	df	Sig.	Cox and smell's R Square	Nagelkerke R square	-2loig-likelihood
Omnibus tests of model coefficients	73.300	6	.000	.307	.413	198.817
Hosmer and Lemeshow test	11.667	8	.167			

The results show that the Chi-square is 73.300, no associated significance level is less than 0.05, and the present model shows a decrease in deviance from the base model. As Hosmer and Lemeshow test, the Chi-square is 11.667, and no associated significance level is more than 0.05; the present model shows a decrease in deviance from the base model. Therefore, this model is a better fit compared to the base model. The results confirm the effect size of Cox and Snell & R Square value is .307 and Nagelkerke's & R-square value is .413 indicating a better fit in the present model.

Table 11. The wholesome model to predict parents' satisfaction toward Montessori schools' facilities (N = 200)

Independent variables	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95% C.I.for EXP(B)	
							Lower	Upper
The behaviour and roles of Montessori staff/receptionists	.401	.202	3.960	1	.047	1.494	1.006	2.219
The personal influence of Montessori staff	-.022	.217	.011	1	.918	.978	.639	1.497
The facilities of Montessori schools	-1.024	.231	19.713	1	.000	.359	.229	.565
The influence of Montessori quality	-.895	.215	17.332	1	.000	.409	.268	.623
The behaviour and roles of Montessori teachers	-.862	.200	18.540	1	.000	.422	.285	.625
The duties and responsibilities of Montessori teachers	-.144	.185	.607	1	.436	.866	.602	1.244
Constant	-.489	.180	7.366	1	.007	.613		

The results confirm the significant value of the independent variable is less than 0.05; the parameters are significant. The odds value of 1.494 is greater than that of other variables, showing their significant association and a positive relation with the dependent variable. The results indicate a significant association between the facilities of Montessori schools ($p < 0.05$, $B = -1.024$, odds = .359), showing a positive impact on parental satisfaction. The results further indicate a significant association between the facilities of Montessori schools, the influence of Montessori education quality, the behaviour of Montessori staff and parental satisfaction ($p < 0.05$, $B = .895$, odds = .409),

indicating a negative impact on parental satisfaction (see Table 11). The result highlights no association between the behaviour and roles of office staff/receptionists and parental satisfaction in Nawalparasi district, Nepal ($p > 0.05$) (see Table 11).

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

My discussion is based on objectives and research questions about parents' satisfaction with Montessori education. This study has already presented three research questions based on the parents' satisfaction. This study's main focus was Montessori education and facilities. The quality and facilities of Montessori schools related to parents' satisfaction with Montessori schooling. This study was conducted with a survey administered instrument to the total sample was one thousand, but the total sample population was two hundred. Data were collected from four sampled Montessori schools in Gaidakot 1 and 2. The survey questionnaire was used to collect primary data and analyzed by using regression and correlation and then presented using tables created with the data analysis programs of SPSS and Excel.

The results indicate that the behaviour and roles of office staff and receptionist, the personal influence of Montessori members, the facilities of Montessori schools, the influence of Montessori quality, the behaviour and roles of Montessori teachers, and the duties and responsibilities of Montessori teachers were subscales of the survey variables. The mean values of facilities of Montessori schools have the highest mean value following the lowest mean value (2.161) of facilities of Montessori schools. The results also indicate that the data of this study was reliable and valid because the Alpha value was better (.601).

Similarly, the results show a significant association between the personal influence of Montessori members observing parents' satisfaction in Montessori schools, indicating a negative association with parents' satisfaction in Montessori schools ($p < 0.05$). Further, it shows that there was no association between these subscales. The results indicate a negative association between the facilities of Montessori schools with parents' satisfaction in Montessori schools (see Table 11). The results further indicate that that there was no association between the personal influence of Montessori members and the duties and responsibilities of Montessori teachers and parents' satisfaction. The

results further indicate a negative association between the duties and responsibilities of parents' satisfaction in Montessori schools (see Table 11).

First research question

What is the association between the behaviour and roles of office staff and reception of Montessori schools and parental satisfaction with their children's education quality?

The result shows a significant association between the behaviour and roles of office staff and receptionists of parents' satisfaction in Montessori schools, indicating a positive association with parents' satisfaction in Montessori schools ($p < 0.05$). Similarly, the results show a significant association between the personal influences of Montessori members observing parents' satisfaction in Montessori schools, indicating a negative association with parents' satisfaction in Montessori schools ($p < 0.05$). The study of Lillard, Meyer, Vasco & Fukuda (2021) and Schmidt, Schmidt & Syd Kruse (2009) supported this study and found that the behaviour and roles of office staff and reception of Montessori schools positively impact parental satisfaction in Montessori Education.

Second research question

What is the association between the facilities of Montessori schools and parental satisfaction with their children's education quality?

The result further indicates a significant association between the facilities of Montessori schools observing parents' satisfaction in Montessori schools, indicating the negative association with parents' satisfaction in Montessori schools ($p < 0.05$). Similarly, the results show that there was a significant association between the influence of Montessori quality on parents' satisfaction in Montessori schools, indicating a negative association with parents' satisfaction in Montessori schools ($p < 0.05$) (see Table 7). The current studies supported the previous studies of Xanthavanij and Eamoraphan (2019) and Mustafa et al. (2014), who found that parents' satisfaction with the Montessori education system in various areas was embedded in physical activities, safety and security, the Montessori feeding system, teaching-learning and play materials.

Third research question

What is the association between the behaviour and roles of Montessori teachers and parental satisfaction with their children's education quality?

The result further indicates a significant association between the behaviour and roles of Montessori teachers observing parents' satisfaction in Montessori schools, indicating a negative association with parents' satisfaction in Montessori schools ($p < 0.05$). Similarly, the results show a significant association between the duties and responsibilities of Montessori teachers and parents' satisfaction with Montessori school quality, indicating a negative association with parents' satisfaction in Montessori schools ($p < 0.05$). The current study is supported by Hu et al. (2020), who found that the behaviour and roles of Montessori teachers positively impact parental satisfaction in Montessori schools.

Recommendations

- Future research could focus on using the mixed methods approach to understand the multiple reality of the impact of the Montessori school's facilities on parents' satisfaction
- We can analyze and strengthen the findings using a larger sample size and more people and samples.
- More funding could lead to more stable and reliable data analysis in the research.
- It could be more than just academic research that contributes to Montessori advancement in the academe and other sectors.
- More time could have been spent on data collection, literature reviews, and in-depth research.
- The effects of Montessori programs on the learning outcomes of children from low-income families are also required in the future study.

Acknowledgement

I would also want to thank my mother, Mrs. Lal Maya Thapa (Gurung) and my father, Mr. Dhak Bahadur Gurung, including my aunty Ramkumari Thapa (Tamang), my uncle Kale Tamang, my close friend Sujayana Piya, my lovely brother Susan Gurung for their love and support in all of my extracurricular activities and for leading me in the correct

direction. I am grateful to Prof. Er. Hair Prasad Bhandari, my respected principal, for always supporting and helping me. Mr. Prem Sharma (HOD, BBA) has always planned and incorporated me in every vocational and practical knowledge. I would also like to thank everyone who participated in my survey.

REFERENCES

- Ackerman, D. J. (2019). The Montessori Preschool Landscape in the United States: Programmatic History Inputs, Availability, and Effects. *ETS Research Report Series*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ets2.12252>
- Adhikari, B. P. (2022). *An Investigation of the Impact on the Key Components of The Induction Programme on New Teacher Retention Intention in Chitwan district, Nepal* (pp. 1–337) [Dissertation]. An Investigation of the Impact on the Key Components of The Induction Programme on New Teacher Retention Intention in Chitwan district, Nepal
- Blog, F. (2022, February 18). *Survey Methods: Definition, Types, and Examples*. Available at
- Chapman, C., & Muijs, D. (2013). Collaborative School Turnaround: A Study of the Impact
- Chen, A., & Guo, S. L. (2021). The Spread of Montessori Education in Mainland China.
- Dahari, Z. B. D. (2011). *Factors influencing parent's choice of pre-school education in Malaysia: An exploratory study*.
- Ebner, R., & Ebner, H. (2022). Adlerian Lineage and Legacy: Mother, Montessori, and the Future. *The Journal of Individual Psychology*, 78(1), 122-127
- Educational Policy Studies Journal*, 3(2), 51–69. <https://doi.org/10.26529/cepsj.239>
- Eriksson, P., & Kovalainen, A. (2008). *Qualitative methods in business research*. London. SAGE Publications Ltd.
- Gibbons, S., & Silva, O. (2011). School quality, child well-being and parents' satisfaction. *Economics of Education Review*, 30(2), 312–331.
- Hiles, E. (2018). Parents' Reasons for Sending Their Child to Montessori Schools. *Journal of Montessori Research*, 4(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.17161/jomr.v4i1.6714>

<https://baselinesupport.campuslabs.com> and accessed on 26th November 2022

<https://baselinesupport.campuslabs.com>, and accessed on 26th November 2022

Hu, B. Y., Alexander, C. R., Wu, H., Roberts, S. K., & Li, Y. (2020). Exploring Home-School Partnership and Chinese Parental Satisfaction of Preschool Services: The Moderating Effect of Childrearing Beliefs. *Journal of Child and Family Studies*, 30(1), 206–219.

Journal of Montessori Research & Education, 3(1), 1–8.

Kindergarten Teacher Students' Opinions of their Role in Children's Lives. *Center for Koirala*, B. N. (2019, January 30). *Reforming 'Nepal's education: Koirala says private schools will continue, but 'can't take' 100% 'profit' - OnlineKhabar English News*. Available at <https://english.onlinekhabar.com/reforming-nepals-education-koirala-says-private>, and accessed on 27th December, 2022.

Kopila (2009), a newsletter on Early Childhood Development. CERID/TU, with the support of UNICEF/Nepal 14

lab, C. (2018). *Types of Descriptive Statistics*. Baseline Help Center. Available at

Lab, C. (2018). *Types of Descriptive Statistics*. Baseline Help Center. Available at

Lewa, D. K. (2018). Parents' Perception on The Quality of Management of Public Pre-Primary Schools in Kilifi County, Kenya. Unpublished M. Ed Research Project, Kenyatta University.

Lillard, A. S., & Heise, M. J. (2016). An Intervention Study: Removing Supplemented

Lillard, A. S., Meyer, M. J., Vasc, D., & Fukuda, E. (2021). An Association between Montessori Education in Childhood and Adult Wellbeing. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.72194>.

Materials from Montessori Classrooms Associated with Better Child Outcomes. *Journal of Miljevic-Riddick*, R., Pahic, T., & Saric, M. (2013). A Croatian Study of Practitioners and *Montessori Research*, 2(1), 16. <https://doi.org/10.17161/jomr.v2i1.5678>

Montessori, M. (2014). *The Montessori method*. London. Transaction Publishers.

Mustafa, L. M. B. (2016). *Relationship between service quality dimensions and parents' satisfaction in Kemas pre-school lily Muliana Binti Mustafa dissertation submitted in fulfillment of the requirement for the degree of Master of Education*

(business management) (master by mixed mode research). Available at <https://ir.upsi.edu.my/files/docs> and accessed on November 28, 2022.

Mustafa, L. M., Yunus, N. K. Y., & Azman, M. N. A. (2014). An Overview of Private Pre-school in Malaysia: Marketing Strategies and Challenges. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 130, 105–113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.04.013>

Of School Federations on Student Outcomes. *Leadership and Policy in Schools*, 12(3), 200-

Omondi, A. M. (2013). Parental Satisfaction with The Quality of Pre-Primary Education in Bondo District, Siaya County, Kenya. *Undefined*. Available at <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Parental-Satisfaction-With-The-Quality-ofeducation> and accessed on November 22 2022.

Parents. Dog Ear Publishing, Llc.

Parker, D. E. (2007). *Navigating the social/cultural politics of school choice: why do parents choose Montessori? A case study*. Available at <https://libres.uncg.edu/ir/uncg/listing.aspx?id=1284> and accessed on November 28, 2022.

Parker, Deborah Evans. "Navigating the Social/Cultural Politics of School Choice.

Pihanperä, M., Lepistö, J., & Ruokonen, I. (2022). An Integrative Literature Review of University-Based Early Childhood Education and Care Centres within Early Childhood Teacher Education Settings. *Education Sciences*, 12(2), 141.

Schmidt, M., Schmidt, D., & Syd Kruse. (2009). *Understanding Montessori: a guide for parents*. Dog Ear Publishing, Llc.

UNICEF. (2019). A World Ready to Learn: Prioritizing quality early childhood education. Retrieved from <https://www.unicef.org/reports/a-worldready-to-learn-2019>, and accessed on November 22, 2022.

Winston-Salem State University. (2022). *Key Elements of a Research Proposal Quantitative*

with the Quality of Education According to Their Demographics in Palina Kindergarten, Bangkok, Thailand. *Scholar: Human Sciences*, 11(1), 99–99.

www.formpl.us and accessed on 26th November 2022

Xanthavanij, P., & Eamoraphan, S. (2019). A Comparative Study of Parental Satisfaction.

Relationship Between Internet Scrolling Habit and Social Media Marketing

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Received: November 19, 2022

Revised: December 20, 2022

Accepted: January 04, 2023

Published: January 29, 2023

How to cite this paper:

Piya, S. & Adhikari, B.P (2022).

Relationship Between Internet Scrolling Habit and Social Media Marketing

The OCEM Journal of Management, Technology & Social Sciences, 2(2), 81-102

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Journal. www.oxfordcollege.edu.np

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Originality: This paper is original and has not been published anywhere else

Paper type: Research paper

J.E.L. Classification: M (3), M (31)

Abstract

The previous study has concluded that internet scrolling is required to generate business, and social media employs psychological techniques to advertise for business purposes. The primary objective of this study was to investigate the opinions and experiences of bachelor's level students on the role of internet scrolling addiction impact on social media marketing. This study applied the quantitative approach and the survey instrument to collect data. The sample population was two hundred bachelor's level students at Oxford College of Engineering and Management. A random sampling method was used to select sample students among three thousand students

The results show a significant association between internet scrolling habits and observing social media marketing, implying a negative association with using social media marketing ($p < 0.05$). Similarly, there was a positive association between social media marketing and influence on chatting apps ($p < 0.05$). Further, the results indicated a negative association between time of activeness and the use of social media with social media marketing. This study's implication would benefit social media marketers, students, scholars, entrepreneurs and owners of social media marketing businesses.

Keywords: *Implication, higher-level students, Internet scrolling habit, positive and negative association, social media marketing,*

1. INTRODUCTION

The following topic, "Relationship Between Internet Scrolling Habit and Social Media Marketing", relates to the two independent variables internet scrolling habit (and social media marketing). Internet scrolling habit is the state of being dependent on a specific drug or activity, i.e., in order to examine different areas of a screen; scrolling is the activity of moving displayed text or graphics up, down, or across the screen (Wiederhold, 2018). The theme was a mash-up of numerous topics, ranging from scrolling habit reducing children's attention span to the relationship between scrolling habit and social media marketing. The issue was modified as a marketing student based on course selection and desire.

As a grown-up adult and a marketing student, I was always fascinated by how social media plays a role in reaching end users and how today's world's most pervasive problem, "scrolling habit," affects social media marketing. This focal point has created the possibility of going deeper into this subject. As a researcher, I was curious about how customers perceive social media marketing and how it affects their perception of a marketing brand. This research was an eager process to acknowledge the relationship that can be found between the two independent variables. The current scenario of the state depends upon our population using smartphones and the Internet daily, which results in marketers being innovative and acknowledging the current situation globally. This research solely focuses on the findings that help understand the relationship between those two variables. This research was held mainly because of my curiosity and the light leading me to know more about the two variables' relationship.

Internet scrolling has a positive as well as negative impact on social media marketing. Some of the positive effects of internet scrolling are that it lets the prospects get knowledge about the product or the services. It helps in online engagement, promoting the right content at the right time. Internet scrolling not only helps big and small brands creatively approach prospects with less monetary value but has helped every business flourish in the market with the help of social media marketing. (Cheung et al., 2020)

Every coin has two sides, so internet scrolling has its own drawbacks too. The major impact of internet scrolling on social media marketing is that the prospect is to be

conscious about their mental health, such as anxiety and depression, in the long term (Kwak et al., 2022). The mindless internet scrolling leads to a goldfish memory of the prospect, which leads the marketing sector to be quick and innovative while presenting their presence on the market to catch the attention of the prospects. (Stanton, 2017)

The topic itself is imprecise and broad regarding psychological difficulties and how everyone perceives them. The biggest issue encountered while selecting this topic was determining how to demonstrate that the two independent variables had a relationship rather than being both individual characters. Knowing and admitting how a person's mind works and how individuals perceive social media marketing was a challenge because "social media marketing" and "Internet Scrolling habit" are both individual and broader horizons of knowledge. The following challenge was to collect first hand data. My curiosity, trust, and motivation have come from my teachers, who helped me with this research. It has paved the route for mining resources for this research. People claim motivation occurs when you are over concerned with knowing how, where, what, and when an issue emerges. The same goes for the inspiration for this research. I've always had these questions on my mind, along with my professors, who have invariably inspired me, acknowledged my abilities, and trusted me with their resources (Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

An objective is a concise statement outlining a broad qualitative goal designed to propel the organization forward in a desired direction. Basically, it asks, "What do we want to do?" A well-worded objective is time-bound (doable in a quarter) and should inspire and capture the shared imagination of desired study. The primary objectives of this study were to investigate the opinions and experiences of higher-level students on the role of internet scrolling habit impact on social media marketing.

1. To examine the opinions on the purpose of internet scrolling habit and social media on higher-level students
2. To examine the relationship between social media factors and social media marketing

1.2 Primary research question

When a researcher carries out an investigation to collect original and first-hand data, it is called primary research question. The question that describes the main specific objective of this type of research is known as the primary research question (Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

1. *What is the association between the purpose of internet scrolling habit and social media marketing factors?*

1.1. *What is the association between scrolling habit and social media marketing?*

1.2. *What is the association between the use of social media and social media marketing?*

The following null hypothesis has been tested in this study.

H₀₁: There is no association between scrolling habit and social media marketing.

H₀₂: There is no association between the use of social media and social media marketing.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This review was based on the relationship between internet scrolling habit and social media marketing, the association between scrolling habit and social media marketing and the association between the use of social media and social media marketing. The critical factor was to enlighten the previous findings on the relationship between internet scrolling habit and social media marketing factors in high-level students. The review of this study is based on books, journals and a thesis found on various websites such as google scholar, research gate etc. A summary of similar findings is presented (see Table 1).

Table 1. Findings of previous studies on internet scrolling habit and social media marketing

AUTHOR AND PUBLICATION YEARS	METHODS	FINDINGS
Gomathi (2020)	Descriptive research design	The results found that internet scrolling is required to generate business, and social media employs psychological techniques. The results further show that the social media platform's "feed" feature, where users are continuously flooded with content, is built-in, and flow is constant and at a large scale

AUTHOR AND PUBLICATION YEARS	METHODS	FINDINGS
Lupinacci (2020) Azpeitia (2020) Bunce, Flens & Neiles (2020)	Quantitative and Qualitative research, thematic analysis and	The results acknowledged that social media draws interest and promotes active, measurable participation in an online community and mindless scrolling, resulting in a shorter consumer attention span.
Czmecci (2017) Huan Chen (2017)	Descriptive Qualitative research	The results show that the habit to looking via social media is not gender-specific; digital word of mouth is a must in social media marketing. To engage consumers of young age while scrolling habit, marketers should have pictures and some images.
Coker, Flight & Baima (2017)	Descriptive	The following writers concluded that the consumer has more control over the content.
Gaddefors & Tollqvist (2017)	Deductive	The result shows that the marketer can contain the consumer and build relationships with the consumer through emotional content. Three concepts must be acknowledged reasons for using social media, the customer path, and the intention to buy.
Alalwan, Rana., Dwivedi & Algharabat, Zarrella (2017)	Survey research methods	The research found that social media marketing trends are based on digital word of mouth, customer relation management, and performance. There is a waste of opportunities resulting from a lack of social media marketing awareness among businesses.

Different writers (Gomathi & Veeramani, 2022; Ludmila & Lupinacci, 2020) emphasized that social media uses psychological techniques to produce business; its platform's "feed" feature, where users are constantly swamped with content, is built-in, and flow is steady and on a huge scale to advertise. Similarly, the three writers (Lupinacci, 2020; Azpeitia, 2021; Bunce et al., 2010) have discussed social media drawing interest and promoting active, measurable participation in an online community.

Furthermore, mindless scrolling raises questions about whether it reached the intended audience and whether social media marketing techniques are effective in the eyes of scrolling habit in young consumers, as well as scrolling habit affecting social media marketing, resulting in a shorter consumer attention span. Çizmecci (2017) and Chen (2017) highlighted that social media habit is not gender-specific. Only young consumers and college students don't need to use social media marketing as an approved celebrity and digital word-of-mouth. Marketers must have some image to engage young consumers addicted to scrolling online.

Many authors (Coker et al., 2017; Gaddefors & Tollqvist, 2017) highlighted that consumers have more control over the content, and Marketers should be able to satisfy Consumers by building relationships with Consumers through emotional content. Consumer intention is the main factor in social media marketing, resulting in Three concepts that must be acknowledged reasons for using social media, the customer path, and intention to buy. The trend of social media marketing on digital word of mouth, customer relationship management, performance, and social media marketing issues are current indicators of internet scrolling. It is a waste of opportunities caused by organizations' lack of social media marketing understanding (Alalwan et al. 2017; Zarrella 2009).

The primary goal of this study was to examine the attainment of social media marketing among college students and determine whether scrolling habit is related to the trend of social media marketing among college students. The studies mentioned above are critical for anyone directly or indirectly involved in social media marketing and anyone who uses a smartphone daily. Being a marketing student who is always interested in technological advancements in the marketing field is represented in this study. The study is quite important in my life because it serves as a stepping stone for me in this research field. This research is very important to me since it provides an educational and life-changing platform for me to be heard as a capable individual.

3. METHODOLOGY

Research paradigm is connected with (beliefs: epistemology, ontology), theoretical lens (social science theories), methodological approach (Quantitative methods approach), and methods (the survey) of data collection (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011). Worldviews differ in social reality (Ontology), how people gain knowledge of what they know (epistemology), and the role values play in research (axiology).

Similarly, the process of research (methodology), and the language of research (rhetoric) are different elements of the four worldviews. Methods of data collection help inform the problems under study. This study has followed Positivist worldviews typically associated with a quantitative approach. The Positivism worldview focuses on

the consequences of research. The primary importance of the question asked rather than the methods to inform the problems under the positivism study. Thus, it is pluralistic and oriented toward what works, and practices are required (Cohen et al. 2011).

Quantitative research method

Quantitative research is a research strategy that quantifies data collecting and analysis. It is built on a deductive method, emphasizing theory testing. It basically makes my observations about something unknown, unexplained, or new and investigates current theories surrounding my problem or issue. Descriptive, correlational, causal-comparative or quasi-experimental, and experimental are four quantitative research methods (Cohen et al. 2011). It tries to identify cause-effect correlations between dependent and independent variables. This study has used the survey method of a quantitative approach (Winston-Salem State University, 2022)

The study uses the correlation method of the quantitative research approach. Statistical data is used to determine the strength of a link between two or more variables. Relationships between and among a number of facts are sought and understood in this design style. This approach identify trends and patterns in data, but it not go so far as to prove the reasons for these observation patterns because observational research does not rely on cause and effect. Only collected data, relationships, and variable distributions are embedded in this quantitative approach (Creswell & Piano Clark 2011; Winston-Salem State University, 2022).

The strength of quantitative research is more accurate and reliable data as it involves studying and analyzing the data in the form of numbers, not in texts (Winston-Salem State University, 2022).

The survey method

This study has applied the survey study, which uses a process, tools, and techniques to collect information or data from a certain designated set of people. This method allows me to gather data from a large sample size or research population, helps me improve the validity and accuracy of my findings and is a convenient method of data collection for the researcher and the respondents. The cross-sectional survey covers a series of

structured questions linked to the research that were closed-ended questions with rating scales and semantic scales in this study. The survey was conducted at the Oxford College of Engineering and Management. The total sample size was 3000 students, with 200 samples chosen at random from all semesters of all three faculties (BBA, BCA, and Engineering)—having 200 data points ensures that the results obtained from my sample are close to what would have been collected if the entire population had been measured. It gives all units in the population an equal chance of being chosen. (Blog, 2022). Data concerning this research was collected personally through a 5-point Likert scale (i.e., strongly disagree, disagree, I do not know, agree, and strongly agree).

Data Analysis

My data analysis is based on mainly primary research question entitled *What is the association between the purpose of internet scrolling habit and social media marketing factors?*

Descriptive statistical tools have been used to analyze the survey data, identifying trends and relationships in currently collected primary data. It comes in four varieties. Measures of Frequency (count, percentage, frequency, and using this to show how frequently a response is given), measures of central tendency (Mean), using tool shows how an average or most commonly indicated response), Measures of Dispersion or variation (Standard Deviation) that show how "spread out" the data are), and measures of position (comparing the mean value of two independent t-Test) that score to a normalized score (Lab 2018).

The survey collected the bachelor's students' responses to achieve the study's fixed objectives. The BCA, BBA and Engineering department heads were first contacted by email. In the second phase, they were requested to provide their students' contact emails when they replied to this author's first email. In the third stage, the permission of departments was requested. Three departments agreed to meet them and discuss this research's importance.

In the fourth phase, students of different departments were randomly selected for the further process of data collection. When this author got information from different departments about students' information, a consent form was sent to participate in this

research. After the students' acceptance, this author decided to go for the questionnaire distribution. Before sending the questionnaire, ten students were sent the survey questionnaire to pilot it. After the pilot study, some minor correction was made and sent the questionnaire to parents by email. The total population of parents was unknown, but this author sent two hundred fifteen (N = 215) questionnaires to the students, but only 200 questionnaires were returned by the returnees (N =200).

The data was initially uploaded in the SPSS of version 26 and cleared the data. After clearing the data, the analysis began with the dimension reduction method. After this process, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was applied to find the subscales of categorized variables in the Rotated Component Matrix. After that each variable of the principal component (subscale) was recorded further to calculate each subscale's mean and standard deviation. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is a statistical approach that allows us to summarise the information in huge data tables using a smaller collection of "summary indices" that may be more readily displayed and studied. PCA aids in data interpretation, although it does not always detect key patterns (Creswell & Plano Clark 2011). Principal component analysis (PCA) reduces the complexity of multidimensional data while preserving trends and patterns. It accomplishes this by reducing the data to fewer dimensions that serve as feature summaries (Lever et al., 2017).

The PCA found seven subscales and seven independent variables: screen timing, use of social media, social networking site, app guidance, *audience preference*, *time of activeness on the Internet and the interesting factor of social media* (see Table 2). The primary purpose of using the Binary Logistic Regression Model (BLRM) was applied to find the impact of the independent variable (*screen timing, use of social media, social networking site, guidance of app, audience preference, time of activeness on the Internet and the interesting factor of social media*) on the dependent variable (**internet scrolling to social media marketing**). The primary purpose of using the regression model was to find the association between the dependent and independent variables.

Table 2. Research questions, subscales, number of variables in each scale, and regression factors (N = 200).

Research question	Scales	Subscales	Number of variables	PCA of Regression Analysis
Main research question	<i>What is the association between the purpose of internet scrolling habit and social media marketing factors?</i>			
First question	<i>What is the association between scrolling habit and social media marketing?</i>	1. Youth screen timing	6	REGR 1: Youth screen timing
		2. Use of social media	4	REGR 2: Use of social media
		1. Social networking site	5	REGR 1: Social networking site
		2. Guidance of app audience preference	3	REGR 2: Guidance of app audience preference
Second question	<i>What is the association between the use of social media and social media marketing?</i>	3. Time of activeness on the Internet	2	REGR 3: Time of activeness on the Internet
		4. The exciting factor of social media	3	REGR 4: The exciting factor of social media

Five-point Likert type

The result confirmed that the percentage of female (67%) respondents is higher than that of male respondents (33%). Two hundred students (N = 200) completed the questionnaire and shared their opinion on internet scrolling habit and social media marketing factors

4. RESULTS

Social media marketing (SMM) efficiently fosters communications between customers and marketers, enabling activities that enhance brand awareness. For that reason, SMM remains considered a new marketing strategy, but how it impacts intentions is limited. But, to date, a lot of research on SMM is focused on consumer behaviour,

creative strategies, content analysis and the benefits of user-generated content, and their relevance to creating virtual brand communities (Jamil et al., 2022).

Table 3. Mean, Standard deviation and Alpha value of the Internet scrolling habit and social media marketing on the relationship between them. (N=200)

Subscales	Mean	STD	Alpha	Variances	KMO and Bartlett's Test
Digital well-being	3.45	.770	.773	20.046	
Use of social media	1.88	.539	.60	11.455	.736
Social networking site	2.85	.741	.614	8.368	
Guidance of app	2.88	.821	.651	8.275	
Audience preference	2.51	.689	.633	7.907	.655
Time of activeness on the Internet	3.59	1.0867	.610	6.303	
The exciting factor of social media	2.44	.7014	.601	7.406	

For the result, we have a scale ranging from 1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree. As we can see from the tabulated data, the highest mean is digital well-being corresponding to $M = 3.45$, which indicates that the participants agree on spending more time on the internet scrolling through social media rather than engaging in physical activities, talking to friends, playing games, spending time with family, studying, and following international news and events.

The following measure of the variable "use of social media" makes clear that the majority of the research participants disagree with the statement that social media should be used for business, communication, education, or amusement. The mean value of 1.88, which is less (2), indicated that social media users disagree mostly on using social media for the following purposes: education, communication, business, entertainment, and news (See Table 3).

Similarly, the results and value estimation of the social media-related parameters are shown (see Table 3). The first tabulated mean value, 2.85, which is less than (3), shows that participants disagree on utilizing the social media platforms like Facebook, Instagram, and YouTube between 6 pm and 12 pm. As 2.85 can be rounded into three parts, most people believe that such social media platforms are used most of the time. Furthermore, with a mean estimate of 2.88 less than (3), it can be concluded that

participants are dissatisfied with being informed on how to use the application via the mentioned photos, videos, articles, and blogs. The mean of the data for this subscale is 2.51. Most respondents disagree on preferring to see the content of videos, pictures, blogs or emails. Following the participants' peak activity period is the next data set to be tallied. The participants agreed to use social media between 12 pm to 5 am and from 5 am to 12 am, as indicated by the mean computed for this component is 3.59, which is greater than (3), indicating that participants have a neutral response on being active at a particular time as mentioned above. The mean value of the next factor, which measures participants' interest in the service, product, and promotion, is 2.4483, greater than (2), resulting that participants disagree on being interested in the service, product, or promotion of any business (See Table 3).

The standard deviation, connected to the normal distribution, measures how far the responses deviate from the mean. A large standard deviation compared to the mean suggests that the mean does not adequately represent the data. (Collis & Hussey, 2014). As per the tabulated standard deviation beside the subscale time of activeness on the Internet, all the subscales range from .500 to .900, which is comparative good than the one subscale with higher STD, which has variation in answers from the participants. Worldwide, an alpha value that is greater than .60 is considered valuable. All the subscales are above or equal to .60, which is acceptable for data analysis.

4.1 Internet scrolling habit of the youth generation

The Internet has become an important part of the daily life of adolescents. Easy access to the Internet and its social appeal among adolescent males render them at an increased risk of internet habit and the associated adverse physical and psychosocial effects. There are four main themes from the experiences of adolescents with internet habit: reasons for internet habit, unmet social needs without the Internet, effects of internet habit, and self-control over internet usage (Rakhmawati et al., 2021).

What is the association between scrolling habit and social media marketing?

Recent years have witnessed a dramatic increase in Internet use across the world. The Internet has become an important part of the daily life of adolescents. Globally, Nepal

is also heading to use more Internet, approximately more than 37.5 %. Adolescents account for Nepal's internet users' highest proportion (Aryal, 2019). The results of block zero models has been presented (see)

Table 4. Summary table of block 1 models

Model	Chi-square	df	Sig.	Cox and Snell's R Square	Nagelkerke's R square	-2log-likelihood
Omnibus tests of model coefficients	5.468	8	.707	.035	.048	246.587
Hosmer and Lemeshow test	5.468	8	.707			

The findings show that analyzing the factors' influence on the model odd was feasible. Thus, according to the model developed (digital well-being and use of social media) for higher level students' internet scrolling habit on social media marketing experience, the student's own beliefs lead to application positively that participants are on their smartphone screen, demonstrating the value of an odds ratio was 1.157 greater than the students whose beliefs lead to the impact of internet scrolling through use of social media. (.655) (see Table 4). As Campman (2017) stated, Nagelkerke's R square adjusted Cox and Snell's R Square calculus to theoretically enable the value to reach one (1); therefore, Nagelkerke's R square is always greater than Cox and Snell's R Square. It is the reason for considering Nagelkerke's R square value in this research.

Table 5. Binary model to predict youth's internet scrolling addition to social media marketing (N = 200)

Independent variables	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95% C.I.for EXP(B)	
							Lower	Upper
Digital well-being	.146	.155	.892	1	.345	1.157	.855	1.567
Use of social media	-.423	.185	5.249	1	.022	.655	.456	.941
Constant	.744	.156	22.867	1	.000	2.105		

The result further indicates a significant association between internet scrolling habits and observing social media marketing, implying the negative association with using social media marketing ($p < 0.05$, $B = -.423$, odds= .655). The result highlighted that there was no association with digital well-being ($p > 0.05$) (See Table 5).

4.2 The use of social media during social media marketing

What is the association between the use of social media and social media marketing?

Social media is becoming more and more popular all over the world and in Nepal too. The need for social media marketing in Nepal is more significant than ever. Social media marketing in Nepal has multiplied over the past decade. It is about sharing information using the Internet through social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, YouTube, etc. Due to easily accessible smartphones, people, from children to the elderly, are connected to social networks. Social networks do not seem to stop until the world exists because it offers many advantages (Aryal, 2019; Warokka, 2020).

Table 6. Summary table of block 1 models

Model	Chi-square	df	Sig.	Cox and Snell's R Square	Nagelkerke's R square	-2log-likelihood
Omnibus tests of model coefficients	17.556	5	.004			
Hosmer and Lemeshow test	13.903	8	.084	.084	.117	236.115

The analysis presented in table 4 only focuses on the block 1 results. As represented in table 6, the Chi-square-tested significant values were lower than 0.05, indicating that the model with the independent variable was better than the model with no independent variable (Block 0). The second item to verify was the -2log-likelihood (overall model fit). It was helpful to compare different models and identify which model better explains the information. The comparison cannot be made since this study analysis a single model. Nagelkerke's R square value shows its effect size of .117 (see Table 6).

The result of the classification table shows that it is possible to observe that the model correctly classifies 70% of 200 cases. It is exciting compared to the rate of block 0 models, in which no variables are considered. This rate was 82% in block 0 shows that the validated variables positively impact the model since block 1 correctly classifies a higher percentage of 200 cases. Through the analysis, it was possible to verify that all variables were validated by Wald's test ($p < 0.05$) from the all-variable study. The results indicate that analyzing the variables' impact on the model odd was possible. Thus, according to the model generated (Social networking site, guidance of app,

Audience preference, time of activeness on the Internet and the exciting factor of social media) for higher level students' internet scrolling habit on social media marketing experience, the students own beliefs lead to influence on the guidance of application positively influence their engagement in internet scrolling, showing the value of an odds ratio was 1.547 greater than the students whose beliefs lead to the impact of the internet scrolling on social media factor (.007) (see Table 6)

The result further indicates that there was a significant association between internet scrolling habits and observing social media marketing, showing the negative association to social media marketing ($p < 0.05$, $B = -.345$, odds = .708) through being active on Internet (see Table 5). Similarly, there is a positive association between social media marketing and influence on chatting apps ($p < 0.05$, $B = .436$, odds = 1.547)

Table 7. Binary model to predict youth's internet scrolling addition to social media marketing (N = 200)

Independent variables	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95% C.I. for EXP(B)	
							Lower	Upper
Social networking site	-.290	.162	3.213	1	.073	.748	.545	1.027
Guidance of application	-.213	.161	1.754	1	.185	.808	.589	1.108
Audience preference	.021	.158	.018	1	.894	1.021	.750	1.391
Influence on chatting app	.436	.161	7.312	1	.007	1.547	1.128	2.123
Time activeness internet	-.345	.158	4.769	1	.029	.708	.520	.965
Constant	.771	.160	23.244	1	.000	2.162		

The result highlighted no association between social networking sites, application guidance, and audience preferences ($p > 0.05$). (See Table 6). Thus, the analysis presented focuses on block 1 results. As shown in table 5, the Chi-square-tested significant values were lower than 0.05, indicating that the model with independent variables was better than the model with no independent variable (Block 0). The second item to verify was the -2log- likelihood (overall model fit). It was helpful to compare different models and identify which model better explains the information. The comparison cannot be made since this study analysis a single model. Nagelkerke's R square value shows its effect size of .159 (see Table 7).

In the Homers and Lemeshow test, the significant value is higher than 0.05, indicating

that the model perfectly fits the data (see table 7). The result of the classification table shows that it is possible to observe that the model correctly classifies 69% of 200 cases. It is exciting when compared with the rate of the block 0 models, in which no variables are considered. This rate was 67% in block 0, which shows that the validated variables positively impact the model since block 1 correctly classifies a higher percentage of 200 cases. Through the analysis, it was possible to verify that all variables were validated by Wald's test ($p < 0.05$) from all analyzed variables.

Table 8. Summary table of block 1 models

Model	Chi-square	df	Sig.	Cox and Snell's R Square	Nagelkerke's R square	-2log-likelihood
Omnibus tests of model coefficients	24.252	7	.001	.114	.159	229.419
Hosmer and Lemeshow test	6.884	8	.549			

The results indicate that analyzing the variables' impact on the model odd was possible. Thus, according to the model generated (Screen timing, Use of social media, Social networking site, guidance of app, Audience preference, time of activeness on the Internet and the exciting factor of social media) for higher-level students, internet scrolling habit in social media marketing experience, the students own beliefs lead to influence on the guidance of application positively influence their engagement in internet scrolling, showing the value of an odds ratio was 1.567 greater than the students whose beliefs lead to the impact of the internet scrolling on use of social media and time activeness on Internet (.032 and .021 respectively)(see Table 8).

Table 9. Wholesome model to predict youth's internet scrolling addition to social media marketing (N = 200).

Independent variables	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95% C.I. for EXP(B)	
							Lower	Upper
Digital well-being	.191	.168	1.292	1	.256	1.210	.871	1.680
Use of social media	-.433	.202	4.577	1	.032	.648	.436	.964
Social networking site	-.288	.170	2.891	1	.089	.749	.537	1.045
Guidance on app	-.159	.167	.910	1	.340	.853	.615	1.183
Audience preference	.034	.163	.043	1	.836	1.034	.751	1.424
Influence on chat app	.449	.164	7.494	1	.006	1.567	1.136	2.161
Time activeness internet	-.375	.162	5.364	1	.021	.687	.501	.944
Constant	.816	.166	24.087	1	.000	2.261		

The result further indicates a significant association between internet scrolling habits and observing social media marketing, implying a negative association with social media marketing ($p < 0.05$, $B = -.433$, $odds = .648$). Similarly, the results show that there was a significant association between time activeness on the Internet and observing social media marketing, indicating a negative association with social media marketing ($p < 0.05$, $B = -.375$, $odds = .687$) (see Table 8). The result highlighted that there was no association between digital well-being, social networking sites, the guidance of applications and audience preferences ($p > 0.05$) (See Table 9).

The student's independent t-test results show that the mean score for boys ($n = 66$) on the first subscale audience preference on social media ($M = 2.578$, $SD = 0.598$) is statistically significantly different from that of girls ($n = 134$) for the same variable ($M = 2.378$, $SD = 0.723$), indicating that there was a difference in audience preference on social media content.

Table 10. Results of Chi-Square results

Table 8 Chi-Square Tests					
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	5.502 ^a	1	.019		
Continuity Correction	4.801	1	.028		
Likelihood Ratio	5.441	1	.020		
Fisher's Exact Test				.021	.015
N of Valid Cases	200				

The value of Pearson Chi-square is 5.502, and the significant associated value is .019 (which is less than .05). The alternative H_1 and H_2 are rejected as the Asymp Sig value is less than .05 in Table 10, which results indicate an association between scrolling habit and social media marketing and the use of social media and social media marketing.

5. DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

My discussion is based on the study's research questions entitled the association between the purpose of internet scrolling habit and social media marketing factors. Three questions have already been raised in this study. The independent variables

examine the relationship between online scrolling habit and social media marketing. This study aimed to learn more about the influence of internet scrolling habit on social media marketing among young people.

The survey variables were derived from the Principal Component Analysis (PCA). Later they were converted into subscales ranging from digital well-being to usage of social media, social networking sites, doom scrolling, communication and technology, apps guidance, audience preferences, influences on chat applications, social networking sites, the interesting factor of social media, personal influence on social media and internet time activeness.

The results indicate that the subscales' highest and lowest mean values were analyzed. The Alpha values of all the variables of subscales are above .60, signifying that the data collected was not a hunch, but accurate data was collected from the respondents. The significant value is compatible if the value is ($p < 0.05$). Similarly, the results show that social media use negatively impacts internet scrolling habit. But the influence of chatting apps has a positive impact on internet scrolling habit and social media marketing, and we can analyze that the variable time activeness has a negative impact on both the independent factor of internet scrolling habit and social media marketing. Furthermore, we can analyze from the data that there is no significant difference between the subscale audience preference as the significant value is higher than 0.05.

The results show a significant association between internet scrolling habits and observing social media marketing, implying a negative association with social media marketing ($p < 0.05$). Similarly, the results show a significant association between time activeness on the Internet and observing social media marketing, indicating a negative association with social media marketing ($p < 0.05$). But the result further highlighted that there was no association between digital well-being, social networking sites, the guidance of applications and audience preferences ($p > 0.05$).

Through the study, a t-test of various gender opinions on similar questions was also performed, and the results were nearly identical. Still, when it came to the preference of overlooking the content, there was a difference with a value of $p = 0.042$, which is statistically different.

Research question 1. *What is the association between scrolling habit and social media marketing?*

The results show a significant association between internet scrolling habits and observing social media marketing, implying a negative association with using social media marketing ($p < 0.05$). The result of this study is supported by the study of Koessmeier and Büttner (2021), who found an opposite association between internet scrolling habits and the attraction of social media marketing. They also found individual differences.

Research question 2. *What is the association between the use of social media and social media marketing?*

The result shows a significant association between social media use and marketing, implying a negative association. This study is supported by the study of Gomathi and Veeramani (2022), who found a positive association between the use of social media and social media marketing among the youth. Social media allows marketers to connect and engage potential customers where they are on LinkedIn, Twitter, YouTube, Facebook, Instagram, and even some of the younger platforms like TikTok. Marketers can engage their audience with a solid social media strategy and the ability to create engaging content.

Recommendation

- Future research could focus on using the mixed methods approach to understand the multiple reality of the impact of internet scrolling on social media marketing.
- Other bigger sample sizes could have been used instead of just 200, and the results and answers could have been more varied and accurate.
- Another element that could improve the future study's outcome is the presence of people of all ages.
- Further research could focus on collecting data from larger sample size and area.
- Further, future research could focus on the income constraint of the participants more than age in the buying perception that comes with online marketing.
- Future research could focus on the Geographical advancement of Nepal with online marketing.

Acknowledgement

I would also like to thank my mother, Mrs Gita Shrestha Piya, and my father, Mr Sushan Raj Piya, for financial support in all of my extracurricular activities and for leading me in the correct direction. Prof. Er. Hair Prasad Bhandari, my respected principal, for always supporting and helping me. Mr Prem Sharma (HoD, BBA) has always planned and incorporated me in every vocational and practical knowledge. I would also like to thank everyone who participated in my survey.

REFERENCES

- Alalwan, A. A., Rana, N. P., Dwivedi, Y. K., & Algharabat, R. (2017). Social Media in marketing: A Review and Analysis of the Existing Literature. *Telematics and Informatics*, 34(7), 1177–1190.
- Aryal, M. (2019, December 12). *Internet Habit In Young People Rise In Nepal*. *ICT Frame*. <https://ictframe.com/young-internet-addicts-on-the-rise-in-nepal/> Available at <https://doi.org>, accessed on 27th November 2022
- Azpeitia, J. (2021). *Janell Azpeitia Social Media Marketing and its Effects on TikTok Users International Business 2021*. Available at <https://www.theseus.fi> , and accessed on 24th November 2022
- Bunce, D. M., Flens, E. A., & Neiles, K. Y. (2010). *How Long Can Students Pay Attention in Class? A Study of Student Attention Decline Using Clickers*. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 87(12), 1438–1443.
- Chapman, C., & Muijs, D. (2013). *Collaborative School Turnaround: A Study of the Impact of School Federations on Student Outcomes*. *Leadership and Policy in Schools*, 12(3), 200–226.
- Chen, H. (2017). *College-Aged Young Consumers' Perceptions of Social Media Marketing: The Story of Instagram*. *Journal of Current Issues & Research in Advertising*, 39(1), 22–36. Available at <https://doi.org/10.1080/10641734.2017.1372321d>, and accessed on 24th November 2022
- Cheung, M. L., Pires, G., & Rosenberger, P. J. (2020). The Influence of Perceived social media Marketing Elements on Consumer–Brand Engagement and Brand Knowledge. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics*, 32(3), 695–720.

- Çizmeçi, E. (2017). *No Time for Reading, Addicted to Scrolling: The Relationship Between Smartphone Habit and Reading Attitudes of Turkish Youth*. *Intermedia International E-Journal*, 4(7), 290–302. Available at <https://doi.org>, and accessed on 24th November 2022
- Coker, K. K., Flight, R. L., Baima, D. M. (2017). *Skip It or View It: Coker, Flight and Baima 75 Marketing Management Journal*, Fall 2017. Available at <http://www.mmaglobal.org>, and accessed on 24th November 2022
- Collis, J., & Hussey, R. (2014). (PDF) *Business research: A practical guide for undergraduate*. (5th ed.). USA. Red Globe Press.
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches* (5th ed.). SAGE Publications.
- Digital Terai. (2020). *Social Media Marketing in Nepal | The Ultimate Guide*. Digital Terai. <https://digitalterai.com/social-media-marketing-nepal>
- Gaddefors, L., & Tollqvist, F. (2017). Available at <http://www.diva-portal.org>, and accessed on 24th November 2022
- Gomathi, A., & Veeramani, P. (2022). *The Study on Social Media Habit Among Adolescents*. ResearchGate; Available at <https://www.researchgate.net> and accessed on November 22, 2022.
- Jamil, K., Dunnan, L., Gul, R. F., Shehzad, M. U., Gillani, S. H. M., & Awan, F. H. (2022). Role of Social Media Marketing Activities in Influencing Customer Intentions: A Perspective of a New Emerging Era. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12. *Frontiersin*. Available at <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.808525>, and accessed on December 25 2022.
- Koessmeier, C., & Büttner, O. B. (2021). Why Are We Distracted by social media? Distraction Situations and Strategies, Reasons for Distraction, and Individual Differences. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.711416>, accessed on 25th December 2022.
- Kwak, Y., Kim, H., & Ahn, J.-W. (2022). Impact of Internet usage time on mental health in adolescents: Using the 14th Korea Youth Risk Behavior Web-Based Survey 2018. *PLOS ONE*, 17(3), e0264948. Available at <https://doi.org> Accessed on 27th November 2022

- Lab, C. (2018). *Types of Descriptive Statistics. Baseline Help Center. Available at <https://baselinesupport.campuslabs.com>* Accessed on 26th November 2022
- Lever, J., Krzywinski, M., & Altman, N. (2017). Points of Significance: Principal component analysis. *Nature Methods*, 14(7), 641–643.
- Lupinacci, L. (2020). "Absentmindedly scrolling through nothing": liveness and compulsory continuous connectedness in social media. *Media, Culture & Society*, 43(2), 35-45
- McDonald, J. (2018). *Social Media Marketing Workbook : how to use social media for business. Canada. Createspace Indep Pub.*
- Rakhmawati, W., Kosasih, C. E., Widiasih, R., Suryani, S., & Arifin, H. (2021). Internet Habit Among Male Adolescents in Indonesia: A Qualitative Study. *American Journal of Men's Health*, 15(3), 15-26
- Stanton, L. (2017). *Goldfish Memory Span: How Long Is It? (Hint: NOT 3 Seconds). Hepper0. Available at <https://www.hepper.com/>*, accessed on 27th November 2022
- Walden University. (2010, January 1). *7 Research Challenges (And how to overcome them) | Articles | Walden University. Available at www.waldenu.edu*. Accessed on 27th November 2022
- Warokka, A. (2020). Digital Marketing Support and Business Development Using Online Marketing Tools: An Experimental Analysis. *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 24(1), 1181–1188.
- Wiederhold, B. K. (2018). *Stop Scrolling, Start Living: The Growing Reality of Internet Habit Disorder. Cyberpsychology, Behavior, and Social Networking*, 21(5), 279–280.

A Review of Plastic Bricks as a Construction Material

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Received: November 20, 2022

Revised: December 21, 2022

Accepted: January 05, 2023

Published: January 29, 2023

How to cite this paper:

Shrestha, M.N., Kandel, J, KC, P, Bhatta, A, Paudyal, S, Poudel, A & Adhikari, B.P (2022). A Review of Plastic Bricks as a Construction Material

The OCEM Journal of Management, Technology & Social Sciences, 2(2), 103-114

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Oxford College of Engineering and Management

Originality: This paper is original and has not been published anywhere else

Paper type: Research paper
J.E.L. Classification: I (2), I (29)

Abstract

Plastic brick is the form of brick manufactured from the combination of non-recyclable waste plastic with other constituents (sand, aggregate, cement, water, stone dust, fly ash, etc.) This study aimed to examine the research findings on transforming waste plastic into bricks that might be used to replace traditional bricks. Different journal articles were reviewed entitled the transformation of waste plastic into bricks to replace traditional clay bricks. Different open-access journal articles were searched to fit the topic of this study. The results indicate that the concrete blocks made with plastic bottles have 57% higher compressive strength and which was cited seventy-nine times by the other researchers (n = 79) "Use of recycled plastic water bottles in concrete blocks". The results further show that the compressive strength and other properties can be increased significantly when plastic is used as a binder with sand. But when it is used as filler, it produces competitive strength as ordinary bricks and can be used without any restrictions or hesitation. The main reflection of this review is to conduct primary research on a large scale to find an innovative model to transform waste plastic into environmentally friendly bricks. The implication of this study would be beneficial to students, future researchers, the Engineering Department of Oxford College of Engineering and Management, Gaindakot 2 in Nawalparasi district and young academicians.

Keywords: *Plastic bricks, Construction materials, Conventional Bricks, filler, binder*

1. INTRODUCTION

Plastic bricks are the types of bricks that are manufactured using plastic waste. These bricks are not only cost-effective and eco-friendly but also have low water absorption value and high compressive strength and will not have problems like efflorescence in future. Plastic waste is increasing due to an increase in pollution, organization, and development. Since the rate of plastic production is projected to double the value every ten years, a more sustainable and safer way is needed to be taken (Prasanth, Gopalakrishnan, G Thanigainathan & Kathiravan, 2018, Kulkarni, Ravekar, Rama Rao, Waigokar & Hingankar, 2022). Plastic brick gives better temperature resistance than conventional brick even after 30 minutes of heating in the corners and the centre of the modal brick (Shrimali and Shikhar, 2017).

Bricks made by recycling soft plastic waste had high pressure withstand capacity and were very lightweight compared to conventional bricks. (Kognole, Shipkule and Survase, 2019) Plastic replaced the clay as a binder, which was much cheaper than ordinary brick, and water absorption capacity was zero percent when crushed waste (0.75 kg) and red soil (2 kg) were mixed. (Kumar, Biswas and Nath, 2020) Bricks made from plastic waste have minimal water absorption compared to conventional bricks (Prasanth, Gopalakrishnan, Thanigainathan, and Kathiravan, 2018). The water absorption capacity of fly ash bricks decreases from 12.714% to 1.8% when plastic waste significantly increases to the fly ash (Belay Wendimu, NeguseFurgasa, & Mohammed Hajji, 2021). The bricks made of plastic met the standard referred by the ASTM and Ethiopian, but it was not recommended on using in the places like kitchens, chimneys and walling purposes because of its low melting capacity. (Manas, 2022) reveals that water absorption and compression strength are more than ordinary bricks (Kadhone, Rajput, Deshmukh, Narkhede & Dhivare, 2022). Plastic bottles had beneficial use on optimization in energy by reducing the degradation of the environment with sustainable waste management. The primary objective of this study was to analyze an efficient way to effectively utilize waste plastic which is a more significant threat to the sustainment of ecological balance, give the knowledge of replacing the traditional construction brocks and compare the properties of the bricks with other construction material.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Table 1. Literature review of waste plastic transformation into bricks

Authors & Publication Years	Topics of the articles	Objective	Types of journals	Citations counts	Methods	Findings	Future Research
Chauhan, Kumar, Shankar Singh, Khan, Goyal, & Goyal (2019), UMundhe & Dhawale (2018).	1. Fabrication and Testing of Plastic Sand Bricks 2. Use of Waste Plastic as a Construction Material	To create masonry units to replace conventional bricks by recycling plastic.	<i>International Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences</i>	8	Experimental method	The compressive strength of brick is more than conventional clay brick.	Further research is required for the fire resistance of bricks and to improve the quality durability.
Al-Sinan & Bubshait (2022)	Utilization of Plastic waste for Making Bricks	To solve plastic waste by creating bricks made from plastic.	<i>International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology</i>	23	Experimental method.	Plastic sand bricks are useful for construction and reduce environmental pollution.	Future research could focus on the cost-effective model of transformation of waste plastic into bricks
Lamba, Kaur, Raj & Sorout (2021) Ogundairo-Olukann, Akinwunmi & Adegoke (2021)	1. Recycling/ reuse of plastic waste as construction material For sustainable development: a review 2. A review of plastic waste as a sustainable resource in civil engineering applications	To use plastic waste as a constituent of construction material To produce high-durability and quality bricks as well as to achieve optimum balance in all aspects, especially in terms of cost and functionality	1. <i>Environmental Science and Pollution Research</i> 2. <i>I.O.P. Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering</i>	17	Literature Review Method	Plastic waste may produce construction bricks, concrete blocks, road construction materials, and tiles.	Further research is required to determine the optimum proportion of plastic waste as a constituent of construction materials.
Al-Sinan & Bubshait (2022)	Using Plastic Sand as a Construction Material toward a Circular Economy: A Review	To look at the recent studies regarding the development of plastic sand bricks and the different percentages of plastic and sand used in the bricks.	Reviewed article	4	Literature review method	The compressive strength of the brick increased by increasing the ratio of plastic to sand.	Required further investigation on the types of plastic used and the flammability used in resistance to fire, also, their lack of standard code to the definite proportion of sand and plastic use in construction of the brick.
Kumar Biswas & Nath (2020)	A Study of Manufacturing Bricks Using Plastic Wastes Plastic in Bricks Application	To study the properties of the brick manufactured using plastic waste.	<i>International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development</i>	24	Experimental study	The bricks produced are lightweight, have a smooth surface and fine edges, do not have cracks, and have high crushing strength.	Future research has to focus on finding cost-effective methods to transform the waste plastic into bricks

Authors & Publication Years	Topics of the articles	Objective	Types of journals	Citations counts	Methods	Findings	Future Research
Yusof (2018)	Plastic in Brick Application	To outline the utilization of municipal plastic waste in construction industries	<i>Trends in Civil Engineering and its Architecture</i>	2	Literature review method	Plastic waste can be substituted either partially or completely in brick production.	Require further investigation on increasing the durability and quality of bricks
Al-Sinan and Bubshait, (2022)	Using Plastic Sand as a Construction Material toward a Circular Economy: A Review	To look at the recent studies regarding the development of plastic sand bricks and the different percentages of plastic and sand used in the bricks.	<i>Journal of substantiality and development</i>	4	Literature Review Method	Plastic brick can be used as an alternative to ordinary brick, which shows competitive results in terms of physical properties (e.g., compressive strength)	More research is required on the physical issue (fire resistance, commercial aspects of plastic brick)
Safinia & Alkalbani (2016)	Use of recycled plastic water bottles in concrete blocks	To research the use of plastic water bottles in concrete blocks.	<i>Procedia Engineering</i>	80	Experimental Method	The results show, Concrete blocks made with plastic bottles have 57% higher compressive strength.	Further research is required for concrete mix design and the feasibility of production in the industry to reduce cost.
Velmurugan (2019)	Rebuilding of Plastic Waste to Pavement Bricks	To recycle rich plastic for the concrete block.	<i>International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology</i>	6	Experimental Method	The result shows that the best ratio to construct the plastic brick is 30% plastic and 70% sand.	Future research could examine the cost-effective methods of transforming waste plastic into bricks
Sahani et al., (2022)	Mechanical Properties of Plastic Sand Brick Containing Plastic Waste	To utilize unused plastic to prepare plastic sand bricks.	<i>Advances in Civil Engineering</i>	35	Experimental Method	The results show that the best ratio to prepare plastic sand brick is 1:4, which has the maximum compressive strength and split tensile strength.	The future researcher may be interested in finding cost-effective methods of transforming waste plastic into bricks
User (2019)	Utilization of Waste Plastic in the Manufacturing of Paver Blocks	To the properties of plastic-made brick.	<i>International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology</i>	24	Experimental methods	Plastic sand bricks provide more advantages compared to continental brick in terms of cost efficiency, ultimately removing plastic waste.	On further research, the manufacturing cost could be reduced by replacing river sand with fly ash, quarry dust, or other waste products.

Our review study can create a platform for scholars who might be interested in plastic waste management. The review essay about bricks is significant since it can potentially increase readers' or students' understanding. It provides information on the various processes used in various countries to convert plastic waste into bricks. Among other things, it provides a concept for lowering or regulating the environmental pollution caused by plastics. The main thing that attracted us to this topic was the current context that the entire world is facing regarding plastic waste management. With a limited understanding of waste management, we realized that the waste plastic might be turned into many other construction materials without creating environmental deterioration.

Objective

- To analyze the highly cited articles on the related topics of bricks
- To find key models of the transformation of waste plastic into bricks.
- To analyze the review's main findings, which are based on the literature in Table one.
- To find the research gaps in the models used in converting the waste plastic into bricks
- To compare the properties of bricks with other construction materials.

Scope of the study

- To give new knowledge, replace the binding material of ordinary brick with plastic.
- To enhance the knowledge of how to minimize the cost of bricks compared to ordinary bricks.
- To find efficient ways of managing the non-degradable plastic waste
- To compare the properties of bricks with other construction materials.

Research questions

- What are the highly cited articles on the related topics of bricks?
- What are the key models of the transformation of waste plastic into bricks?
- What are the main findings of the review based on Table one?
- What research gaps exist in the models used to convert waste plastic into bricks?
- What are the different methods of comparing the properties of bricks with other construction materials?

3. METHODS AND MATERIALS

Different articles on converting waste plastic into bricks were studied by reviewing the abstracts of the papers. After that, a few paragraphs of each article give us a general introduction to their problem area. Then, we moved to the last paragraph before the heading "Method," which is usually the first major heading in the text of a research article (Galvan, 1987). This paragraph is a traditional way for researchers to state their specific hypotheses, research questions, or research purposes. Then, we scanned the rest of the article, highlighting all headings and subheadings by scanning the text in each subsection. Our purpose at this point was to get an overview.

It should be noted that by adhering to this rule, we pretreated, which is a method that is frequently suggested by reading specialists as the first step in reading a technical paper. Prereading provided an overview of a report's goal and contents, which helped us focus on the big picture as we worked through the specifics of a research report from start to finish. As recommended in the following guideline, the knowledge we gathered through prereading also assisted us in categorizing the articles (Galvan, 1987). We extract several journals from different sites of google. Our review is primarily based on published materials that examine recent or current literature that can cover a wide range of subjects at different levels of completeness and comprehensiveness of bricks. This literature has concluded research findings on transforming waste plastic into bricks. Our review has primarily focused on authors & publication years, the topic of the reviewed articles, objectives, citation counts, methods used in the articles, findings, and the future recommendation of research on this topic of this review.

4. RESULTS

After looking through numerous papers, articles, reviews and conference papers, we found that the plastic goods being discarded can be turned into different construction materials that can be utilized as binders and fillers for solid and interlocking bricks and tiles. The results highlighted that the compressive strength of brick is more than conventional clay bricks (Chauhan et al. (2019). The result of this study is supported by the study of Murthi et al. (2020), who found that the compressive strength of brick is more than conventional clay brick.

Research question 1. *What are the highly cited articles on the related topics of plastic bricks?*

The results indicate that the concrete blocks made with plastic bottles have 57% higher compressive strength, and it was cited 79 times. The results further highlighted that the best ratio to prepare plastic sand brick is 1:4, which has the maximum compressive strength and split tensile strength and was cited 35 times. Similarly, the review concludes that Plastic sand bricks provide more advantages than continental bricks in terms of cost efficiency, which also ultimately removes plastic waste and is cited 24 times. The results also highlight that crushed recycled plastic heated until hot melted and mixed with stone dust to mould brick and was cited 23 times (see Table 1).

Research question 2. *What are the key models of the transformation of waste plastic into bricks?*

The results highlight that the key models of transforming waste plastic into bricks use plastic as a partial filler or a binder material. In a plastic filler process, a small percentage by weight of the plastic was mixed with sand or aggregate with cement, and when plastic was used as a binder, a maximum proportion of sand could be used with sand in brick production (see Table 1).

Research question 3. *What are the main findings of the review based on Table one?*

The review of different journals finds that the compressive strength and other properties can be increased significantly when plastic is used as a binder with sand. But when it is used as a filler, it produces competitive strength as ordinary bricks and can be used without any restrictions or hesitation. The results highlighted that the compressive strength of brick is more than conventional clay brick, and plastic sand bricks are useful for construction and reduce environmental pollution. Additionally, the results show that plastic waste may produce construction bricks, concrete blocks, road construction materials, and tiles, and further reveal that the compressive strength of the brick increased by increasing the ratio of plastic to sand.

It was found that the bricks produced are lightweight, have a smooth surface and fine edges do not have cracks, and have high crushing strength. Plastic waste can be substituted either partially or completely in brick production. It was found that plastic

brick can be used as an alternative to ordinary brick, which shows competitive results in terms of physical properties (e.g., compressive strength). The results indicate that the concrete blocks made with plastic bottles have 57% higher compressive strength. Finally, the result shows that the best ratio to construct the plastic brick is 30% plastic and 70% sand, and also shows that the best ratio to prepare plastic sand brick is 1:4, which has the maximum compressive strength and split tensile strength (see Table 1).

Research question 4. *What research gaps exist in the models used to convert waste plastic into bricks?*

The results highlight a research gap in examining the fire resistance of bricks to improve the quality durability and could focus on the cost-effective model of transforming waste plastic into bricks. There is also a research gap in determining the optimum proportion of plastic waste as a constituent of construction materials. There is also a research gap on what types of plastic could be used and the flammability used in resistance to fire, also, their ick of standard code ta o the definite proportion of sand and plastic use in construct use of the rick. There is a research gap in finding cost-effective methods to transform waste plastic into bricks, and increasing the durability and quality of bricks has to be conducted. The results indicate that a research gap was to conduct more research on the physical issue (fire resistance, commercial aspects of plastic brick). It is also expected to do further research on concrete mix design and the feasibility of production in the industry to reduce costs. There is a research gap in examining how the manufacturing cost could be reduced by replacing river sand with fly ash, quarry dust, or other waste products (see Table 1).

Research question 5. *What are the different methods of comparing the properties of bricks with other construction materials?*

The results highlighted that plastic usage in our daily life had increased significantly due to urbanization as it is an advantageous and popular material. The only disadvantage is non-biodegradability. This study summarizes the work done by authors to use plastic as construction material in bricks. The recyclable properties of plastic waste can be utilized to recycle this waste and produce a new product having a lesser negative impact on the environment. One of the options to recycle plastic waste is to form bricks of plastic by mixing plastics with sand which can be used to replace traditional bricks.

The results indicate that various authors performed a comparative study with brick made up of other materials by using various testing methods. For example, scratch test, compressive test, apparent porosity, water absorption, apparent porosity test, soundness test, and efflorescence test and analyzed that further research in this field can enrich the strength, quality and durability of these masonry bricks. These bricks absorb less water compared to conventional bricks, which is also incredibly significant in the view of environmental sustainability. The results highlighted that using waste materials in construction materials had shown enormous potential. Although some properties may decrease when the waste fibres are added, the slightly lower properties compared to the cost and energy saved could be a sustainable and environmentally beneficial trade-off. In some cases, the processing cost for recycling and utilizing the waste materials may be higher than the typical cost of virgin materials, which limits their appeal for usage (see Table 1).

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

When crushed waste plastic (0.750 kg) was melted and mixed with river sand (2kg), a brick's compressive strength and water absorption capacity were 97.5k N/m² and 3%, respectively. But on mixing the red soil (2 kg) with crushed and melted waste plastic (0.750 kg), the compressive strength and water absorption capacity of a brick obtained were 26 kN/m² and 0%, respectively (Kognole, Shipkule & Survase, 2019). The average compressive strength and split tensile strength of a plastic sand brick of ratio 1:3, 1:4, and 1:5 are 9.72 N/mm² and 737.486 MPa, 12.28 N/mm² and 804.53 MPa, 3.39 N/mm² and 654.25 MPa respectively. The compressive and split tensile strength increases with a reduction in the percentage of plastic from 25% to 20%. Sahani et al., (2022)

Our review found that the transformation of waste plastic into bricks primarily focused on environmentally friendly solutions, which eventually reduce the cost of production and manage our community's waste plastic. Future research is expected to examine the topic of this study to foreground the understanding of the different models of transforming conventional brick into plastic brick. We are reflected for the future primary study based on the cost-effective experimental model to convert waste plastic into bricks.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We want to recognize our family members' love and affection in the article's writing. Our seniors kept telling us; we are a writer." It was very inspiring for our writing. Our teachers and department always inspire us to go ahead. We express our sincere thanks to the Department of Civil Engineering. We would also like to acknowledge the help of the RMC of OCEM for the continuous support of our paper.

REFERENCE

- Al-Sinan, M. A., & Bubshait, A. A. (2022). Using Plastic Sand as a Construction Material toward circular Economy: A Review. *Sustainability*, 14(11), 6446. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14116446> Accessed on 19th December 2022.
- Belay Wendimu, T., NeguseFurgasa, B., & Mohammed Hajji, B. (2021). Suitability and Utilization Study on Waste Plastic Brick as Alternative Construction Material. *Journal of Civil, Construction and Environmental Engineering*, 6(1), 9.
- Chauhan, S. S., Kumar, B., Shankar Singh, P., Khan, A., Goyal, H., & Goyal, S. (2019). Fabrication and Testing of Plastic Sand Bricks. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, 69(1). Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899x/691/1/012083>. Accessed on 19th December 2022.
- Galvan, J. L. (1987). Literature review issue. *Deep Sea Research Part B. Oceanographic Literature Review*, 34(12), 1082.
- Kadhane, Y., Rajput, S., Deshmukh, Narkhede, A., & Dhivare, Prof. J. A. (2022). Utilization of Waste Plastic in Manufacturing of Bricks. *International Journal for Research in Applied Science and Engineering Technology*, 10(5), 801–804.
- Kognole, R.S., Shipkule, K. and Survase, K.S. | M.P. | L.P. | U. (2019). Utilization of Plastic waste for Making Bricks. *International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development*, 3(4), 878–880.
- Kulkarni, P., Ravekar, V., Rama Rao, P., Waigokar, S., & Hingankar, S. (2022). Recycling of waste HDPE and P.P. plastic in preparation of plastic brick and its mechanical properties. *Cleaner Materials*, 5, Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clema.2022.100113> and accessed on 19th December 2022.

- Kumar, A., Biswas, M., & Nath, D. (2020). Issue 8 www.jetir.org (ISSN-2349-5162). *JETIR2008243 Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, 7. Retrieved from <https://www.jetir.org/papers/JETIR2008243.pdf> and accessed on 19th December 2022.
- Kumar, R., Kumar, M., Kumar, I. and Srivastava, D. (2021). A review on the utilization of plastic waste materials in the brick manufacturing process. *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 46 (6), 6775–6780.
- Lamba, P., Kaur, D. P., Raj, S., & Sorout, J. (2021). Recycling/reuse of plastic waste as construction material for sustainable development: a review. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-021-16980-y> and accessed on 19th December 2022.
- Manas, D. (2022). Recycle Plastic Waste Brick. *International Journal for Research in Applied Science and Engineering Technology*, 10(1), 1271–1274.
- Murthi, P., Bhavani, M., Mushtaq, Md. Saqlain., Jauhar, Md. Osman., & Rama Devi, V. (2020). Development of relationship between compressive strength of brick masonry and brick strength. *Materials Today: Proceedings*. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2020.07.040>. Accessed on 19th December 2022.
- Prasanth, R. L., Gopalakrishnan, S., G Thanigainathan, & Kathiravan, A. (2018). Utilization of waste plastics in fly ash bricks. *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics*. 119(15):1417-1424
- Safinia, S., & Alkalbani, A. (2016). Use of Recycled Plastic Water Bottles in Concrete Blocks. *Procedia Engineering*, 164 (7), 214–221.
- Sahani, K., Joshi, B. R., Khatri, K., Magar, A. T., Chapagain, S., & Karmacharya, N. (2022). Mechanical Properties of Plastic Sand Brick Containing Plastic Waste. *Advances in Civil Engineering*, 1(1), 1–10.
- Sahu, M.K. (2017). Critical Review on Fly Ash Bricks. *International Journal of Advance Engineering and Research Development*, 4(03). 16-22.
- Shrimali., Shikhar. (2017). Bricks From Waste Plastic. *International Journal of Advanced Research*, 5(1), 2839–2845.
- Soni, A., Rajput, T. S., Sahu, K., & Rajak, S. (2022). Utilization of Waste Plastic in

Manufacturing of Paver Blocks. *International Journal for Research in Applied Science and Engineering Technology*, 10(2), 939–942.

Subathra, P., Varghese, B., Jamsheed K. P, M., & T. H, M. (2022). Experimental Investigation on Making of Plastic Brick. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Science, Communication and Technology*, 1–7. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.48175/ijarsct-2225>. Accessed on 19th December 2022.

UMundhe, Ms. A., & Dhawale, A. W. (2018). An Overview of Use of Waste Plastic In Road Construction. *Journal of Advances and Scholarly Research in Allied Education*, 15(2),446–448.

User, S. (2019). *Utilization of Waste Plastic in Manufacturing of Paver Blocks*. *IRJET-International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 6(4), 1967-1970

Velmurugan, V. (2019). Rebuilding of Plastic Waste to Pavement Bricks. *International Journal for Research in Applied Science and Engineering Technology*, 7(4), 927–931.

Impact of Shear Wall Location on the Response of RC Framed Building

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Received: November 21, 2022

Revised: December 23, 2022

Accepted: January 06, 2023

Published: January 29, 2023

How to cite this paper:

Shrestha, A, Kandel, B, Shrestha, M & Poudel, A (2022). Impact of Shear Wall Location on the Response of RC Framed Building

The OCEM Journal of Management, Technology & Social Sciences, 2(2), 115-125

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Oxford College of Engineering and Management

Originality: This paper is original and has not been published anywhere else

Paper type: Research paper

J.E.L. Classification: I (2), I (29)

Abstract

The objective of this study was to understand the impact of storey walls on the Response of RC Framed Building. The shear wall provides huge stiffness against lateral load, making the structure less vulnerable during the Earthquake. The location of the shear wall plays a vital load defending seismic force on the building. The research method was experimental research. In this paper, the most favorable position of the shear wall was determined by creating different alternates ALT-1, ALT-2, ALT-3 and ALT-4. The results of storey drift, lateral sway and base share were computed with the base model. Finite element software ETABS was used for the linear dynamic analysis and design of 11 storey building. The results show that Lateral sway and storey drift declined with the introduction of a shear wall with a central location exhibiting the most desirable result. The implication of this study would be beneficial to the Engineering Department of OCEM, students, researchers, and scholars to know the impact of Shear Wall Location on the Response of RC Framed Buildings.

Keywords: *Base shear, Framed Building, Lateral sway, Shear Wall Location, Storey drift*

1. INTRODUCTION

The basic aim of the seismic analysis was to identify the safe structure of wall and fulfill its intended purpose. Shear wall is the best structural element for high-rise buildings to lessen the effect of earthquakes as it contributes huge lateral stiffness making the structure safe. Shear walls in buildings have to be situated in plan symmetrically to decrease the adverse impacts of twists in buildings.

Shear walls are normally constructed from materials like concrete and masonry. When the shear wall is not announced in such a building, beams and columns are larger. The objective of this study was to identify the impact of Shear Wall Location on the Response of RC Framed Buildings.

Mishra et al. (2018), the storey displacement is the least when shear walls are placed in the periphery of the building. The existence of the shear wall in the bare frame alignment and the filled frame structure revises the lateral force behavior of the RC framed building to a large extent. Vidyashree et al. (2017), storey displacement is maximum at the top storey, and storey drift value increases until the maximum value and starts to decrease with the increase of height of the storey in the model. Without shear walls building has more dislocation, story drift and reduced stiffness compared to the five models with the shear wall.

Anshuman et al.(2011), the top deflection was reduced and reached within the permissible deflection after providing the shear wall in any of the 6th & 7th frames, and applies in the 1st and 12th frames in the shorter track. They further highlighted that both turning moment and shear force in the 1st and 12th frames were reduced after providing the shear wall in any of the 6th & 7th frames.

It was also the same in the 1st and 12th frames in the shorter direction. Kumar et al. (2014) highlighted that shear walls could be used as lateral load-resisting systems and retrofitting structures. The internal shear walls are more cost-effective than external shear walls compared to cyclic load tests. Gandhi (2015), the percent of the opening increases deflection up to 40% in proportion, but deflection increases more rapidly as opening increases. The 20% eccentric zigzag opening has reduced deflection, and the eccentric straight has highest deflection and concentric loading

Chandiwala (2012), the Shear wall directly obstructs end oscillation, hence decreasing the overall turning moment of the building. Venkatesh and Bai (2011), the thickness of shear forces does not impact decreasing shear stresses, and interior shear walls' performance is reasonable associated to exterior shear walls. In retrofitting methods, external shear walls are considered as an alternative to internal shear walls.

2. BUILDING CONFIGURATION

An 11-storey building is considered with a square plan dimension so that result analysis would be easier. Alternate models are created with different locations of the shared wall; the plan for all the alternatives is shown in Figure 1. The width and thickness of the shear wall are kept constant in all models.

Plan of Base Model

Alt -1

Alt -3

Alt -2

Alt -4

Figure 1. Plan of all the models

Table 1. Example of building configuration

Building System	RCC Framed Structure
Building Type	Multi-Storey Commercial complex building
Number of Storey	11 Storey
Floor Height	3.5m
Column Size	550mm X 550mm
Beam Size	450mm X 300mm
Slab Thickness	165mm
Shear Wall Thickness	150mm
Outer Wall Thickness	230mm
Partition Wall Thickness	115mm
Concrete Grade	M30
Steel Grade	Fe500
Importance factor	1.5
Seismic Zone	V

3. METHODS OF ANALYSIS

The equivalent static analysis is a simplified technique that substitutes the dynamic loading effect of an anticipated earthquake by a constant force spread horizontally on the building formation. In this technique, it is considered that the building responds in its own fundamental mode when the vibrations due to earthquakes are generated. For this to be valid, the building must be low-rise and symmetrical to prevent underground torsional motion. This technique of analysis can use to buildings whose seismic reaction

in each route is not considerably affected by contributions from modes higher than the basic mode

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Five models with the same plan dimension and size of structural elements with alternate positions of share wall are analyzed. Results are extracted and compared to base shear, storey drift and lateral sway.

4.1 Base shear

The base shear in all the models achieved from linear dynamic assessment as per IS code 1893 (part 1): 2016 are presented in Figure 2. Base shear increases as the share wall location move inward, with the highest value in alternate 4 with the core share wall. The base model receives nearly half the share quantity than the last alternate. A larger base shear value is obtained as seismic weight and horizontal seismic coefficient increase in shear wall models (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Base shear in all alternate models

4.2 Storey Drift

Storey drift, also referred to as inter-storey drift, is the displacement of a storey concerning the adjacent storey when the lateral loads act upon it. The storey drift of any storey in a building should not outstrip 0.004 times the storey height.

The pattern of storey drift is similar in all models, as seen in Figure 3, where the base model has the uppermost value, which decreases by 45% in Alternate 1. Shear wall models have identical behaviour attaining maximum drift at the 6th storey. 13% less than the preceding model in Alt 2 and 3 exhibits a similar drift amount. It is 10% greater than succeeding Alternate 4. The building with a central core shear wall has the least storey drift making it the most desirable position (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Storey Drift in all Alternate Models

4.3 Lateral Sway

Lateral sway also referred to as storey displacement, is the displacement of a top storey concerning the bottom of the structure. Cl. 20.5 of IS 456: 2000 restricts the lateral

sway at the top equal to, where the total height of the building is H . It is witnessed from figure 4 that the lateral sway is maximum in the base model with no shear wall, which drastically decreases in succeeding models comprising a shear wall and least in Alternate 4. Sway drops by around 20% in the first alternate than the base model; afterwards 12% fall is evident in Alternate 2 and Alternate 3 with almost equal sway. Finally, the least of all 37mm displacement is seen in the last alternate with the core shear wall. It is a decline of 10% from the prior model and around 40% less than the base model (see Figure 4).

Figure 4. Lateral sway in all alternates

5. CONCLUSION

Shear walls are vertical elements of the horizontal force-resisting system, which are constructed to counter the effects of lateral load acting on a structure. In residential construction, Shear walls are straight external walls that typically form a box which provides all of the lateral support for the building. When shear walls are designed and constructed correctly, they will have the strength and stiffness to resist horizontal forces. The study compares parameters, for example, storey drift, storey shear, and displacement of a building under lateral loads based on the strategic positioning of

shear walls. The effect of shear wall location on various parameters is to be compared. The static and response spectrum method is used to obtain the overall performance level of a structure

The results show that buildings with shear walls perform better in earthquakes as they exhibit lesser lateral sway and inter-storey drift; however, has greater base shear. Similarly, alternates 2 and 3 have no significant difference in their seismic behavior, and alternate 4 with the central core shear wall is the best alternative for the position of the shear wall. The results further indicate that shear walls in outer grids are seen as less effective than in inner grids.

The study by Singh, Victor, and Jain (2019) found that Shear walls are upright elements of the flat energy resisting system, which are built to deal with the consequences of lateral load working on a structure. In domestic construction, Shear walls are straight exterior walls that normally form a box which delivers all of the lateral assistance for the building.

When shear walls are constructed and composed appropriately, they will have the power and strength to avoid horizontal forces. In building building, a rigid vertical diaphragm can transmit lateral forces from exterior walls.

The floors, and roofs to the ground foundation in a direction parallel to their planes in building. Their study compares parameters, for example, storey drift, storey shear, and displacement of a building under lateral loads based on the strategic positioning of shear walls. The impact of shear wall setting on various parameters is to be evaluated. The constant and response spectrum technique is utilized to achieve the overall performance level of a structure.

Similarly, Acharya and Shrestha (2019) found that Shear walls perform a important role in increasing the seismic performance of the building. It is vital to establish the most effective position of shear walls. Shear wall composition must be correct because if not, it will affect an harmful effect instead. This paper aims to predict the impact of placing RC shear walls of several shapes on the structural reply of RC buildings resting on sloping ground.

Recommendations

This study shows that shear walls work better when placed in both directions than in cases where shear walls are placed in only one direction. Again, among all the cases, shear walls provide maximum resistance to lateral forces when placed along the periphery. So, for a symmetrical or nearly symmetrical high-rise building, it would be very effective to provide shear walls along the periphery in both directions.

- This study was performed for a 6-storey building in seismic zone II of OCEM. Future studies can be carried out for higher-storey buildings in other seismic zones of OCEM.
- This study considers all the important issues like storey shear, storey drift and movement, stiffness, and torsional irregularity. However, other parameters, for example, the soft storey effect, can be introduced for further analysis.
- This whole study is performed for a symmetrical structure. If the structure is unsymmetrical, the optimum location and orientation of the shear walls may vary.
- There are very few works entitled unsymmetrical structures. Therefore, there is a huge scope for further study-analysis of the optimum location of shear walls in unsymmetrical structures.
- This study was performed for a 6-storey building in seismic Zone V. Future studies can be carried out for higher-storey buildings in other seismic Zones.
- This study considers all the important parameters like storey shear, storey drift and displacement. However, other parameters, for example, Impact of the stiffness, and torsion can be introduced for further analysis.
- This whole study is performed for a symmetrical structure. If the structure is unsymmetrical, the optimum location and orientation of the shear walls may vary.
- There are very few works entitled unsymmetrical structures. Therefore, there is a huge scope for further study-analysis of the optimum location of shear walls in unsymmetrical structures.

REFERENCES

- Anshuman S., D. B. (2011). Solution of Shear Wall Location in Multi-Storey Building. *International Journal of Civil & Structural Engineering*, 2(2), 493-506
- Fahim, M., Ashikur, S., Simon, R., Kabir, F., Sanjid, H., & Safat, A. (2021). *Orientation and Location of Shear Walls in RC Buildings to Control Deflection and Drifts*. Retrieved from <http://103.82.172.44:8080/xmlui/bitstream/handle/123456789/1358/Thesis2020>, and accessed on 3rd of January, 2023.
- Singh, R., Victor, O., & Jain, S. I. (2019). Seismic analysis of buildings on different types of soil with and without shear wall: A review. *Proceedings of the International Conference on Sustainable Materials And Structures for Civil Infrastructures (Smsci2019)*. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5127131>, and accessed on 3rd of January, 2023.
- Suarjana, M., & Wibowo, A. (2010). Coupling of Finite Element and Boundary Element Methods for Structural Analysis of Shear Wall - Frame Building. *Jurnal Teknik Sipil*, 17(1), 15.
- Code of practice for design loads (other than Earthquake) for Buildings and Structures – Dead Loads _ Unit weight of building materials and stored materials*. (IS 875(Part I):1987). New Delhi: Bureau of Indian Standards.
- Code of practice for design loads (other than Earthquake) for Buildings and Structures – Imposed Loads*. (IS 875(Part II):1987). New Delhi: Bureau of Indian Standards.
- Code of practice for earthquake design and construction of buildings*. (IS 4326:2013). New Delhi: Bureau of Indian Standards.
- Criteria for Earthquake resistant design of structures*. (IS 1893(Part-I):2016). New Delhi: Bureau of Indian Standards.
- Ductile design and detailing of reinforced concrete*. (IS 13920:2016). New Delhi: Bureau of Indian Standards.
- Plain and Reinforced Concrete-Code of Practice*. (IS 456:2000). New Delhi: Bureau of Indian Standards.
- Plain and Reinforced Concrete-Code of Practice*. (IS 456:2000). New Delhi: Bureau of Indian Standards.

- Chandiwala, A. (2012, December). Earthquake Analysis of Building Configuration with Different Positions of Shear Wall. *International Journal of Emerging Technology and Advanced Engineering*, 2(12), 347-353
- Venkata Sairam Kumar. N, S. B. (2014, February). Shear walls – A review. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology (IJIRSET)*, 3(2), 9691-9694
- Venkata Sairam Kumar.N, S. B. (2014, February). Shear walls – A review. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology (IJIRSET)*, 3(2), 9691-9694
- Gandhi, B. H. (2015, December). Effect of Opening on Behaviour of Shear Wall. *International Journal For Technological Research In Engineering*, 3(4), 875-878
- Vidyashree, D. V. (2017, August). Analysis of RCC Multistoried Building with and without shear wall and optimum location of shear wall. *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET)*, 4(8), 302-307
- Smriti Mishra, R. R. (2018, March). Effective location of the shear wall, its significance and displacement analysis. *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET)*, 5(3), 827-828
- Suarjana, M., & Wibowo, A. (2010). Coupling of Finite Element and Boundary Element Methods for Structural Analysis of Shear Wall - Frame Building. *Jurnal Teknik Sipil*, 17(1), 15.

Effect of Management Information System (MIS) on Decision-Making in the Academic Sector

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Received: November 22, 2022

Revised: December 24, 2022

Accepted: January 07, 2023

Published: January 29, 2023

How to cite this paper:

Bhandari, H.P (2022). Effect of Management Information System (MIS) on Decision-Making in the Academic Sector.

The OCEM Journal of Management, Technology & Social Sciences, 2(2), 126-146

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Originality: This paper is original and has not been published anywhere else

Paper type: Research paper

J.E.L. Classification: I (2), I (29)

Abstract

The current era is the information era; people are running on society 5.0, where machines are integrated with humans for a healthy, comfortable, easy, and long life. In general, information is blood, and MIS is body; blood flows for life which can be compared with the flow of information on the organization as per the requirement for decision-making to grow the organization to meet its desired outcome. The overall objective of this research is to assess the effect of MIS on decision-making among academic institutions. This machine can function effectively and efficiently only with the help of data and information for humanitarian assistance for various purposes. Nowadays, every organization cannot run smoothly without the use of MIS. It signifies the dependability of decision-making on MIS. This research has attempted to identify necessary variables. They are used to evaluate the influence of management information systems on decision-support capabilities in the organization.

This study also discusses the concept, attributes, characteristics, types of MIS, and the MIS model, and finally, highlights the effect of MIS in decision-making in academic institutions. At the same time, different models and figures are presented to enrich the discussion and to highlight the status of each MIS and DSS information system in an organization's decision-making process. Here fifteen related articles are incorporated to review the title to ensure the research gap and where conceptual review approach based on descriptive content analysis using long-term classroom discussion. This research will create an awareness to develop an integrated MIS among academic institutions to ensure success through rational scientific decision-making.

Keywords: *MIS, decision making machine, society 5.0, academic institution*

1. INTRODUCTION

Data, information, knowledge and result are interrelated terms to perform the specific decision-making process. The information management system is an integrated set of parts of gathering, organizing, extracting, storing, processing and disseminating information for decision-making. Some information systems have been developed for various purposes, especially in business sectors such as TPS, DAS, KWS, MIS, DSS, E.S., CSCWS, GDSS and ESS. Each plays multiple roles in the organizational hierarchy for activities and decision-making. Management Information Systems (MIS) is a newly evolved business and organization management concept. It is an integrated system of man, machine, programs and procedures for providing the information to support the organization's transaction, operations and decision-making function for effective and efficient management. Shortly, it is a computer-based information system (Ali, 1019).

The Management Information System is an effective tool for managing complex, huge, unmanaged data in a simplified manner to perform business activities at the various levels of the organization (Tripathi, 2010). Information systems and decision-making activities are interrelated where information system is a system used to collect the right information and the right time with high reliability for the right decision-making of the organization. Nowadays, a successful organization is the symbol of the proper implication of an MIS system in an organization that helps solve both structured and unstructured problems (Alkhaffaf, 2012).

No doubt, the primary resource of the organization's success is accurate, reliable, and timely information. Effective and efficient information and decision-making activities are the main success factors of various administrative activities. There are five attributes of the information to be remarkable to the organization: appropriateness, accuracy, quantity, timeliness, and accessibility of data used in the organization—the more reliable and timelier the information, the more correct and beneficial the decision. Consequently, an integrated information system should provide the organization with current and future data to help in accurate managerial decision-making (Yassine, 2017).

Many authors discuss information, management information system and decision-making; the relationship among information, information system, system analysis

and decision-making which was established in 1966 by Oleh Kostetsky. Management information system generates knowledge about an organization's relative position and fundamental workable force. Srinivas Nowduri said that there is a good relationship between MIS and decision-making. The decision-making process and its effect on middle-level and top-level management in a business organization have a significant role in automated decision-making (Ghaffarzadeh, 2015).

2. OBJECTIVES AND RESEARCH QUESTION

The main objective of the research article is to review the effect of Management Information Systems (MIS) on decision-making in the academic sector. Besides, it has some minor objectives highlighting the findings or outcomes during the research.

- To identify highly cited journals on the impact of MIS in the decision-making process.
- To identify the research method applied in the review articles.
- To identify the impact of MIS on the decision-making process
- To determine the relationship between management information systems and the managerial decision-making process.

Research Question

Which is the highest cited journal article in this review research and its main results?

What methods were used in the reviewed articles of this study?

What is the impact of MIS on the decision-making process?

What is the relationship between management information systems and managerial decision-making processes?

3. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The author has collected 23 articles on management information system and decision-making for the literature review, including related books and other online resources. Out of them, important 15 articles are incorporated to review the literature. The most related fifteen articles are reviewed (see Table 1).

Table 1. Summary of the previous studies on the roles of MIS in the decision-making process in organization

Name of the Article	Name of the Journal	Article Publisher	Author and Publication Year	Citation Score	Method Used	Key Words	Results
Comparison of Management Information System and Decision Support System and Its Role in the Decision-making Process of Managers of Economic Affairs and Finance of Zahedan	International Review of Management and Marketing	Econjournals	Keshtegar and Vakili, (2018)	1	Quantitative analysis Method	Management Information System, Decision Support System, Managers, Decision-making Process	The result indicated that MIS and DSS have a significant relationship with managers' decision-making process and that rational decision-making process as the intermediary variable inferred and explained this effect.
Decision Making Based on Management Information System and Decision Support System	International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management	European Researchers	Ada & Ghaffarza-deh, (2015)	194	Literature Review Method	Management Information Systems, Decision Support Systems, Decision-making	The results highlighted that the management information system works online mode. But the decision support system works in real-time mode. The management support system supports a medium level of data, but the decision support system supports huge volumes of data. The management support system uses low graphics support, but the decision support system uses large graphics support. The management information system focuses only on fully structured tasks or routines for decisions, but the decision support system focuses on the structure and semi-structured data.
The Role of Management Information System (MIS) and Decision Support System (DSS) for Managers' Decision Making	International Journal of Business and Management	Canadian Center of Science and Education	Trivedi, (2011)	194	Literature review Method	Management information system, Decision support system, Managers, Decision-making process	The results indicated that the decision-making process, especially with an emphasis on MIS and DSS, provides information services for middle and higher-level managers.
Decision support system and knowledge-based strategic management	International Conference on Communication, Management, and Information Technology (ICCMIT 2015) Decision support system and knowledgebase	Elsevier B.V.	Alyou-bi(2015)	88	Literature review Method	Decision-making, Decision Support Systems (DSS), Knowledge Management (K.M.), Group Support System (GSS), Strategic management, Strategy	The results conclude that the concept of K.M. is as crucial to strategic management as any other activity. Through its enhancement of K.M., DSS has also found use towards enabling decision-makers to make more informed strategic decisions.

Name of the Article	Name of the Journal	Article Publisher	Author and Publication Year	Citation Score	Method Used	Key Words	Results
DECISION SUPPORT SYSTEM (DSS)	Singaporean Journal of Business Economics and Management Studies	National Library Singapore, 2013	Khodashahri & Arabi, (2018)	6	Literature Review Method	Organizations, decision support systems, managers, semi-structured problems	The results concluded that the decision support system is a counsellor beside a decision maker and allows it to run with huge information mass and use them arbitrarily and in a suitable model frame to improve decision making.
Decision Support Systems (DSS) in Higher Education Systems	International Journal of Applied Information Systems (IJ AIS)	Foundation of Computer Science FCS, New York, USA	Fakeeh (2015)	36	Literature Review Method	Decision Support System (DSS), Higher Education, and Information Systems.	The results concluded that the headway and integration of a DSS with the higher education institute information and communication technology structures might settle on a compact outlay and anticipated time. It would focus on critical drafting issues and grasping the most appropriate decisions for the higher educational systems' delegate involvement.
Impact of Management Information Systems (MIS) on Decision Making	Global Disclosure of Economics and Business, Volume 8, No 2/2019	ISSN 2305-9168 (print); 2307-9592 (online)	Ali (2019)	1	Literature Review Method	MIS, Database, Information access, Decision support system, Decision quality, Decision-making process, organization	This research article concluded that using information systems, i.e. MIS, can influence the decision-making process through the various attributes of information like accuracy, timeliness, relevance, completeness, economic information etc. The success of information systems will enhance the performance of enterprises
Management Information System and Decision-Making	Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies	MCSER (Mediterranean Center of Social and Educational Research), Rome-Italy	Berisha - Shaqiri (2014)	60	Literature Review Method	Management Information Systems, decision-making, organization, database	The main results indicate that the number of contemporary business data and information exponentially grows, and efficient business decision-making is possible only if the necessary information is fast and accurate. It can be managed by adequate staff; in most cases, poor efficiency results from a lack of sound management information systems.
MIS is an Effective Tool for Decision Making	International Journal of Computer Applications (0975 – 8887)	International Journal of Computer Applications support centre	Tripathi, (2010)	7	Literature Review Method	Management Information System, Transaction Processing System, Decision Support System, MIS Model.	The results indicate that the MIS plays an important role in providing the information required for crucial decision-making for the top-level management, directly affecting the organization's performance.

Name of the Article	Name of the Journal	Article Publisher	Author and Publication Year	Citation Score	Method Used	Key Words	Results
Rational Model of Decision Making	Global Encyclopedia of Public Administration, Public Policy, and Governance,	Springer International Publishing	Uzonwanne (2016)	41	Literature Review Method	Decision-making models; Leadership decision making; Rational decisions; Rational planning model	This article's outcome is that rational decision-making is positioned as the most promising, effective, and functional decision-making process for leaders, managers, and individuals, especially when stakeholders, investments, and high stakes are involved.
The Role of Management Information System (MIS) and Decision Support System (DSS) for Managers Decision Making Process	International Journal of Business and Management	Canadian Center of Science and Education	Asemi et al. (2011)	193	Literature Review Method	Management information system, Decision support system, Managers, Decision-making process	It could be concluded that DSS can extend its support to the same steps of the decision-making process and has more roles in decision-making and problem-solving than MIS.
The Role of Management Information Systems in the Effectiveness of Managerial Decision-Making in Greater Irbid Municipality	Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review	Arabian J Bus Manag Review, an open-access journal	Yassine (2017)	11	Quantitative Method	Management information systems; Managerial decision making; Greater Irbid Municipality	The results concluded that management information systems have a medium to high effectiveness role in the greater Irbid municipality and provide the required information to make a managerial decision; their degree of convenience range from moderate to high. The results further highlight a relationship between the use of management information systems and the effectiveness of managerial decision-making. • Improving management information systems impacts the effectiveness of managerial decision-making.
Exploring the Relationship between MIS and Decision-Making Process at Al-Hussein Bin Talal University	International Journal of Engineering and Management Research	www.ijemr.net	Al-Ghonmein et al. (2020)	1	Statistical analysis Method	Al-Hussein Bin Talal University, Decision Support System, Information Systems, Decision-Making	The results confirm that there is a vital role for the management information system in choosing the most appropriate alternative from among the available options. It contributes to increasing the ability of managers and decision-makers at AHU to choose the most suitable choice to solve the problem in a highly efficient and effective manner. The results also found that the MIS improves the implementation and follow-up of the decision-making process. It also contributes to assessing the decision-making process results and determining the efficiency of the proposed solutions in dealing with the problem.

Name of the Article	Name of the Journal	Article Publisher	Author and Publication Year	Citation Score	Method Used	Key Words	Results
Management Information System and Decision-Making Process In Enterprise	Economics management information technology (emit)	Civic Library Europe, Gradanskačitaonica Evropa	Ranisavljević et al., (2012)	26	Literature Review Method	information, management information system, decision-making process	This study concluded that MIS is a renowned concept; having good decision choices guarantees viable business decisions.
The Role of Information Systems in Decision Making: The case of Jordan Bank	Computer Engineering and Intelligent Systems	International Institute for Science, Technology and Education (IISTE): E-Journals	Alkhaffaf, (2012)	20	Empirical study and a structured questionnaire Method	Information systems, decision making.	The study found a strong relationship between information systems and the decision-making process; on the other hand, the results show that Jordan relies heavily on several technologies I.S. used to implement their key activities.

4. RESULTS

R.Q 1. Which are the highest and the lowest cited journal articles in this review research and its main results?

The results highlighted that the most cited journal article (194) is the International Review of Management and Marketing (see Table 1), signifying that MIS and DSS have a meaningful relationship with managers' decision-making processes. The rational decision-making process as the intermediary variable inferred and explained this effect of the decision-making processes.(Ada & Ghaffarzadeh 2015). The role of management information is the second most cited (n = 194) article in MIS and (DSS) for managers' decision-making (see Table 1).

The result showed that the decision-making process emphasizes MIS and DSS providing information services for middle and higher-level managers to make rational decisions (Trivedi 2011). The third most cited (n = 193) article is about the role of MIS and DSS in the manager's decision-making process (see Table 1). The results highlighted that DSS could extend its support to the same steps of the decision-making process and has more roles in the decision-making process and problem-solving than MIS (Asemi et al., 2011). The fourth most cited article (n = 88) is DSS and Knowledge-based strategic management (see Table 1). The results signify that the concept of knowledge management is crucial to strategic management. Through its improvement of knowledge management, the DSS has also been found helpful in improving decisions for more informed strategic decisions (Alyoubi 2015). The fifth most cited article (n = 60) published in the *Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies* is about MIS and

decision-making processes (see Table 1).

The main finding indicates that the number of current business data and information exponentially grows. The results further show that business decision-making is possible only if the necessary information is fast, accurate and adequate staff for most cases (Berisha-Shaqiri 2014). The rational decision-making model is the sixth most cited article (n = 41). It was published in the global encyclopedia of public administration, public policy, and Governance (see Table 1). The results indicate that rational decision-making is the most promising, effective, and functional decision-making process for leaders, managers, and individuals, especially when stakeholders, investments, and high stakes are involved (Uzonwanne 2016). The seventh most cited article (n = 36) published in the *International Journal of Applied Information Systems* is DSS in the higher education system (see Table 1).

The results concluded that the headway and integration of a DSS with the higher education might settle on a compact outlay and anticipated time that would focus on the critical issues of drafting and grasping the most appropriate decisions (Fakeeh 2015). The eighth most cited article (n = 26) is *Information System and decision-making* process. It was published in *Economics Management Information Technology Journal* (Ranisavljević et al., 2012) (see Table 1). The ninth most cited article (n = 20) published in *Computer Engineering and Intelligent Systems journal* is systems in decision making (see Table 1). The study found a strong relationship between information systems and decision-making (Alkhaffaf 2012). The tenth most cited article (n = 11) published in the *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review* is about the role of management information systems in the effectiveness of managerial decision-making. This article concluded that MIS have a medium to high effectiveness role in the greater organizations and provides the required information to make administrative decisions. The results also indicate a relationship between the use of management information systems and the effectiveness of managerial decision-making (Yassine, 2017). The eleventh most cited article (n = 7) is MIS is an effective tool for decision-making. It was published in the *International Journal of Computer Applications* (see Table 1). The findings further signify that MIS plays a key role in providing the information required for crucial decision-making for the top-level management, directly affecting the organization's

performance (Tripathi, 2010). The twelfth most cited article ($n = 6$) published in the *Journal of Business Economics and Management Studies Journal* is DSS (see Table 1). The results concluded that DSS could run with huge information mass and use them randomly and in suitable models to improve decision-making (Khodashahri & Arabi 2018). The least cited article ($n = 1$) published in the *International Journal of Engineering and Management Research* is about the relationship between MIS and the decision-making process (see Table 1). The findings show the important role of MIS in choosing the most appropriate alternative among the available options.

The MIS contributes to increase the ability of managers and decision-makers at AHU to choose the most appropriate alternative to solve the problem in a highly efficient and effective manner. The results highlight that the MIS can support improving the implementation and follow-up of the decision-making process. It also contributes to assessing the results of the decision and determining the proposed solutions' efficiency in dealing with the problem (Al-Ghonmein et al. 2020). Similarly, the least cited ($n = 1$) article published in the *Global Disclosure of Economics and Business Journal* is about the impact of MIS on the decision-making process (see Table 1). The results further concluded that using information systems, i.e. MIS, can influence the decision-making process through the various attributes of information like accuracy, timeliness, relevance, completeness, and cost-effective information. The results highlighted that the success of information systems could enhance the performance of enterprises (Ali, 2019). The least cited article ($n = 1$) published in the *International Review of Management and Marketing journal* is a Comparison of MIS and DSS and their role in the decision-making process of managers of economic affairs and finance (see Table 1). The result indicated that MIS and DSS have a committed relationship with managers' decision-making process and that the rational decision-making process as the intermediary variable inferred and explained this effect (Keshtegar and Vakili 2018).

R.Q. 2. What methods were used in the reviewed articles of this study?

The results confirm that the research method was the literature review method in the twelve reviewed articles ($n = 12$). But the quantitative approach ($n = 2$) was used in two reviewed articles (see Table 1). The results show that the literature view method was used. But three reviewed articles have used the qualitative, empirical study and a

structured questionnaire statistical analysis method. The results supported this author for the *assessment of the current state of research on the roles of MIS in the decision-making process, identification of the experts on MIS on the roles of MIS in the decision-making process, identification of critical questions about MIS roles that need further research, and determination of methodologies used in the previous studies of the same or related topics*

R.Q. 3 What is the impact of MIS on the decision-making process?

The results indicate that MIS can influence decision-making through the various attributes of information like accuracy, timeliness, relevance, completeness, and financial information. The success of information systems will enhance the performance of enterprises. The results further indicate that MIS is vital in choosing the most appropriate alternative from the available options. It contributes to increasing the ability of managers and decision-makers at AHU to select the most suitable choice to solve the problem in a highly efficient and effective manner. The results also found that the MIS improves the implementation and follow-up of the decision-making process. MIS also has a direct impact on the decision-making process. A sound MIS system in an academic organization has positive or impressive outcomes so that good academic performance can be achieved (see Table 1).

R.Q. 4 What is the relationship between management information systems and the managerial decision-making process?

The results indicate a good relationship between MIS and the decision-making process. MIS is directly proportionate with the managerial decision-making process because the correct information at the right time and place with the right person always leads to the right decision, which constantly balances good management in an organization, even in the academic organization has effective performance. The results further highlight a relationship between the use of management information systems and the effectiveness of managerial decision-making. It also highlighted that improving management information systems' impacts on the effectiveness of administrative decision-making processes.

QNO 5. What are the research gaps in the reviewed articles on the roles of MIS in the decision-making process?

Organizations have specific system gaps to drive it using the MIS systems. The results highlighted the research gaps in seven issues of the roles of MIS in the decision-making process. The reviewed articles failed to cover attributed information that is important for decision-making, and using MIS in an organization is necessary for decision-making processes. The reviewed article could not focus on the importance of MIS components of the information system used to collect, organize, extract, analyze, store, and disseminate valuable information for top-level management decision-making processes.

The reviewed articles failed to focus on accuracy, timeliness, relevance, completeness, and financial information. The reviewed articles also forgot to mention that there was a relationship between the use of management information systems and the effectiveness of managerial decision-making processes and that improving management information system impacts the effectiveness of managerial decision-making. Besides these, reviewed articles could not highlight the relationship between management with MIS and the decision-making processes. The results further highlight a research gap in ethical consideration while making a decision, integration of society, academician, and professional for decision making integration of information, technology and management role for effective and efficient decision making.

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

MIS is the process of collecting, organizing, managing, extracting, storing and disseminating information for the decision-making process in an organization for a specific purpose. The actual, dependable, timeliness, updated, frequency and readable information is the primary source of MIS, which plays a vital role in the right decision-making (Devaraju, 2016). Nowadays, organizations are running without the proper use of the MIS department in an organization which may lead in the wrong direction so that they cannot reach the desired destination. The current status of the use of MIS is not based on research and objective motive. Generally, the decision-making process will follow the model known as phases. Herbert Simon made vital contributions to enhance

our understanding of the decision-making process. He pioneered the field of decision support systems. According to (Simon 1960) and his later work with (Newell 1972), decision-making is a process with distinct stages. He has suggested for the first time the decision-making model of human beings. The first is **intelligence** which deals with problem identification and data collection of the problem. The second is the **design** which deals with the generation of alternative solutions to the problem at hand, and the third is **choice**, which is selecting the 'best' solution from amongst the alternative solutions using some criterion. The last phase is **implementation, which deals with implementing the solution in actual practice.**

Simon's decision-making model

Fig. Simon's Model of problem-solving (Herbert Alexander Simon, 2000)

It is the first step towards the decision-making process. In this step, the decision-maker identifies/detects the problem or opportunity. A problem in the organizational context is identifying anything that is not according to the plan, rule or standard. An example of the problem is the detection of sudden very high attrition for the current month by an H.R. manager among workers. On the other hand, opportunity-seeking identifies a promising circumstance that might lead to better results. An example of identification of opportunity is that a marketing manager gets to know that two of his competitors will shut down operations (demand being constant) for some reason in the next three months. It means that he will be able to sell more in the market (Herbert Alexander Simon 2000).

Thus, we can see that the decision-making process is instigated either in the case of a problem or for opportunity seeking. The first stage is clearly the understanding of the stimulus that triggers this process. So, if a problem/opportunity triggers this process, the first stage deals with a complete understanding of the problem/opportunity.

The intelligence phase of the decision-making process involves problem-searching and formulation (Herbert Alexander Simon 2000). Problem finding is compared to some standards, and differences are measured; the differences are evaluated to determine whether there is any problem. Problem Formulation: When the problem is identified, there is always a risk of solving the wrong problem and establishing relations with some problem solved earlier in the problem formulation (Herbert Alexander Simon 2000).

Design is the process of constructing solution outlines for the problem, which are designed to solve the same problem. Each alternative solution is evaluated after gathering data about the solution. The evaluation is done on the basic criteria to recognize each solution's positive and negative attributes. Quantitative tools and models are applied to appear at these solutions. At this stage, the solutions are only outlines of real solutions and are meant to analyze their suitability alone.

Creativity and innovation are required to design solutions. The 'best' key may be identified using quantitative tools like decision tree analysis and qualitative tools like the six thinking hats technique and force field analysis. It is not as easy as it sounds because each solution presents a scenario, and the problem may have multiple objectives making the choice process difficult. Also, uncertainty about the outcomes and strategies makes choosing a single solution difficult. After implementing the previous phases, we find the result. If the result is a failure, we must start the procedure again or go to the last step and check for any mistakes (Shulman & Elstein 1975).

Contemporary issues appear to drive the organization as per the requirement of 21st century market demand and the world's competitiveness. The new related issues are extensive data, internet security, cloud computing, mobile computing, and user interface system (Stergiou et al. 2018). The next issue is the combination of academics, society and professionals in the learning management system. But people evolving is the system with less ethical consideration, which is one of the critical factors in meeting

the organization's desired objectives, even in the academic sector. Ethics cannot be measured and improved in a short interval of time which is embossed in their mind from their childhood, family background, education, culture, behaviour and heredity. It is one of the significant issues in modern society to use MIS in decision-making in academic sectors (Carroll 2000).

The ideal solution, desired status, and improvement requirement

It is one of the most significant issues in modern society to use MIS in decision-making, especially in academic sectors. There are three factors to run the MIS smoothly in an organization. They are top-level management commitment, use of technology and good management (Dubey et al. 2017). Significantly, in developing countries like Nepal, top-level management is frequently changing, and they are appointed and transferred with the help of top-level political forces. Top-level management commitment is one of the significant issues to success in using technology and implementing MIS in an organization if they are ready and interested in that issue. Most Nepalese organizations have been led by such groups of people who are generally not interested in applying the new system in an organization similar to academic organizations. Management is the most compelling element of the organization, where humans, information, and technology can be appropriately managed for the ideal MIS solution. Now society, academics and professionals are not integrated into each other, which may lead to wrong decisions in an organization (Panda & Rath, 2021). To improve this problem, integrated MIS and the three factors mentioned earlier must be appropriately managed.

Research agendas based on the research gap

The research gap may arise in various research agendas more relevant for new researchers: a) *What is the quality of output and measuring system?* b) *What is the investment for such an application?* c) *What kind of relationship is to be established among information technology, management and measuring procedures?* d) *What is the impact of information system on managerial decision-making process?* e) *How does ethical consideration affect making decision process?* f) *How do we integrate society, academicians, and professionals for sound decision making* g) *How do integration of information, technology, and management take place for effective and efficient decision-making?*

Analysis of research agendas

The research agendas are analyzed based on their nature and available resources too. The organization's output quality will be favourable if input quality is available. The accuracy, timeliness, reliability, frequency, understandability, and updated information must be measured qualitatively and quantitatively. The quality product is directly proportionate with the total investment in information, technology, management, and human resources. The use of technology, information and management are interrelated to generate a quality decision in the organization, even in academic sectors. There is a good relationship with society, academicians, and professionals because they depend on each other. Information, proper technology, and effective and efficient management are significant factors in achieving quality output in an academic organization. There are significant threats to middle and top-level managers, whether they function ethically or not. The 21st century is facing many problems due to ethical considerations in management for decision-making.

Final research proposal/ problem in the chosen topic

This research article is interesting for the researchers and incredibly challenging because very few studies have taken place so far. After a long history of such related research, the researcher decided research proposal, so the title effect of MIS on decision-making in academic sectors is selected. The researcher has found very few topics on such related topics for research. Especially in Nepal, few researchers are available on such issues, and resource persons are not available in the current market. This research topic is associated with MIS and the decision-making system, which is integrated with ICT, management, and engineering, so identifying the problem and getting the problem's respective solution is challenging. Playing with complex topics can generate innovations in the research field. The literature review is done to identify the various problems with such research types and minimize the research gap.

ABCD analysis/ slop/ six thinking hats/ other analysis of chosen research proposal

Information is the blood of the academic organization, whereas MIS is the body. Blood circulation is regular only if there is an excellent functional heart. The MIS works as a body's heart, but pure blood is needed for a healthy life (Jones 2014). Similarly, information should cover accuracy, timeliness, relevance, completeness, understanding,

and financial information so that MIS can provide quality output to the middle and top-level management of any academic organization to make the right decision. This research can create significant opportunities for new researchers to analyze and optimize the value of information and its roles for effective and efficient organizational decision-making (Leidner & Jarvenpaa, 1995). This research can create an open door for further research to advance this system in an organization's decision-making activities, which may lead to valuable outcomes. This research benefits the modern world in decision-making activities that generate high revenue, academic performance, innovation, a user-friendly environment, low operation cost, and quality results. The initial investment, risk in data security, technology challenges and complexity for human resource management are increased.

Some constraints are technology updating, frequent changes in top-level management, and investment of huge funds for establishing and implementing technology in the first phase. The major constraint is the continuous change in technology and ethical management of human resources (Oswald et al. 2017). As per the six thinking hats principle, the following can be used to analyze any types of research, which may give an overall analysis of the study. They are Blue Hat: organization and planning, Green Hat: creative thinking, Red Hat: feelings and instincts, Yellow Hat: benefits and values, Black Hat: risk assessment and White Hat: information gathering. These research topics can provide the overall importance of MIS and decision-making in an academic organization which can offer positive analytical thinking and creation for the improvement of the organization.

Organizational improvement is a never-ending process where creative characters, feeling, and thinking always generate benefits and add value to the organization. Every organization consists of various risks, which should be peered at carefully to reduce the risk assessment necessary for that quality information. The effect of MIS on decision-making in the academic organization also has a significant positive impact on quality information. Information, technology resource and management are interrelated to each other. Collecting, organizing, storing, extracting, and disseminating are the processes of quality information generation.

In contrast, good management processes involve planning, organizing, directing, monitoring, system thinking, problem analysis, result review, risk assessment, and controlling (Lin et al., 2007). Similarly, resource management, like human resources, software, hardware resource, network resources, and financial resources, are resource management processes. All these factors are to be controlled through proper MIS in the academic sector for good decision-making, which may positively impact the result in the institution (Lengnick-Hall et al. 2011).

Suggestion to implement research activities according to the proposal

MIS is the primary system of the organization, with an excellent decision-making system. MIS is only possible if there is an information system or use of a computer and supporting system for the computer to an organization. Similarly, in an education system, MIS is one of the significant components of collecting, organizing, analyzing, extracting, storing and disseminating information for the managerial level for decision-making. The right decision can be taken only if the existing system is managed correctly regarding quality information, use of sound and modern technology, and perfect management. Things are to be handled perfectly. The integrated approach of society, academicians, and professionals with technology is a must to make an effective and efficient decision in any academic sector.

Limitation of the Proposal

Limitations are always emphasized for further research activities to improve and adjust the research activities. There are some limitations of resources like technology, management, and information to process data for further application. The researcher cannot define fund requirements, technology, information availability, and technologically sound and knowledgeable human resources for technological management.

Conclusion

Good management is a fundamental requirement of an academic organization. Quality information is the basic root of correct decision-making, and correct decision-making is the perfect activity for the best outcomes. Implementing MIS is the most critical element of any academic organization for getting the right outcome due to good

management. Good management is only achieved if there is quality information, use of MIS and knowledgeable resources in an organization.

REFERENCES

- Ada, Ş., & Ghaffarzadeh, M. (2015). Decision Making Based on Management Information System and Decision Support System. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, III(4), 1–1
- Al-Ghonmein, A. M., Al-Moghrabi, K. G., & Talhouni, H. A. (2020). Exploring the Relationship between MIS and Decision-Making Process at Al-Hussein Bin Talal University. *Exploring the Relationship between MIS and Decision-Making Process at Al-Hussein Bin Talal University*, 10(2). Available at <https://doi.org/doi.org/10.31033/ijemr> and accessed on 12th December 2022.
- Al-Ghonmein, A. M., Al-Moghrabi, K. G., & Talhouni, H. A. (2020). Exploring the Relationship between MIS and Decision-Making Process at Al-Hussein Bin Talal University. *Exploring the Relationship between MIS and Decision-Making Process at Al-Hussein Bin Talal University*, 10(2). <https://doi.org/doi.org/10.31033/ijemr.10.2.6>
- Ali, Md. M. (1019). Impact of Management Information Systems (MIS) on Decision Making. *Global Disclosure of Economics and Business*, 8(2).
- Alkhaffaf, M. (2012). The Role of Information Systems in Decision Making: The case of Jordan Bank. *Computer Engineering and Intelligent Systems*, Vol 3, No.10, (ISSN 2222-2863 (Online)).
- Alyoubi, Bader. A. (2015). Decision Support System and Knowledge-based Strategic Management. *Procedia Computer Science*, 65, 278–284. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2015.09.079>
- Berisha - Shaqiri, A. (2014). Management Information System and Decision-Making AfërdÖta Berisha - Shaqiri Assistant Professor, PhD. Department of Management & Informatics, Faculty of Economics. *Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*, 3(2).

- Carroll, A. B. (2000). Ethical Challenges for Business in the New Millennium: Corporate Social Responsibility and Models of Management Morality. *Business Ethics Quarterly*, 10(1), 33–42. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3857692>
- Devaraju, Dr. P. (2016). The Role of MIS in Business Decision Supporting Applications and Features. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Engineering & Management*, 3(6), 518–521.
- Dubey, R., Gunasekaran, A., Childe, S. J., Papadopoulos, T., Hazen, B. T., & Roubaud, D. (2017). Examining top management commitment to TQM diffusion using institutional and upper echelon theories. *International Journal of Production Research*, 56(8), 2988–3006. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207543.2017.1394590>
- Fakeeh, K. A. (2015). Decision Support Systems (DSS) in Higher Education System. *International Journal of Applied Information Systems (IJ AIS)*, 9(2).
- Herbert Alexander Simon. (2000). *Administrative behaviour: a study of decision-making processes in administrative organizations*. Free Press.
- Jones, M. (2014). A Matter of Life and Death: Exploring Conceptualizations of Sociomateriality in the Context of Critical Care. *MIS Quarterly*, 38(3), 895–925. <https://doi.org/10.25300/misq/2014/38.3.12>
- Keshtegar, Abdolali, and Nadia Vakili. "Comparison of Management Information System and Decision Support System and Its Role in the Decision-Making Process of Managers of Economic Affairs and Finance of Zahedan." *Www.econjournals.com*, International Review of Management and Marketing, 2018, <http://www.econjournals.com>. [Accessed 12 Oct. 2022].
- Khodashahri, N. G., & Arabi, M. M. H. (2018). Decision Support System (DSS). *Singaporean Journal of Business Economics and Management*, 1(6). 12-18
- Leidner, D. E., & Jarvenpaa, S. L. (1995). The Use of Information Technology to Enhance Management School Education: A Theoretical View. *MIS Quarterly*, 19(3), 265. <https://doi.org/10.2307/249596>
- Lengnick-Hall, C. A., Beck, T. E., & Lengnick-Hall, M. L. (2011). Developing a capacity for organizational resilience through strategic human resource management. *Human Resource Management Review*, 21(3), 243–255. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hrmr.2011.05.001>

doi.org/10.1016/j.hrmr.2010.07.001

- Lin, S., Gao, J., Koronios, A., & Chanana, V. (2007). Developing a data quality framework for asset management in engineering organizations. *International Journal of Information Quality*, 1(1), 100. <https://doi.org/10.1504/ijiq.2007.013378>
- Oswald, F. L., Behrend, T. S., Putka, D. J., & Sinar, E. (2017). Big Data in Industrial-Organizational Psychology and Human Resource Management: Forward Progress for Organizational Research and Practice. *Annual Review of Organizational Psychology and Organizational Behavior*, 7(1). <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-orgpsych-032117-104553>
- Panda, S., & Rath, S. K. (2021). How information technology capability influences organizational agility: empirical evidence from the Indian banking industry. *Journal of Indian Business Research*, ahead-of-print(ahead-of-print). <https://doi.org/10.1108/jibr-11-2020-0364>
- Ranisavljević, P., Spasić, T., & Ranisavljević, I. M. (2012). *Management Information System And Decision-Making Process In Enterprise*. www.emit.kcbor.net; Civic Library Europe, (Građanska čitaonica Evropa) ISSN 2217-9011 e-ISSN 2334-6531. <http://emit.kcbor.net>
- Security and Privacy for Storage and Computation in Cloud Computing. (2015). *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)*, 4(12), 525–527. <https://doi.org/10.21275/v4i12.nov151792>
- Shulman, L. S., & Elstein, A. S. (1975). 1: Studies of Problem-Solving, Judgment, and Decision Making: Implications for Educational Research. *Review of Research in Education*, 3(1), 3–42. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0091732x003001003>
- Stergiou, C., Psannis, K. E., Gupta, B. B., & Ishibashi, Y. (2018). Security, privacy & efficiency of sustainable Cloud Computing for Big Data & IoT. *Sustainable Computing: Informatics and Systems*, 19, 174–184. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.suscom.2018.06.003>
- Supriadi, D., Usman, H., & Jabar, C. S. A. (2021). The Moderation Effect of Information Systems on Vocational High School Principal Decision-Making Model. *Jurnal Cakrawala Pendidikan*, 40(1), 43–55. <https://doi.org/10.21831/cp.v40i1.31268>

- Tripathi, K. P. (2010). MIS is an Effective Tool for Decision Making. *International Journal of Computer Applications* (0975 – 8887), 7(11).
- Trivedi, A. (2011). *The Role of Management Information System (MIS) and Decision Support System (DSS) for Manager's Decision Making*. Academia. Available at <https://d1wqtxts1xzle7.cloudfront.net/32041534/8940-33616-1-PB-with-cover>. [Accessed on 11^{Oct} 2022].
- Uzonwanne, F. C. (2016). Rational Model of Decision Making. *Global Encyclopedia of Public Administration, Public Policy, and Governance*, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-31816-5_2474-1
- Yassine, F. A. (2017). The Role of Management Information Systems in the Effectiveness of Managerial Decision Making in Greater Irbid Municipality. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, 7(4).

A Review of an Article Based on the Mixed Methods Approach in Educational Sciences Regarding Teacher Retention Intention in the Asian Context

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Received: November 23, 2022

Revised: December 25, 2022

Accepted: January 8, 2023

Published: January 29, 2023

How to cite this paper:

Adhikari, B.P & Adhikari, R. (2022). A review of an article based on the Mixed Methods Approach in Educational Sciences Regarding Teacher Retention Intention in the Asian context

The OCEM Journal of Management, Technology & Social Sciences, 2(2), 147-177

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Originality: This paper is original and has not been published anywhere else

Paper type: Research paper
J.E.L. Classification: I (2), I (29)

Abstract

The primary objective of this study was to evaluate the different models of the mixed methods approach along with research problems, questions, and data analysis techniques and to review its overall methodology applied to collect data in a selected educational article. A mixed methods approach is a newly emerged research design of this 21st century where both quantitative and qualitative data can be collected one at a time. This study was based on the review of different articles, books, cases, magazines, and newspapers connecting with the mixed methods approach. The key focus of this study was to introduce the mixed methods approach, quantitative and qualitative approaches, evaluate the theoretical strengths and weaknesses of the mixed methods approach, and explicit meaning of both qualitative and quantitative design and its applications in the different fields of research studies.

The results indicate that the study has covered different aspects of the mixed methods approach along with the theoretical weaknesses of the mixed methods approach. The results have also focused on both quantitative and qualitative research approaches along with the mixed methods approach and different designs of the mixed methods approach. The results further indicate that the core designs of the mixed methods approach are contemporary development and expansion designs, the validity and reliability of the mixed methods approach, the generalization of research outcomes, and statistical generalization. It was indicated that the key findings and discussions were also focused on while reviewing different journals and online documents. The results suggest that factors affecting teacher retention and attrition intention were based on the high workload and unsupportive colleagues and administration, which are similar within China, Nepal, India, and Sri Lanka. The results show that approximately 42% of the teachers reported being highly stressed in China; the same scenario has also occurred in the Nepalese context. The implications of this study would be beneficial to young researchers, students, college teachers and master-level students to foreground the knowledge in the mixed methods approach.

Keywords: *Convergent parallel design, mixed methods approach, qualitative approach, quantitative approach, teacher's retention, teacher attrition intention*

1. INTRODUCTION OF THE CHOSEN ARTICLE

This research has chosen the article entitled Chinese teachers' work stress and their turnover intention published by Liu and Onwuegbuzie (2012). It was taken from the *International Journal of Educational Research*: School of Education, Northeast Normal University. This article has mainly focused on teachers' attention to remain or leave the teaching profession. It has also highlighted the factors affecting teacher recruitment and retention in the Asian context, for example, China, Nepal, India, and Sri Lanka. This article has further summarised that approximately 42% of the teachers reported being highly stressed in China; the same scenario has also occurred in Nepal (Liu and Teddlie, 2010; Subedi, 2008). This researcher strongly believes that factors affecting teachers' intention to leave or remain in the teaching profession are mostly the same in both countries, i.e., Nepal and China.

1.1 Justification of the chosen article with the Nepalese context

This researcher has selected this article for the critical analysis of the Mixed Methods Approach because the context of Nepal and China is highly correlated culturally, religiously, socially, educationally and geographically. More importantly, Nepal and China both lie in the Asia continent and have the same educational background. Additionally, this researcher has chosen this article because it reflects the teachers' retention intention, which supports my future dissertation.

This study helps investigate the teachers' retention intention in the Nepalese context. It will be more appropriate to foreground the knowledge on MMA and factors affecting teacher retention or attrition intention in the teaching profession in the Nepalese context because this researcher is also seeking to investigate teacher attrition and retention intention in the Nepalese context (Veldman et al., 2013).

1.2 Major weaknesses of the chosen article

The major weakness of the chosen article is the limited theoretical foundation on teachers' attrition and retention intention in the teaching profession. Furthermore, a lack of cohesiveness between research objectives and questions is another weakness, along with a biased research design. A lack of cohesiveness between qualitative and

quantitative research design and data analysis and the reliability and validity of research findings are other serious weaknesses (Griensven et al., 2014). Grounding the theoretical foundation to set up appropriate research objectives and questions in the research process is imperative. But this researcher did not find sufficient theoretical foundation and other issues mentioned in the chosen article. Each weakness is discussed below with the argument of different researchers and this researcher (Chen and Yang, 2009).

2. THEORETICAL WEAKNESS

Two authors of the chosen article have only summarised the preliminary discussion of teacher attrition intention in the Chinese context; However, the selected article failed to discuss the rich and holistic literature on factors affecting teacher attrition intention in the Chinese context. The chosen article could not examine new teachers' job satisfaction and dissatisfaction (Darling-Hammond, 2003). Furthermore, the article failed to discuss the key factors affecting teachers' retention and attrition intention in the teaching profession. A lack of social respect, student discipline, colleague support, administrative support; appropriate educational policy; political stability; handsome salary, economic and non-economic financial incentives, and an effective performance evaluation mechanism are entirely marginalized in the chosen article (Ingersoll and Smith, 2003). This researcher concentrates on a strong theoretical foundation for teacher recruitment and retention. But the selected article has covered feeble discussion on teachers' intention to leave or remain in the teaching profession.

Skaalvik and Skaalvik (2011) strongly recommended that education theory be linked with educational practices and cover pedagogy, andragogy, curriculum, learning, education policy, organization and leadership. They further suggested that educational thought is informed by many disciplines, for example, history, philosophy, sociology, and psychology. But these disciplines are neglected, and the chosen article has failed to address the critical theories of education, so the literature on teacher attrition in the Chinese context has been marginalized (Macdonald, 1999).

2.1 Weakness of research design of the selected article

Every educational researcher in every discipline needs to be aware of alternative

research traditions to decide which research method should be used while conducting a research activity. Two major research approaches can be used to study the social and individual world, i.e., qualitative and quantitative research. A combination of these two major research approaches in a research study is called MMA. Many research studies have been focusing on MMA at this so that MMA can be applied to collect and analyze data in the field of educational research (Cohen et al., 2011). This researcher believes that it is better to discuss qualitative and quantitative method research initially in the methodological sector than the researchers can strongly focus on the concrete definition of MMA later on. But this researcher did not find any evidence of a correct combination of qualitative and quantitative method research. Two authors of the chosen article seemed biased toward the qualitative method only to collect data and the qualitative interviews. More importantly, this researcher did not find any coherence between the research questions and objectives. This researcher argues that there would be a lack of validity and reliability of research findings because of the lack of coherence between research questions and research objectives. It threatens research findings (Cohen et al., 2007). It is universally accepted that both qualitative and quantitative research methods can develop a new approach to minimize each method's limitations and maximize the strengths of both qualitative and quantitative research methods. This study aims to explain the significant advantages and disadvantages of MMA and its appropriateness in the context of educational research.

3. QUANTITATIVE RESEARCH APPROACH

3.1 Quantitative Research Design

Pilot and Hungler (2013) defined Quantitative Research Methods as a means for testing objective theories by examining the relationship among variables, i.e., dependent and independent variables. Wong (2014) described that a variable is a factor that can be controlled in an experiment. White and Miller (2014) also noted that the quantitative methods are embedded with quantify or amounts. They further stated that data collected during the study is quantified in quantitative methods, which we call statistical evidence. Many writers (For example, Wong, 2014; Pilot and Hungler, 2013; White and Miller, 2014) have explored their standard views that the variables are categorized as dependent

and independent, and the dependent variables are affected by the event of independent variables; for example, the teacher attrition rate is dependent variable and a lack of administrative support is an independent variable because low salary increases teacher attrition and high salary decreases the teacher attrition at schools in Chitwan District. The teacher attrition rate is influenced by the independent variables, for example, low salary, a lack of student discipline, and a lack of administrative support. Jirojwong et al. (2014) noted that quantitative research falls within the philosophical underpinning of Positivism, where a Positivist believes that social reality is objective and single.

Furthermore, Hamer and Collinson (2014) also supported the views of White and Miller (2014). They noted that quantitative methods research attempts to establish statistically significant relationships between dependent and independent variables. It addresses questions by measuring and describing the phenomena based on objective measurement and observation embedded with the cause-and-effect relationship. Ingham-Broomfield (2015) noted that Quantitative Research Designs are categorized into descriptive, relational, Experimental and Quasi-experimental. Ingham-Broomfield (2015) clarified that the descriptive design could be used in both quantitative and qualitative methods. The correlational design can be used in the survey method to determine correlations; the experimental design is purely embedded with quantitative methods research; and the Quasi-experimental design can use observation and questionnaires to collect data (Ostlund, 2011). Quantitative research design is also a crucial step of a research study, so it will be better to present the research design of qualitative methods (see Table 1).

Table 1. Quantitative research design

Area	Quantitative Methods
Purpose of Research	Directed
Research Paradigm	Positivist, Outcome-focused
Sample Selection	Random
Research Protocol	Structure
Data collection	Precise and Numerical
Validity and reliability	Focused on Instrument
Data analysis	Statistical

Source: Creswell (2003)

Quantitative research design is divided into seven sections: directed, positivist, outcome-oriented, random sampling, structured, precise and numerical, focus on instrument, and Statistical. Quantitative research design is more flexible and easier to collect data than qualitative research design because researchers can adjust the latest data while doing data analysis (Opie, 2004).

3.2 Qualitative Research Approach

Denzin and Lincoln (2005) offer an 'initial, generic definition of qualitative research methods:

Qualitative research is a situated activity that locates the observer in the world. It consists of a set of interpretive, material practices that make the world visible. These practices transform the world. They turn the world into a series of representations, including field notes, interviews, conversations, photographs, recordings, and memos to the self. Qualitative research involves an interpretive, naturalistic approach to the world at this level. Qualitative researchers study things in their natural settings, attempting to make sense of or interpret phenomena in terms of the meanings people bring to them (p. 3).

Yilmaz (2013) supported the views of Denzin and Lincoln (2005a) and noted that qualitative research methods explain any research that produces finding not arrived at by statistical procedures and other means of quantification. But this definition is fundamental because it has solely focused on procedures and techniques used to collect and analyze data, ignoring other aspects of research design. Gay and Airasian (2000) disagreed with the views of Yilmaz (2013) and Denzin and Lincoln (2005a). They explored their views that qualitative research methods help collect extensive data on many variables over an extended period in a natural setting to understand that other types of research methods are impossible. Still, this definition also suffers from an identical problem because it uses a quantitative concept to define qualitative terms (Opie, 2004). Qualitative and quantitative designs are equally important, so it will be better to present both methods separately (see Table 2).

Table 2. Philosophical Foundation of the Constructivism

Approaches to subjective viewpoints		Description of the making of social situations	Hermeneutic analysis of underlying structures
Theoretical positions	Symbolic Interactionism Phenomenology	Ethnomethodology Constructionism	Psychoanalysis Genetic Structuralism
Methods of data collection	Semi-structured Interviews Narrative Interviews	Focus groups Ethnography Participant's observation Recording interactions Collecting documents	Recordings Interactions Photography Film
Methods of interpretation	Theoretical coding Content analysis Narrative analysis Hermeneutic methods	Conversation analysis Discourse analysis Analysis of documents	Objective Hermeneutics Deep hermeneutics

Source: Creswell (2003)

The qualitative designs are embedded with approaches to subjective viewpoints, description of the making of social situations, and hermeneutic analysis of underlying structures where theoretical positions, methods of data collection, and methods of interpretation are sub-divisions of qualitative research designs (Lichtman, 2006).

The chosen article also failed to discuss the research perspectives of qualitative methods research which is highlighted in the above table. On the other hand, this researcher also believes that discussing the complete methodological procedures to conduct any research activities is imperative because the holistic discussion of an appropriate research design or methodology ensures the vitality and reliability of research findings (Cohen et al., 2011).

4. MIXED METHODS APPROACH

A Mixed Method approach has been widely applied within educational research for various reasons; for example, this method can ensure the validity and reliability of research findings. The combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches is an exciting topic and continues to be one of discussion. In fact, the different epistemological and ontological assumptions and paradigms related to quantitative and qualitative

research have had a key influence on whether integrating two different methods is possible (Morgan, 2007). Mixed Method research can be viewed as an approach that draws upon each method's strengths and perspectives, recognizing the existence and importance of reality and the influence of human experience as well as the importance of the physical and natural world (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004). They further defined that a mixed research design is a general type of research that includes quantitative and qualitative research data, techniques and methods. All these paradigm characteristics are mixed in one case study. This method design involves research that uses combined data, for example, numbers and text and additional means, such as statistics and text analysis. A mixed method uses both deductive and inductive scientific methods, collects multiple forms of data, and produces eclectic and pragmatic reports (Hall et al., 2014).

4.1 Meaning of Mixed Method Approach

Tashakkori and Creswell (2007) broadly define the Mixed Methods Approach as "research in which the investigator collects and analyses data, integrates the findings and draws inferences using both qualitative and quantitative approaches" (2007:3). Cohen et al. (2011) and Hall et al. (2014) supported the views of Tashakkori and Creswell (2007). They noted that mixed-methods research combines both qualitative and quantitative methods and is also embedded with empirical research that involves collecting and analyzing both qualitative and quantitative data. Creswell and Plano-Clark (2007) also defined MMA differently.

They noted that it is embedded with the focused-on research questions that call for real-life, contextual understandings, multi-level perspectives, and cultural influences. Hall et al. (2014) also summarised that Mixed Method Research (MMA) is the combination of two different paradigms that maximizes the strengths of both qualitative and quantitative approaches and frames the investigation within the proper philosophical and theoretical positions. The definition is given by Hall et al. (2014); Creswell and Plano Clark (2011) are limited and confusing because the definition is not specific to the clear concept of Mixed Method Research and fails to cover the philosophical background of MMA. Yilmaz, 2(013); Hall et al. (2014); Durksen and Klassen (2014) summarized that a mixed research design is a general type of research. It includes

quantitative and qualitative research data, techniques and methods. It involves research that uses mixed methods approach data, for example, numbers and text, as well as additional means, like statistics and text analysis. They further summarised that mixed-methods research uses both deductive and inductive scientific methods, has multiple forms of data-collecting instruments and produces eclectic and pragmatic reports.

The definition noted by Hall et al. (2014); Creswell and Plano-Clark (2007) is supported by Tashakkori and Creswell (2007) and states that in the Mixed Methods Approach, the researcher gathers and analyses data, integrates the findings and draws inferences by applying both quantitative and qualitative approaches. The mixed methods approach is the type of research in which a researcher combines elements of qualitative and quantitative research approaches (e.g., use of qualitative and quantitative viewpoints, data collection, analysis, and inference techniques) for the general purposes of breadth and depth of understanding and corroboration. (Johnson et al. 2007. p. 123).

4.2 The philosophical background of mixed method research design

The chosen article failed to cover the satisfactory level of the philosophical background of Mixed Method Research Design because the philosophical strengths of MMA can ensure to set off proper research questions. The authors of the chosen article also failed to convince the readers to apply MMA design for educational research because the theoretical discussion in the methodological section has been marginalized. This researcher has tried to minimize the limitations of MMA design and explore the meaning, research design, strengths, and limitations of MMA design in the following section so that the readers of this study will be convinced and feel comfortable while reading this study.

Leech and Onwuegbuzie (2009) state the following statement to clarify Mixed Methods Design

The adoption of mixed-method designs has been popular science since the 1960s and is considered the new movement in research (p.266).

Jogulu et al. (2011) supported the views of Leech and Onwuegbuzie (2009) and noted that a third methodology, known as the mixed methods approach, has recently gained

researchers' confidence. They further argued that a mixed method approach is also referred to as the third path, the third research paradigm and the third methodological movement. This researcher also believes that mixed-methods research is an emerging research approach to strengthen the reliability and validity of the research findings (Connelly, 2009). Gorarad and Taylor (2004) noted that mixed methods research has emerged as a third methodological tool to investigate social reality. Cohen et al. (2011) also supported the views of Gorarad and Taylor (2004) and defined the Mixed Methods Approach as the third methodological part of educational research.

Similarly, Johnson and Onwuegbuzie (2004) explained MMA in the same way as Gorarad and Taylor (2004), and Cohen et al. (2011) did in the earlier section. Tashakkori and Teddle (1998), Gorarad and Taylor (2004) and Cohen et al. (2011) have given the same definitions of MMA and further noted that MMA is regarded as the third research paradigm. Known to be an intensely comprehensive technique for research in the social sciences through analysis techniques appear to lead to greater depth and breadth in overall results, from which this researcher can make more accurate inferences with increased credibility on teacher recruitment and retention in the Nepalese context (Tashakkori and Creswell, 2007). Yilmaz (2013) and Philips and Paugh (2005) summarised the mixed methods approach as a research design with two fundamental issues.

The first is a theoretical concern related to any specific disciplines in education, that is, the capacity for mixed methods to benefit a variety of research disciplines, for example, education, psychology, organizational behaviour, and health sciences. They further argued that the MMA advocates using inductive and deductive research logic, which is a great strength. Using an inductive and deductive sequence enables researchers to equally undertake theory generation and hypothesis testing in a single study without compromising one for the other. This researcher also believes that researchers must move more into sophisticated research designs, multiple data sources, and analysis which create divergent views and findings (Tashakkori and Creswell, 2007).

Ostlund et al. (2011) have strongly noted that a Mixed Methods Approach combines qualitative and quantitative methods research. It is increasingly acknowledged as a valuable research method because it can potentially capitalize on the respective

strengths of quantitative and qualitative approaches. They further argued that using triangulation as a methodological metaphor can support a better understanding of the links between theory and empirical findings, aid the development of new theories and challenge the current theoretical assumptions of qualitative and quantitative research methods. But the two authors of the chosen article have completely marginalized the above-mentioned philosophical background of MMA. In the meantime, they also failed to explore the strengths and weaknesses of MMA in their article. Therefore, this researcher has discussed the strengths and weaknesses of MMA in the following section.

The chosen article has applied MMA, but it has missed the philosophical background of MMA. This researcher wonders how MMA was used without discussing its theoretical aspects in the literature section. He further argued that the chosen article needs to focus on the strengths and weaknesses of MMA so that the authors could construct relevant research questions and fit their research process properly to collect data. This researcher argues that the chosen article has neglected the literature on the strengths and limitations of MMA. This researcher has presented some aspects of strengths and limitations in the following section (Creswell and Plano-Clark 2007).

4.2.1 Strengths and weaknesses of MMA

Two authors of the chosen article have failed to discuss the strengths and limitations of MMA. Therefore, this researcher argues that the research design of the selected article was very weak and failed to link each section of the research design because a lack of adequate discussion on the methodological section marginalizes the validity and reliability of research findings (Cohen et al., 2011). Furthermore, this researcher argues that the discussion on the strengths and limitations of MMA can support researchers in successfully managing and fitting their research strategies for educational research (Cronholm and Hjalmarsson 2011). This researcher agreed with the argument of Bryman (2007) and noted that integrating quantitative and qualitative findings could strengthen an overall account of the results, which is not possible by using a single research approach, for example, qualitative or quantitative methods research. Similarly, Bernardi et al. (2007) have also stood up in favour of MMA and argued that MMA

could support to highlight the similarities and differences between particular aspects of a research phenomenon, for example, the recruitment and retention of teachers in Chitwan district, because MMA is the combination of two different approaches. The chosen article has failed to argue that logical issues have most recently powered the use of MMA. The increasing demand for a cost-effective research study, the move away from theoretically driven investigation to research meets policymakers' and practitioners' needs, and the growing competition for research funding. Many authors (For example, Creswell et al., 2011) noted that MMA is a pragmatic perspective that draws on employing "what works," using diverse approaches, giving primacy to the importance of the research problem and questions, and valuing both objective and subjective philosophical knowledge.

Johnson and Onwuegbuzie (2004) stated that a mixed-method approach is the third paradigm in educational research, enabling researchers to conduct more effectively. Greene et al. (1989) summarised that triangulation's core premise as a design strategy is that all methods have inherent biases and limitations, so using *only one method to assess a given phenomenon will inevitably yield biased and limited results. However, when two or more methods that have offsetting biases are used to determine a given phenomenon, and the results of these methods converge or corroborate one another, then the validity of inquiry findings is enhanced* (p. 256)

Caruth (2013) agreed with the views of Greene et al. (1989) and noted that the strengths of MMA design could be summarised in that words, photos, and narratives can be used to add meaning to numbers while numbers can add accuracy to words, photos, and narratives. Cronholm and Hjalmarsson (2011) further argued that MMA could handle a broader range of research questions because the researcher is not limited to one research design, can present a stronger conclusion, and offers enhanced validity through triangulation. They further concluded that MMA could add insight and understanding, which might be missed when only a single research method is applied, for example, qualitative or quantitative study design. In mixed methods studies, investigators intentionally integrate quantitative and qualitative data rather than keeping them separate to ensure the reliability and validity of research findings. Creswell and Tashakkori (2007) also supported the views of Creswell and Tashakkori (2007). They

noted that integrating quantitative and qualitative data can maximize the strengths and minimize the weaknesses of each type of collected data of both research methods, for example, qualitative and quantitative methods research. They further noted that the idea of integration separates current views of mixed methods from older perspectives in which investigators collected both forms of data but kept them separate or casually combined them rather than using systematic integrative procedures.

Johnson and Onwuegbuzie (2004) strongly noted that MMA is beneficial for providing a narrative to add meaning to numbers and using numbers to add precision to narrative data. They further argued that a researcher could generate a theory by applying qualitative research and then test it quantitatively. They also noted that mixed methods allow researchers to answer a broader, more complete range of research questions because they are not limited to one approach. Finally, they noted that the mixed-method approach is the third paradigm in educational research, enabling researchers to conduct more scientifically.

Connelly (2009); Creswell and Plano Clark. (2007) agreed with the views of Cohen et al. (2007) and Johnson and Onwuegbuzie (2004) and added that a researcher could use one method to overcome the weaknesses of another method to identify stronger evidence for a conclusion. Applying qualitative and quantitative data in a study can produce complete knowledge needed to inform the educational practice.

Conversely, Yin (2006) warned that a researcher might find it challenging to conduct both quantitative and qualitative research methods, especially if both data types are collected simultaneously. Therefore, a team approach usually is necessary. Yin (2006) strongly argued that the team could understand multiple methods and the best sequence to conduct the research and also be able to combine the findings of both methods of research into a meaningful product. Yin (2006) further argued that MMA usually is more expensive and time-consuming to conduct research studies because it requires multiple data collection methods and demands more money. They further argued strongly that one of the key criticisms of MMA is that researchers often are not clear on how the findings from qualitative and quantitative data can be integrated to provide a fuller understanding of the phenomenon.

4.2.2 Different models of Mixed Methods Approach

The chosen article failed to explain the different models of MMA and their applications in the research design, so this researcher has highlighted some of the critical research designs of MMA in the following section. Hesse-Biber (2010) highlighted five different logics of Mixed Methods design. Each design influences the complementary strengths of qualitative and quantitative methods: It is further noted that each MMA model is not equally crucial for all research studies because it depends on research questions and objectives chosen by a researcher.

4.2.2.1 Triangulation design

Ostlund et al. (2011) state the following statement to support the importance of triangulation in a research study.

Using triangulation as a methodological metaphor may also support a better understanding of the links between theory and empirical findings, challenge theoretical assumptions and aid the development of the new theory (p.370).

Johnson and Onwuegbuzie (2004) noted that the triangulation design of MMA integrates different methods used independently and simultaneously in the study of the same disciplines. It balances the biases and limitations of qualitative and quantitative methods validity of the research findings will be somehow guaranteed.

4.2.2.2 Complementarity design

It is a design of MMA where results from one method are used to elaborate, enhance, and clarify results from the other method. The MMA will allow the researchers to validate constructs and findings and explore different facets of the same phenomenon (Castro et al., 2010).

4.2.2.3 Development Design

Schifferdecker and Reed (2009) highlighted that the development design of MMA is defined as the process of informing the results from one method to another, typically in a chronological system; for example, qualitative interviews can be used to inform the outline of a subsequent survey.

4.2.2.4 Initiation design

Glik et al. (2005) noted that initiation design aims to find and explore paradoxes and contradictions in the research findings. They further declared that the methods are designed to generate new interpretations and conclusions.

4.2.2.5 Expansion design

Expansion design is the combination of two methods used on different phenomena to extend the scope and range of the study. A typical example is the application of quantitative and qualitative research methods used to explore a research project's outcomes and implementation process, respectively (Greene et al., 1989).

This researcher believes this study should mention the three subtypes of MMA designs. The discussion on this issue can support this researcher in choosing one of the three subtypes designs of MMA for his future dissertation and makes him clear to select the most suitable design of MMA. Johnson et al. (2007) further declared that there are three types of Mixed Methods Approach Designs: qualitative dominant, pure mixed, and quantitative dominant. Creswell, Shope, Plano Clark, and Green (2006) also supported the views of Johnson et al. (2007) also that dominant qualitative MMA is suitable for capturing the complexity of some educational and social issues. The qualitative dominant MMA study offers the enormous possibility for generating new ways of understanding the complexities. The contexts of social experience and enhancing the researchers' capacities for social explanation and generalization; this approach can draw on and extend some of the best principles of qualitative enquiry in the educational context (Creswell and Piano Clerk, 2011).

4.3 Research objectives and research questions

4.3.1 Methodological errors

Two authors of the chosen article have applied the Mixed Methods Approach to collect and analyze the data. But this researcher did not find a proper balance and connectivity between qualitative and quantitative research methods. It is universally accepted that the Mixed Methods Approach is embedded with qualitative and quantitative methods research and balanced quantitative and qualitative research instruments to enhance the

reliability and validity of research findings. But the two authors of the chosen article, Liu and Onwuegbuzie (2012), have focused solely on qualitative research methods rather than quantitative method research, so there was more possibility of violating the research validity and reliability (Cohen et al., 2011). Research validity and reliability are crucial elements of both qualitative and quantitative methods. The validity has recently taken in different forms; for example, in qualitative data, validity is embedded with the honesty; depth, richness and scope of the data achieved; the participants approached; the degree of triangulation, and the impartiality of the researchers (Cohen et al., 2007). Similarly, the next in quantitative data, validity, is deeply rooted in the selection of sampling, appropriate research instrumentation and appropriate statistical treatments of the collected data (Opie, 2004). But this researcher did not find a complete combination between the two research designs, i.e., qualitative and quantitative. A lack of a proper research strategy and a wrong research process made the research findings controversial and doubtful of the chosen article. More importantly, the sampling method was stratified sampling. But two researchers of the selected article failed to apply the principles of the stratified sampling method in their research process because they could not determine the primary, lower-secondary and secondary-level teachers from the sampled schools in China. Two authors chose 30 schools as their sample size but did not mention their teaching levels. I want to raise the question of the generalizability of research findings because it was evident that a less representative sample population threatens the generalizability of the results. This author's concern here is the reliability and validity of research findings because feelings, experiences, and opinions of Pre-primary, Primary, Lower Secondary and Secondary teachers are not necessarily the same in the case of their attrition.

Moreover, collected data could not reflect the feeling of all levels of teachers because the chosen sample of teachers does not represent all levels of teachers. Collecting data from four strata is imperative so that actual causes of teachers' intention to leave or remain in the teaching profession could be holistic and rich. More importantly, the authors of the chosen article have entirely broken the critical principles of the stratified sampling method. Two authors of the selected article have applied the survey method in the chosen article. However, they failed to minimize the limitations of the survey

research method because it is inappropriate to collect data on personal experiences, feelings, opinions, ideas, and views regarding the recruitment and retention of teachers and their intention to leave the teaching profession.

Regarding teachers' retention and attrition intention, it would be much better to arrange qualitative interviews (for example, structured and semi-structured interviews) to foreground the research phenomenon. Therefore, the authors could collect holistic and reliable data on factors influencing the recruitment and retention of teachers in the Chinese context (Inghams-Broomfield, 2015). On the other hand, survey methods research is often applied inappropriately. It is relatively clear-cut and fairly simple to employ, even though this may be more illusion than reality (Flower, 2013).

They argued that the survey methods research could be fairly expensive in both budget and time depending on the data collection methods, for example, survey questionnaires and survey interviews. This researcher believes that data collected in the chosen article might be superficial or inadequate compared to other research methods, for example, behavioural observation. More importantly, two authors of the selected article distributed 600 questionnaires to the sampled teachers. They even compelled them to complete within an hour, which is a very sensitive methodological error because teachers who answered the survey questionnaires within an hour lacked internal validity because limited time blocks holistic and rich data from the respondents and limits the accuracy of research findings (Cohen et al., 2007).

On the other hand, 4.21% of participants were principals. But this researcher is not sure that the data given by principals were fair because there are always controversial thoughts between teachers and administrators regarding the cause of teacher attrition. This researcher believes that the research findings generated by analyzing the data collected from the principles lacked descriptive validity because principals are mostly rigid towards teachers' complaints and understating them while exploring their opinion for the causes of their departure or retention (Brunetti, 2001). The big concern of this researcher is also embedded with the data collected by using the random sampling method in the chosen articles because it is challenging to obtain a truly random sample of many populations, and most probable of low rate of response rates (Flower, 2013).

4.3.2 Sampling errors

Two authors have applied the Stratified Random Sampling Method (SRSM) in the chosen article and insisted on its suitability for educational research. This researcher also agrees with Liu and Onwuegbuzie's (2012) views. They added that a stratified random sample is a valuable blend of randomization and categorization. It also enables qualitative and quantitative research (Watanabe and Keeves 2003). This researcher further declares that a quantitative piece of research enables to use of analytical and inferential statistics.

In contrast, qualitative research targets those groups by insinuating participants who can be approached to participate in the study. But the authors of the chosen article ultimately failed to connect with the merits and demerits of SRSM in their research process. The research findings of the selected article cannot be generalized as they did because the data collected from the principles (4.21%) seemed biased and unreliable. The authors of the chosen article applied a simple random sample method. However, it would be better if they had used a stratified random sample method because it provides greater accuracy than a simple random sample method of the same size and greater correctness of the research findings.

Cohen et al. (2011) argued that a stratified random sample often requires a smaller sample, saves money, and guards against an "unrepresentative" sample. A small sample from a mixed-gender population also ensures that the researchers obtain sufficient sample points to support a separate analysis of subgroups.

4.3.2.1 Research tools

The authors of the chosen article have applied opened-ended questions to collect data on possible reasons for teachers' intention to leave the teaching profession. Two authors used opened-ended questions to collect data in the chosen article.

However, this researcher believes that opened-ended questions as a research tool were inappropriate for collecting data on the causes of teachers' attrition in the Chine context because focus group discussion would add more holistic and rich data for the causes of teacher attrition and retention (Cohen et al., 2011). This researcher further believes

that closed questions would be more beneficial to collect data on teachers' intention to leave the teaching profession because closed questions prescribe the range of responses from which the respondents may choose. This researcher further argues that highly structured closed questions are helpful and generate response frequencies amenable to statistical treatment and analysis.

But also enable comparisons across teachers, for example, Pre-Primary, Primary, Lower Secondary and Secondary level teachers in the sample. They are quicker to code up and analyze than word base data, and often, they are direct to the point and deliberately more focused than open-ended questions (Cohen et al., 2007). The survey questionnaires were used to collect data from the chosen articles, which is an appropriate research tool. However, this researcher suspects that two authors of the selected article might have administered questionnaires according to their interests because there is an assumption that respondents will have an opinion about the matters in which researchers are interested. The assumption is risky because it creates problems while administering questionnaires to temporary teachers. It may write anything rather than nothing, which means that the opportunity should be provided for respondents to indicate that they have no opinion on a particular question and feel the question does not apply to them. But this researcher could not find any options in the questionnaires for Chinese temporary teachers in the chosen article (Flower, 2002).

More importantly, the questionnaires applied by the two authors in the selected article were very confusing and difficult to understand for all levels of teachers because there is the issue of choice of vocabulary and the concepts and information behind the administered questionnaires (Opie, 2004). The next issue is English, where questionnaires were administered in English. This researcher did not find any pieces of evidence that all Chinese teachers from different levels could understand the English language correctly. They could not answer the survey questionnaires with complete confidence distributed by the two authors of the chosen article. The language and the concept should be written within the grasp of Chinese respondents because the researcher is interested in and has a background in a particular topic is no guarantee that the respondents will be minded (Vinton, 2015).

The effect of the questionnaires on the respondent has to be considered carefully. But this researcher did not find any supporting evidence to minimize the questionnaire's limitations in the research process (Lichtman, 2006). He further argues that the survey questionnaires can answer the questions of what; where; when; and how, but it is not so easy to provide the answers to why questions by administering questionnaires.

Furthermore, a questionnaire can rarely prove causal relationships and focus on fact-finding. This researcher further argues that the issue of teachers' intention to leave the teaching profession is specific, so it needs to be discussed holistically for rich data that can be collected using qualitative interviews. But the authors of the chosen article failed to address the issues raised by Lichtman (2006) regarding the qualitative methodology.

This researcher suggests that the two authors of the chosen article would have collected valid and reliable data if they had applied the Focus Group Interviews as a research tool. Because More and more research has pointed out that focus group interview is one of the most common methods for collecting qualitative data in the academic arena (Jamieson and Williams, 2003). Cohen et al. (2011) also supported the views of Jamieson and Williams (2003). They added their opinions on the significance of focus group interviews in educational research because focus group interviews help collect data on teachers' attributes, values, experiences and views for their recruitment and retention, as this researcher believes.

4.3.2.2 Convergent design of mixed methods approach

Convergent Parallel Design is one of the popular mixed methods designs. Initially, quantitative data are generally collected by the survey questionnaire, and the interview collects qualitative data, focus group discussion, and narrative storytelling. After a data analysis of both quantitative and qualitative data, similar results are merged into one pile and interpreted rigorously and supported by the qualitative results, and support to foreground the quantitative results (Creswell and Plano Clerk, 2011). The convergent parallel design of the mixed methods approach can be framed (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Mixed methods design

Source: Creswell and Piano Clark (2011)

4.4 Data analysis issues of the selected article

The chosen article has applied descriptive statistics as a quantitative data analysis technique and comparative content analysis as a qualitative data analysis technique. Quantitative data analysis is a powerful research tool from the positivist tradition. It is often associated with large-scale research but can also serve smaller-scale research studies, with case studies, action research, correlational research and experiments (Cohen et al., 2007). Qualitative data analysis involves organizing, accounting and explaining the collected data; in short, making sense of data in terms of the participants' definitions of the situation does not consist of patterns, categories, and regularities (Cohen et al., 2011). They further noted that qualitative data could be analyzed using different techniques (e.g., Analytic Induction, Constant Comparison, Typological Analysis and Enumeration Analysis). Johnson and Onwuegbuzie (2004) summarised the steps in data analysis in a mixed-method approach: data collection, data analysis, data reduction, data display, and then data transformation to other rounds. After this, they further recommend performing the following steps in the order of data

analysis: data consolidation, data correlation, data comparison, data integration, data interpretation, data legitimation, drawing conclusions and producing a final report. But the chosen article failed to address these crucial steps when analyzing the collected data. Furthermore, two authors of the selected article also could not follow the crucial steps of data analysis; recommended by Johnson and Onwuegbuzie (2004).

4.4.1 Validity and reliability of research findings

The use of triangulation through complementary methods enabled the consideration of many facets of the given problem in a research study. Many authors (for example, Creswell and Miller, 2000; Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004; Mertens, 2005, Carcelli and Greene, 1993; Creswell and Miller, 2000; Greene et al., 1989; Jick, 1979; Mathison, 1988) argue that triangulation increases the validity and reliability of the data. Flick (2005) also supported the views of Creswell and Miller (2000); Johnson and Onwuegbuzie (2004); Mertens (2005) added that triangulation is a validity procedure where researchers can search for the convergence among multiple and different sources of information to form themes in a study. They further noted that triangulation could be more than a scale for validity and reliability. Cohen et al. (2007) argued that triangulation could also capture a more complete, holistic, and contextual portrayal of the units under study. On the other hand, the study of Fraenkel and Wallen (2003) argued that techniques to enhance validity, for example, continuing the data collection over a sufficiently long period and collecting data in as many contexts and situations as possible, will ensure a comprehensive picture of the phenomenon. But this researcher did not find any evidence in the chord article; published by Liu and Onwuegbuzie (2012).

4.4.2 Research generalizability

Pilot and Beck (2010) noted the following statement for the definition of generalizability.

A generalization is an act of reasoning that involves drawing broad conclusions from particular instances, that is, making an inference about the unobserved based on the observed (p.1451).

Kerlinger and Lee (2000); Polit and Beck (2008) noted that generalizability is

considered a primary criterion for evaluating a qualitative research study's quality. They further declared that most qualitative studies aim to provide a rich, contextualized understanding of human experience through intensive research of cases. Cohen et al. (2007) noted that generalization is embedded in the context of the sampling population because a larger sampling population ensures the strength of generalizability based on quantitative data. They further concluded that generalizability is very weak in more minor sampling data based on qualitative data.

The chosen article was biased toward qualitative research methods. Two authors of the selected article argued that they had applied MMA. But this researcher, as a reader, found that most of the data were collected using qualitative tools, for example, qualitative interviews and focus group discussions; however, two authors of the chosen article generalized the research findings for the whole Chinese population. Therefore, it is a completely unacceptable and invalid generalization because the issue of generalization is even more complicated and controversial in qualitative methods research. Thorne (2009) argued that qualitative researchers seldom worry explicitly about the issue of generalizability and cannot cover a larger population. The generalization can be categorized as follows.

4.4.3 Statistical generalization

Lincoln and Guba (1985) referred to nomothetic generalization and further argued that quantitative researchers begin by identifying the population to which they wish to generalize their results. Furthermore, this researcher did not find the selected sample population representative of the whole population. This author further believes that the best strategy for achieving a representative sample population is to use probability (random sampling) methods. This method can give every member of the population an equal chance to have participated in the study with a determinable likelihood of selection (Creswell and Piano-Clerk, 2011). Still, the chosen article ultimately failed to address this critical issue of representative sampling (Polit, 2010). This researcher argues that a random sample is one of the supporting tools through which the statistical generalization model can be enacted (Cohen et al., 2007).

5. RESULTS

The article's authors have summarised some key issues of teachers' attrition and retention intention. For example, there was a lack of administrative support, student discipline; handsome salary; student motivation; and over workload. However, the research findings raised many ethical dilemmas, reliability, validity, and generalizability of the research findings in the chosen article. Eeva-Mari Ihantola Lili-Anne Kuhn (2011) states the following statement.

Threats to the internal validity of quantitative work may occur throughout the research process. A good research design is always of crucial importance when pursuing high internal validity. During research design, the threats to internal validity include insufficient knowledge of or contradictions in the logic. However, deficiencies in the later stages of research, i.e., during data collection, analysis, and interpretation, can also lead to studies with low internal validity (p.42).

Earlier, this researcher pointed out a mismatch between research questions and study design. This threatened the contextual validity during the research design phase because two authors had biased to qualitative research design and manualized the quantitative research design (Lillis, 2006). This researcher found that two authors had used excessive qualitative research instruments while collecting data, for example, focus group interviews, observation, and qualitative interviews. More importantly, the research findings of the chosen article lacked internal validity because of the observer-caused effect, observer bias, researcher bias, data access limitations, and complexities and limitations of the human mind of the researchers (Dellinger and Leech, 2007). Finally, the research findings also lacked contextual validity during data analysis and interpretation, for example, a lack of descriptive validity of settings and events to effect size (Onwuegbuzie and Leech, 2007). This researcher further argues that there was a lack of cohesiveness between research objectives and research questions in the earlier section of the chosen article, so the findings should have missed the internal validity and reliability of the research findings.

On the other hand, the research findings of the chosen article are embedded with a lack of clear and standard instructions and measurement instruments description of items

ambiguously. So those research findings were misinterpreted; abstract concepts were not measured with enough indicators of a similar kind and different administration conditions. More specific threats were likely to exist in the MMA of the chosen article. When quantitative and qualitative approaches were combined in the research design, data collection, analysis and interpretation of data because there was not only a lack of combination of data analysis of quantitative and qualitative methods and tools but also designed wrong research design and research process (Collins et al., 2006) so that this researcher earlier criticized the research process.

6. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This article has mainly focused on teachers' retention and attrition intention in the teaching profession. It has also highlighted the factors affecting teacher recruitment and retention in the Asian context, for example, in China, Nepal, India, and Sri Lanka. Approximately 42% of the teachers reported being highly stressed in China; the same scenario has also taken place in the Nepalese context as well (Liu and Teddlie, 2010; Subedi, 2008). This researcher found it interesting to review this article because there were many looping holes in the research questions, objectives, and design. This author enjoyed reading the article *entitled the level of teacher job satisfaction and motivation policies* (Chen & Yang 2009). This researcher has tried to point out all the weaknesses of the chosen article and highlighted some critical issues of MMA which were not presented in the selected article. The chosen article also suffered from a strategy for obtaining a justified meta-inference. Because the selected article failed to maintain a clear understanding of the meaning of qualitative and quantitative data when collecting, analyzing, and interpreting it and also was unable to use peer reviews to obtain a justified viewpoint and use participant review to receive a justified perspective, and finally integrate the parts (Stutchbury and Fox, 2009). There might be other critical issues of research design and process that this researcher could not identify in the chosen article. However, this researcher has presented some vital MMA issues for th4 future research studies (Adhikari 2022).

Methodological reflection

The integrated, mixed methods design allowed this author to combine hypothesis testing and hypothesis generation in a single study. Mixed methods research in educational studies can play an important role in developing research in teacher forms of induction support. Results obtained from different methods can enrich the understanding of teachers' retention and attrition problems and questions. In this regard, mixed methods research may add value and contribute to advance results through the use of triangulation methods. The current review has contributed a deep understanding of new teachers' retention or attrition intention in the profession based on the selected article following a mixed methods approach in their study.

Because it is an easy-to-use framework for collecting and initially analyzing quantitative data and applying the results to inform data collection in subsequent phases, using a mixed methods design also made the selected study's outcomes more valid and reliable concerning what it had to measure and what it really measured. Another benefit of the current review of the article chosen was gained by studying the convergent parallel design to collect and analyze two independent strands of quantitative and qualitative data simultaneously in a single phase, followed by first quantitative and then qualitative data collection. The selected article applied the convergent parallel design, which supported the aims of the data analysis of the review article to prioritize two different methods equally, to keep the data analysis independent, and to mix the results and try to look for convergence, divergence, contradictions and relationships of the two sources of data during the data analysis (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011).

However, the convergent parallel design was challenging for reviewing the selected article's methodology because it requires considerable effort and information to consider the consequences of having different sample sizes when merging the two data sets (see Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011). The purposes of both quantitative and qualitative methods are incredibly different (generalization vs in-depth description). The difficulty in combining two groups of similar questions in the qualitative interview and in the survey questionnaire and their outcomes in a meaningful way was another challenge of this study. The convergent parallel design was also somewhat challenging in managing the data when the quantitative and qualitative results did not agree on specific points of this review (Östlund, Kidd, Wengström, & RowaDewar, 2011).

REFERENCES AND BIBLIOGRAPHIES

- Adhikari, B. P. (2022). *An investigation of the impact of the key components of the induction programme on new teacher retention in Chitwan district, Nepal. ResearchGate; ResearchGate. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication>, accessed on 23rd November 2022.*
- Blenker, P. and Christensen, P.R, (2010) *Hunting the entrepreneurial expertise: entrepreneurs in education", in Fayolle, A. (Ed.), Handbook of Research in Entrepreneurship Education: International Perspectives, Edward Elgar,*
- Brunetti, G (2001). Why do they teach? A study of job satisfaction among long-term high school teachers, *Teacher Education Quarterly; 28(2): 9–74*
- Caracelli, V. J. and Greene, J. C, (1993). Data analysis strategies for mixed-method evaluation designs. *Educational Evaluation and Policy Analysis, 15:2, 195–207.*
- Caruth, GD (2013). Demystifying Mixed Methods Approach Design: A review of Literature: *Mevlana International Journal of Education; 3:2, 112-122*
- Castro, F. G., Kellison, J. G., Boyd, S. J., and Kopak, A (2010). A methodology for conducting integrative Mixed Methods Approach and data analysis: *Journal of Mixed Methods Approach, 4:4, 342-360*
- Chen, H., and Yang, S. (2009). The level of teacher job satisfaction and motivation policies: *School Administration and Development: 12, 20–24*
- Collins, K.M.T, Onwuegbuzie, A.J. and Sutton, I.L, (2006). A model incorporating the rationale and purpose for conducting mixed-methods research in special education and beyond, *Learning Disabilities: A Contemporary Journal; 4:1, 67-100.*
- Connelly, LN, (2009). Mixed Methods Studies; *Medsurg Nursing: 18:1, 31-32*
- Creswell, J, Plano-Clark V. 2007. *Designing and Conducting Mixed Methods Approach: Thousand Oaks: Sage*
- Creswell, J. W, (2007). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches* (2nd ed.). Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications.

- Creswell, J. W., and Plano Clark, V. L, (2011). *Designing and conducting Mixed Methods Approach* (2nd ed.). Thousand Oaks, California: Sage Publications Inc.
- Creswell, J. W., Shope, R., Plano Clark, V. L., and Green, D, (2006). How qualitative interpretive research extends Mixed Methods Approach; *Research in the Schools*, 13:1; 1–11
- Creswell, J.W, (2003). *Research Design Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*; New Delhi, Sage Publication
- Creswell, J.W., and Tashakkori, A, (2007). Developing publishable mixed methods manuscripts. *Journal of Mixed Methods Approach*. 1:2, 107-111.
- Creswell, JW. Klassen, AC., Plano Clark, VL. Smith, K.C, (2011). Best Practices for Mixed Methods Approach in the Health Sciences; Online resource retrieved from https://tigger.uic.edu/jaddams/college/business_office: accessed at 15th A
- Creswell, J. W. and Miller, D. L. (2000). Determining validity in qualitative inquiry: *Theory into Practice*, 39:3, 124–130
- Curtis E, Redmond R, (2007). Focus groups in nursing research; *Nurse Res*; 14:25-37.
- Darling-Hammond, L. (2003). Keeping good teachers: *Educational Leadership*, 60:8, 7–13
- Dellinger, A.B. and Leech, N.L, (2007). Toward a unified validation framework in Mixed Methods Approach; *Journal of Mixed Methods Approach*; 1:4,309-32.
- Denzin, N. K., and Lincoln, Y. S. (Eds.). (2005). *Handbook of qualitative research (3rd ed.)*. Integrating Quantitative and Qualitative approaches in the Social and Behavioural Sciences; Thousand Oaks; Sage Publication
- Durksen, T and Klassen, RM, (2014). Weekly self-efficacy and work stress during the teaching practicum: A mixed methods study: *Learning and Instruction*; 33:158-169
- Eeva-Mari Ihanntola Lili-Anne Kihn, 2011. Threats to validity and reliability in mixed methods accounting research; *Qualitative Research in Accounting and Management*; 8(1), 39 - 58
- Flick, U, (2005). *An introduction to qualitative research*; London: Sage Publications.
- Flower, FJ, (2013). *The Survey Research Methods*; USA, Sage Publication

- Glik, D.C., Parker, K., Muligande, G., Hategikamana, B., (2005). Integrating qualitative and qualitative survey techniques. 1986–87: *International Quarterly of Community Health Education*: 25 (1–2); 115–133
- Greene, J. C., Caracelli, V. J. and Graham, W. F, (1989). Toward a conceptual framework for mixed-method evaluation designs. *Educational Evaluation and Policy Analysis*, 11(3), 255–274.
- Griensven, H.V., Ann P. Moore, AP., Valerie Hall, V, (2014). Mixed Methods Approach-The best of both worlds? *Manual Therapy* 19(4); 367-371
- Hall, V., Moore, AP., Griensven, H.v, (2014). Mixed Methods Approach-The best of both worlds? *Manual Therapy*: 19: 367-371
- Hesse-Biber , S.N, (2010). *Mixed Methods Approach: Merging Theory with Practice*: New York, Guilford Press
- Ingersoll, R. M., and Smith, T. M, (2003). The wrong solution to the teacher shortage; *Educational Leadership*; 60:8, 30–33
- Ingham-Broomfield, RB (2015). A nurses' guide to Quantitative Research; *Scholarly Paper*: 32:2, 32-398
- Jamieson L, Williams LM, (2003). Focus group methodology: explanatory notes for the novice nurse researcher; *Contemp Nurse*; 14:271-80
- Jick, T. D. (1979). Mixing qualitative and quantitative methods: Triangulation in action. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 24:4; 602–611.
- Jogulu, UD. Pansori, J., Botswana, G (2011). "Mixed methods; a research design for management doctoral dissertation" *Management Research Review*; 34(6); 687-701
- Johnson, R. B., Onwuegbuzie, A. J., and Turner, L. A, (2007). Toward a definition of Mixed Methods Approach. *Journal of Mixed Methods Approach*, 1(2), 112–133
- Lillis, A (2006). *Reliability and validity in field study research*", in Hoque, Z. (Ed.), *Methodological Issues in Accounting Research: Theories and Methods*, Paramus, London,
- Liu, S and Onwuegbuzie, AJ, (2012). Chinese teachers' work stress and their turnover intention: *International Journal of Educational Research*: 53(7): 160–170

- Liu, S., and Teddlise, C (2010). Differences in perceptions of effective schools' processes in differentially effective schools in China: *International Journal of Management in Education*, 4, 348–368
- Macdonald, D (1999). Teacher attrition: a review of literature: *Teaching and Teacher Education: 15(9)*, 835-848
- Mathison, S (1988). Why triangulate? *Educational researcher*, 17(2), 13–17
- Mertens, D. M, (2005). *Research and evaluation in education and psychology: Integrating diversity with quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methods* (2nd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications
- Onwuegbuzie, A.J. and Johnson, R.B. (2006). The validity issue in mixed research", *Research in the Schools: 13 (1)*, 48-63.
- Östlund, U., Kidd, L., Wengström, Y., & Rowa–Dewar, N. (2011). Combining qualitative and quantitative research within mixed method research designs: *A methodological review. International Journal of Nursing Studies*, 48(3), 369–383
- Ostlund, U., Kidd, L., Wengstron, Y. and Rowa-Dewar, N. (2011). Combining qualitative and quantitative research within mixed method research designs: A methodological review; *International Journal of Nursing Studies: 48(5)*, 369-383
- Pilot, DF and Beck, C.T, (2010). Generalization in quantitative and qualitative research: Myths and strategies; *International Journal of Nursing Studies; 47(11)*, 1451–1458
- Schifferdecker, K. E., and Reed, V. A, (2009). Using Mixed Methods Approach in medical education: Basic guidelines for researchers. *Medical Education: 43(5)*, 637-644.
- Skaalvik, EM and Skaalvik, S, (2011). Teacher job satisfaction and motivation to leave the teaching profession: Relations with school context, feeling of belonging, and emotional exhaustion: *Teaching and Teacher Education; 27:* 1029-1038
- Stutchbury, K and Fox, A, (2009). Ethics in educational research: introducing a methodological tool for effective, ethical analysis; *Cambridge Journal of Education; 39(7)*.489-504

- Subedi, B.S, (2008). School leadership as a major domain of school effectiveness; *Teacher Education*; 6(4), 102-120; Retrieved from <http://www.nced.gov.np>; accessed on 25th April 2015
- Thorne, S., (2009). The role of qualitative research within an evidence-based context: can meta-synthesis be the answer; *International Journal of Nursing Studies*: 46(9), 569–575.
- Veldman, I., Tartwijk, JV, Brekelmans. Wubbels, T (2013). Job satisfaction and teacher-student relationships across the teaching career: Four case studies: *Teaching and Teacher Education*; 32 (12); 55-65
- Vinten, G (2015). Open versus closed questions – an open issue", *Management Decision*; 33: 4: 27 - 31
- Watanabe, R and Keeves, J (2003). *International handbook of educational research in the Asia-Pacific*, Paris, France, Springer Publication
- Yilmaz, K (2013). Comparison of Quantitative and Qualitative Research Traditions: epistemological, theoretical, and methodological differences: *European Journal of Education*: 48(2), 311–325
- Yin, R.K (2006). Mixed Methods Approach: Are the methods genuinely integrated or merely parallel? *Research in the Schools*, 13(1), 41-47

Reward and Job Satisfaction: An Evidence from Private Colleges of Nepal

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Received: November 24, 2022

Revised: December 26, 2022

Accepted: January 09, 2023

Published: January 29, 2023

How to cite this paper:

Mishra, S. & Adhikari, B.P (2022).
Reward and Job Satisfaction: An
Evidence from Private Colleges of
Nepal

*The OCEM Journal of
Management, Technology & Social
Sciences, 2(2), 178-190*

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Oxford College of Engineering and
Management

Originality: This paper is original
and has not been published
anywhere else

Paper type: Research paper

J.E.L. Classification: I (2), I (29)

Abstract

Human resources are the pivot of organizational effectiveness and the most significant asset an organization can hold. Retaining a skilful and well-equipped workforce in an organization is pertinent to an institution's growth and overall performance. Satisfied employees certainly contribute to the organization's competitive advantage over its competitors. The present study investigates the relationship between employees' rewards and job satisfaction in Nepalese private colleges. The instrument used in information gathering was a structured questionnaire.

The study employed a descriptive survey design in gathering data from 400 members of the teaching and non-teaching staff at private colleges. The data were analyzed using percentages, means, and correlation. The results indicate a positive correlation ($r = .460$) between the reward system and satisfaction. It demonstrates that if there is a change in the reward system by a point, it will bring a change in satisfaction by .460 points. The implications of this study would be beneficial for college educators, young researchers, education leaders, administrators, private college investors, and college teachers to understand the current teachers' retention intention.

Keywords: *College employees, job satisfaction, mean values, reward systems,*

1. INTRODUCTION

Job satisfaction refers to an employee's perception of their jobs, and the work environment refers to how much they like their jobs (Meyer, Stanley, & Herscovitch, 2002). The level of job satisfaction reflects - and is affected by - one's work experiences, present situation, and future expectations. No single model of job satisfaction applies to all work settings because there is no common explanation of what factors and mechanisms account for such an elusive attitude and subjective concept (Schermerhorn, 1991). Although several studies have examined job satisfaction, very few have examined the job satisfaction of college employees. Colleges impart higher education, an indispensable development tool for any country. Colleges worldwide are expected to cultivate new knowledge, give the right kind of leadership, and promote equality and social justice.

It can be achieved when there is job satisfaction among the staff of the institution (Noe, Hollenbeck, Gerhart, & Wright, 2006). However, Tessema & Soeters (2006) found an elusive difference: respondents who give importance to high income are more likely to prefer private-sector employment but less likely to work for the public sector. The unique employees' rewards, motivation and job satisfaction help create unique (Conti, 2005) and dynamic capabilities that drive competitiveness for public and private organizations (Creswell, 2007). Employee motivation is affected by incentives, rewards, and recognition. Today's employees are involved in activities for their benefit and feel intrinsic motivation as their work is enjoyable and satisfactory (Vansteenkiste, 2005).

Recognition and rewards are crucial to motivate employees for better performance (Lawler, 1986). A well-designed reward system can boost an organization's effectiveness and output significantly. Complex reward systems are required today to satisfy the demands of a more diversified workforce. Firms are increasingly recognizing the importance of focusing on the complete remuneration package for employees. Businesses are also developing more elaborate recognition programs focusing on non-monetary benefits for an employee (Malhotra, Budhwar, & Prowse, Linking rewards to commitment: an empirical investigation of four UK call centres, 2007). Many researchers investigated these factors that are very important to an employee's career.

The research has found a high positive correlation between overall job satisfaction and organizational commitment, while job satisfaction with rewards like promotions, pay, supervision and employee relationships (Mathieu & Zajac, 1990).

This study aims to investigate the relationship between reward and motivation and job satisfaction of teaching and non-teaching staff of private colleges. This study examines the relationship between rewards with job satisfaction of teaching and non-teaching employees of private colleges in Nepal. Hence it is important to conduct the study in Nepalese private colleges regarding employee reward and job satisfaction.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Organizations of all sizes, public and private, governmental and non-governmental, profit-making and philanthropic, are adopting reward practices as they compete for essential talents and human capital. As Bowen (2000) argued, in a world of downsizing, where achieving more with less is the norm, reward and recognition are critical to raise morale and build goodwill among employees and supervisors. Malhotra et al. (2007) define rewards as 'all forms of financial return, tangible services and benefits an employee receives as part of an employment relationship'. Employers expect employees to do or produce assigned tasks to their satisfaction. In contrast, employees expect their employers to pay them fair compensation (rewards) after they dutifully deliver what is expected (Eshun & Duah, 2011).

A reward is given or received in return or recompense for service, merit, hardship, etc. The Cambridge dictionary defines it as "something given in exchange for good behaviour or work". Some theorists also refer to reward as compensation. Mathis and Jackson (2004) believe that people are compensated for their contributions to the company through salaries, incentives, and benefits. Most firms today reward their employees based on their ability to meet the company's important business goals. Mayo (1998) argues that if insufficient rewards are given, many organizations cannot instil the joy of working in executing duties and responsibilities. Again, the reward is a visible means of recognizing good performance and letting employees know that the firm appreciates their efforts (Evans & Lindsay, 2003).

Even though people work for salary or wages (rewards), there are numerous ways of rewarding (motivating) employees according to the task or function performed (Eshun & Duah, 2011). The goal of using rewards is to stimulate or induce behaviours in employees that are favourable to improve performance while discouraging behaviour employers and management consider detrimental to organizational effectiveness and efficiency. Thus, rewards serve as a means of motivating desired behaviours (Danish & Usman, 2010). Rewards may be classified into extrinsic/external and intrinsic/internal. Shanks (2007) posits extrinsic rewards "are a host of external things (tangible) that managers can provide that may serve as incentives for employees to increase their productivity". These, among others, include money, benefits, flexible schedules, promotion, job responsibilities, change in status, praise and feedback, a good boss, a nurturing organizational culture, etc.

Tangible rewards (financial rewards) may be direct or indirect. Direct financial rewards refer to an employee's pay in the form of wages, salaries, bonuses, commissions, incentives, merit pay, and stock options. To put it another way, direct financial rewards are divided into base pay and variable compensation (performance-based pay). The fundamental remuneration that an employee receives, which can be a wage or a salary, is determined by both external and internal factors. The former includes labour market conditions, market rates, and government effects. The latter includes employment evaluation, collective bargaining with employee representatives, individual agreements, and so forth. These rewards are based on the amount of time worked and are the primary means through which most employees are directly compensated (Mathis & Jackson, 2004).

Satisfaction is an evaluative phrase that refers to a liking or disliking attitude (Ivancevich, 2004). As a result, job satisfaction is a pleasant emotional state that results from assessing one's work experience. Dissatisfaction, on the other side, arises when a person's job expectations are not met. Mathis and Jackson (2004) explain that the important factor in job satisfaction is what employees expect from their jobs and what they receive as rewards. Job satisfaction, as defined by Locke (1976) cited in (Gruneberg, 1979), is "a pleasurable positive emotional state as a result of work appraisal from one's job experiences".

According to Mumford (1991), cited in Buitendach and Witte (2005) and Sempene, Rieger, and Roodt (2002), the most common aspects of job satisfaction are work, promotion, recognition, benefits, working conditions, supervision, coworkers, company and management. In the same way, Robbins (2001) mentions the more important factors conducive to satisfaction are mentally challenging work, equitable rewards, supportive working conditions and supportive colleagues. He goes on to say that a good personality-job match and an individual's genetic predisposition have a role in job happiness. Agreeing with the factors mentioned earlier, Spector (2000) added status and job content as probable causes of job satisfaction and, conversely, organizational structure as the probable source of dissatisfaction. According to Mumford (1991), Job satisfaction can be analyzed and rated in terms of the fit between what the company requires and what employees want, as well as the fit between what the person wants and what they actually get. Furthermore, numerous authors have pointed out that employee satisfaction is the outcome of a combination of benefits rather than a single reward (Bessell, Dicks, Wysocki, & Kepner, 2002).

Extrinsic and intrinsic incentives are both critical, according to evidence from many studies conducted over the years. Ali and Ahmed (2009) established a substantial affiliation between reward and recognition, and similarly in employee motivation and job satisfaction. According to the study, offering awards and recognition to employees would result in a significant change in job motivation and happiness. Many studies have been conducted on employee rewards in various organizations. However, none of these studies provides an accurate picture of private college employees' reactions. There is no study on the effect of reward systems on job satisfaction among employees of private colleges in Nepal.

Research Objective

This study aims to identify the attitudes and experience of private college staff toward reward strategy and job satisfaction. This study's main objective was to examine the employees' reward systems and job satisfaction in Nepalese private colleges.

Research Hypothesis

H01 There is no significant relationship between reward systems and employee satisfaction

3. METHODOLOGY

The philosophical foundation of the quantitative approach

Postpositivists hold a deterministic philosophy in which causes (probably) determine effects or outcomes. Thus, the problems studied by postpositivists reflect the need to identify and assess the causes that influence outcomes, such as those found in experiments. It is also reductionistic in that the intent is to reduce the ideas into a small, discrete set to test, such as the variables that comprise hypotheses and research questions (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). The knowledge that develops through a postpositivist lens is based on careful observation and measurement of the objective reality. It exists "out there" in the world. Thus, developing numeric measures of observations and studying the behaviour of individuals becomes paramount for a postpositivist. Finally, some laws or theories that govern the world need to be tested, verified, and refined to understand the world. Thus, in the scientific method—the accepted approach to research by postpositivists—a researcher begins with a theory, collects data that either supports or refutes the theory, and then makes necessary revisions and conducts additional tests (Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

Research Design

This study has applied the non-experimental form of the quantitative research approach. It is the correlational design in which this study has applied the correlational statistic to describe and measure the association between organizational reward systems and employees' job satisfaction (Collis & Hussey, 2021).

Research Methods

The quantitative research method is useful to consider the full range of possibilities of data collection and to organize this method, for example, by its degree of predetermined nature, its use of closed-ended versus open-ended questioning, and its focus on numeric versus non-numeric data analysis (Collis & Hussey, 2021).

The survey study

The survey research provides a quantitative or numeric description of a population's trends, attitudes, or opinions by studying a population sample. It includes cross-sectional studies using questionnaires for data collection—with the intent of generalizing from a sample to a population (Mishra, Mahat, & Khanal, 2021). For this study, the survey research technique was utilized to obtain essential information from respondents by distributing copies of the questionnaire.

Sample population

In Kathmandu, Lalitpur, Bhaktapur, Chitwan, and Nawalparasi districts, there were 183 private colleges in operation. The study sampled 20 percent of total colleges. A total of 400 samples were taken. Teaching and non-teaching workers were chosen as the respondents using simple random sampling methods from each college.

Data analysis

IBM SPSS Statistics 26 for Windows was applied to analyze the collected data because it is an affordable, professional analysis program for students based on the professional version of the program available from IBM. The data analysis is based on statistical analysis. The statistical tools were applied to examine the association between the dependent and independent variables, where different reward systems were the independent variables and the employees' satisfaction was the dependent variable. The Cronbach Alpha's Test (Karki, Mahat, & Kandel, 2021) value for the total items of the survey questionnaire was evaluated for the reliability of the collected data in this study (92.7 percent).

4. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

It is imperative to encourage employees to yield the company better output. In doing so, the organizations can encourage employees by establishing a reward system. If employees are rewarded based on their work rate and ethics, then it will encourage other employees to follow the same work rate. It will help for better output of the company. Reward systems may be a family holiday, bonuses or other packages that

help the employees do more work. The study has shown that the frequency of rewarding teachers decreased the job overturn and increased the commitment of teachers towards the job (Kipkirui, 2014). In most colleges, the teachers want to commit to their school and college when there is a reward policy. The teachers felt that they were the most important part of the colleges. So, the reward system helped improve employees' satisfaction with their organization.

In this section, the study presented a different questionnaire for the respondents to know the reward system for the employees. The maximum mean obtained for good work is recognized appropriately (3.51) (see Table 1), and virtually everyone in the college receives an appropriate salary (3.51). It means that a maximum number of respondents agreed strongly with the statement. At the same time, the minimum mean was obtained for an appropriate difference between the pay awarded to good and bad performance (2.93). It means that the maximum number of respondents were almost neutral to the statement (see Table 1).

Table 1: Research instrument of reward system

Reward System							
	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total	Mean
Good work is recognized appropriately	6.5	11.5	23.8	41.3	17.0	100.0	3.51
I think my boss is too tolerant of poor performance	8.5	20.3	33.8	26.0	11.5	100.0	3.12
Work that is not of the highest importance	10.5	10.3	28.8	33.5	17.0	100.0	3.36
In general, people are adequately rewarded in this college	10.8	17.8	30.3	29.3	12.0	100.0	3.14
The college's pay scale is competitive with similar institutions	10.8	13.5	24.5	33.8	17.5	100.0	3.34
I receive an appropriate salary	13.0	12.5	18.0	34.5	22.0	100.0	3.40
I receive appropriate benefits	15.0	19.0	24.3	28.8	13.0	100.0	3.06
An appropriate difference between the pay awarded	18.0	16.5	30.8	24.5	10.3	100.0	2.93
I feel a strong sense of job satisfaction	8.8	14.0	36.3	27.5	13.5	100.0	3.23
Virtually everyone in the college receives an appropriate salary	10.3	8.3	26.3	31.0	24.3	100.0	3.51

Source: Field Survey

It can be interpreted that, apart from the maximum mean with good work recognized appropriately and virtually everyone in the college received an appropriate salary, other questionnaires got an almost neutral response. Most of the respondents did not agree much or less with the statement. The second highest mean was obtained for receiving an appropriate salary (3.40), followed by work that was not of the highest importance and dealt with appropriately (3.36). Therefore, it was concluded that the organization was neutral in providing their employee with a reward system. Although some might take high rewards for their work rate, others felt they were not much rewarded.

Reward and employee satisfaction

It is important to know the reward system of the college and its employee satisfaction. If the employees are not satisfied with the reward system, they might either perform poorly or discontinue their service, which might negatively impact the institution. So, organizations should have a strong reward policy for their employee to have maximum positive output. Strong ties should be between the organization and employees to ensure satisfaction and productivity for both employers and employees.

This study shows the reward policy and employee satisfaction with such a policy. It was found that there was a strong correlation between employee satisfaction and the reward system.

Table 2: Reward and employee satisfaction

Correlations		Reward	Satisfaction
Reward	Pearson Correlation	1	.460**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	400	400
Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.460**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	400	400

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field Survey

It was interpreted that there was a significant correlation between the reward system and

employee satisfaction as the value of p was 0.000, which is less than 0.01 significant levels. There was a positive correlation ($r = .460$) between the reward system and satisfaction, which indicates that if there is a change in the reward system by a point, it will bring a change in satisfaction by .460 points (see Table 2).

Implications of Study

The study made the following implications for the improvement of reward systems and job satisfaction in the private colleges of Nepal:

- A reliable system of Review of remuneration of all units has to be developed to eliminate the lack of consideration of the terms of service for the staff.
- Non-monetary rewards should be adopted adequately in private colleges' reward systems, including recognition and placement for training and other personal development initiatives.
- The allowances and other monetary and non-monetary perks and recognition should be tailored to specific jobs to ensure improvement of the job satisfaction of all the employees of colleges.
- The indicators of the reward system under consideration included a comparison of the reward system with the equivalent in the public and governmental colleges, availability and adequacy of rewards, promptness of rewards and adequacy of them. It should be placed in the right place

5. CONCLUSION

This research focuses on learning more about private college employees' compensation and work satisfaction perspectives. The study was conducted as a cross-sectional study using an exploratory and descriptive approach. A total of one hundred and eighty-three ($N = 183$) private colleges are currently operating in Kathmandu, Lalitpur, Bhaktapur, Chitwan, and Nawalparasi districts. The study selected 20 percent of the total colleges. There were 400 samples obtained in total. Simple random sample procedures were used to choose teaching and non-teaching employees from each institution as the respondents. The organization was uninterested in creating an incentive system for its employees. While some people were recognized for their high work rate, others did not

feel they were. According to the findings, there was a considerable correlation between the reward system and job satisfaction. There was a link between the reward system and job satisfaction.

REFERENCES

- Ali, R., & Ahmed, M. (2009). The impact of reward and recognition programs on employee's motivation and satisfaction: an empirical study. *International Review of Business Research Papers*, 5(4), 270-279.
- Bessell, I., Dicks, B., Wysocki, A., & Kepner, K. (2002). *Understanding Motivation: An Effective Tool for Managers*. Florida: the University of Florida IFAS extension.
- Bowen, R. B. (2000). *Recognizing and rewarding employees*. . New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Buitendach, J., & Witte, H. D. (2005). Job security, extrinsic and intrinsic job satisfaction and effective organizational commitment of maintenance workers in a parastatal. *South African Journal of Business Management*, 36(2), 27-37.
- Collis, J., & Hussey, R. (2021). *Business Research: a practical guide for students*. (5th ed.). Red Globe Press.
- Conti, G. (2005). Training, Productivity and Wages in Italy.
- Creswell, J. W. (2007). *Qualitative inquiry and research design (2nd ed.)*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Danish, R. Q., & Usman, H. (2010). The impact of reward and recognition on job satisfaction and motivation: an empirical study from Pakistan. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 5(2).
- Eshun, C., & Duah, F. (2011). *Rewards as a Motivation Tool for Employee Performance BTH2011*. Retrieved from Eshun.pdf.
- Evans, J. R., & Lindsay, W. M. (2003). *The management and control of quality (5th ed.)*. . US: Thomson.
- Gruneberg, M. (1979). *Understanding job satisfaction*. . Basingstoke: MacMillan.
- Ivancevich, J. M. (2004). *Human resource management (9th ed.)*. Tata: McGraw-Hill.

- Karki, T. B., Mahat, D., & Kandel, D. R. (2021). Effectiveness of Online Class and Physical Class during Covid-19 Pandemic. *Nepal Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (NJMR)*, 16.
- Kipkirui, K. S. (2014). *Influence Of Extrinsic Rewards On Teachers' Job Commitment In Public Primary Schools, Sigor Division, Chepalungu District, Kenya*. Nairobi: Department of Educational Administration and Planning.
- Lawler, E. (1986). *High involvement management*. . San Francisco, CA: Jossey Bass.
- Malhotra, N., Budhwar, P., & Prowse, P. (2007). Linking rewards to commitment: an empirical investigation of four UK call centres. *International Journal of Human Resource Management; Routledge: Taylor & Francis Group*, 2095-2127. volume and issue number?
- Malhotra, N., Budhwar, P., & Prowse, P. (2007). Linking rewards to commitment: an empirical investigation of four UK call centres. *International Journal of Human Resource Management; Routledge: Taylor & Francis Group*. , 2095-2127.
- Mathieu, J. E., & Zajac, D. (1990). A review and meta-analysis of the antecedents correlate and consequences of organizational commitment. *Psychological Bulletin*, 108(2).Page number? check everywhere
- Mathis, R. L., & Jackson, J. H. (2004). *Human resource management (10th ed.)*. Thomson South-Western.
- Mayo, E. (1998). *The human problems of industrialized civilization*. Illinois: Scott Foresman.
- Meyer, J. P., Stanley, D., & Herscovitch, L. (2002). Affective, continuance and normative commitment to the organization: A meta-analysis of antecedents, correlates and consequences. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 61, 20-52.
- Mishra, S., Mahat, D., & Khanal, L. (2021). Employees' Respect and Job satisfaction in Nepalese Private. *Nepal Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (NJMR)*, 45-52.
- Mumford, E. (1991). Job satisfaction: a method of analysis. *Personal Review*, 20(3), pp. 11-19.
- Nepal, H. P. (2014). Effect of Teachers' Job Satisfaction on Transforming Education in Private Schools in Nepal: A Quantitative Analysis. *ACADEMIA*, 1-56.

- Noe, R. A., Hollenbeck, J. R., Gerhart, B., & Wright, P. (2006). *Human Resources Management: Gaining A Competitive Advantage. 5th Ed.* New York: McGraw-Hill/Irwin.
- Robbins, S. (2001). *Organizational behaviour (9th ed.)*. New York: Prentice-Hall, Inc.
- Schermerhorn, J. (1991). *Managing original behaviour. (4thed.)*. New York: John Wiley and Sons.
- Sempene, M., Rieger, H. S., & Roodt, G. (2002). Job satisfaction in relation to organisational culture. *SA Journal of Industrial Psychology, 28(2)*, 23-30. .
- Shanks, N. H. (2007). *Management and motivation: introduction to healthcare management.* . United States: Jones and Bartlett Learning.
- Spector, P. (2000). *Organizational psychology: research and practice.* . New York: John Wiley & Sons.
- Tessema, M., & Soeters, J. (2006). Challenges and prospects of HRM in developing countries: Testing the HRM-performance link in Eritrean civil service. *International Journal of Human Resource Management, 17(1)*, 86-105.
- Vansteenkiste, M. (2005). *Intrinsic versus extrinsic goal promotion and autonomy support versus control.* Leuven: KU Leuven: Doctoral Dissertation.

**Study on Potential and Practices of Rooftop Rainwater Harvesting System in
Oxford College of Engineering and Management**

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Received: November 25, 2022

Revised: December 27, 2022

Accepted: January 09, 2023

Published: January 29, 2023

How to cite this paper:

KC, M., Bhandari, M.P, Timilsena, S, Lamichhane, S., Adhikari, B.P, Poudel A. & Kafle S.C, (2022).

Study on Potential and Practices of Rooftop Rainwater Harvesting System in Oxford College of Engineering and Management

The OCEM Journal of Management, Technology & Social Sciences, 2(2), 191-214

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Oxford College of Engineering and Management

Originality: This paper is original and has not been published anywhere else

Paper type: Research paper

J.E.L. Classification: I (2), I (29)

Abstract

The objective of this study was to evaluate the possibility of promoting rooftop rainwater harvesting to address future water scarcity in the Oxford College of Engineering and Management Nawalparasi district. AutoCAD software drew accepted plans and maps; manual measurement was done with measuring tape since some parts were missing.

The results show that the linear forecast 1558.139, 1581.57mm, 1548.63mm, 1598.14mm and 1570.64mm. The volume of water is 5135.54, 5028.16, 5188.94, 5099.68 respectively. It also shows the calculation of water demand which is 5,820,000 liters per year, and the water harvested is 5188946.58 liters per year. Finally, with this ratio, we realized we could fulfil 89.15% of water demand through water harvesting. The time series relevant results indicated that the A.R.I.M.A. model of forecasting rainfall was based on (0.1.0), signifying the R Square value is .631 and the p-value is insignificant ($p > 250$), which is better for this forecasting model.

Keywords: *Catchment area, demand, forecasting, measurement, rainfall, roof rainwater harvesting*

1. INTRODUCTION

Millions of people worldwide do not have access to clean water for domestic purposes. In many parts of the world, conventional piped water is either absent, unreliable, or unsuitable for the settlements at high mountains. It is also too expensive for people who are under the poverty line. One of the 21st century's biggest challenges is overcoming the growing water shortage (Nepal Water for Health, 2012). Due to rapid growth in urbanization, roof rainwater is one of the best alternative sources of water supply to all sectors. It can fulfil both potable and non-potable water demands. It is also more economical and socially acceptable to the community (Hasnain, 2018).

With technological advancement, various proven methods have evolved for water collection and distribution through pipes for individual and collective communal systems. With more conventional water supply technologies, Rainwater harvesting (R.W.H.) has become a valuable and viable alternative or supplementary water source. Much of the actual or potential water shortages can be relieved if rainwater harvesting is widely practiced (Bittharia, 2021). From an environmental and socioeconomic perspective, a rooftop R.W.H.S. has many advantages. It can be used for agricultural, domestic and industrial purposes. Rooftop rainwater harvesting systems also play an essential role in flood management and stormwater runoff (Ali et al., 2019).

1.1 Background of the study

Roof rainwater harvesting is a simple, low-cost technique requiring minimum expertise or knowledge. Collected rainwater can be supplement to other water sources when it becomes scarce or is of poor quality. It is also a good alternative during drought or when the water table drops and the wells dry. The collected rainwater is a valuable supplement which would otherwise be lost by surface runoff or evaporation (Adugna, Jensen, Lemma & Gebrie 2018). During the past decade, R.W.H. has been actively reintroduced by government and local organizations as an option for increasing access to water in urban and rural areas. With the increased need for water, innovative approaches to improving the water supply are desperately needed in many parts of developing countries. A wide variety of small-scale rainwater harvesting methods are being applied in some countries for the irrigation of crops and sustainable life (Avis

& Avis 2018). In Nepal, this system of collecting rainwater and using it in washing clothes, and utensils, feeding animals, irrigating the gardens, and even recharging the groundwater table can be seen mostly in rural areas. Many organizations have studied rainwater harvesting to mitigate the scarcity of water. Water scarcity is a problem wherever there is an increasing population.

The R.W.H. technology has rapidly gained popularity, with users realizing the benefits of a relatively clean, reliable, and affordable water source at home (Bittharia, 2021). R.W.H. has now been introduced as part of an integrated water supply system. In many areas, there is adequate precipitation throughout the year. The town water supply fluctuation in the regular supply, i.e., it cannot meet the current demands of the community (Bittharia, 2021). (Salāmah., Shutaywī & Al Ragged 2018) analyze and interpret the collected rainwater and household catchment area together. They found that the potential of water harvesting and collected water could be helpful to domestic sources.

Similarly, (Worm, Tim Van Hattum, Catharina De Kat-Reynen, & Al 2006) conclude that the 'World Economic Forum has ranked the water crisis as the most significant risk to humanity and human economics. The world will face water scarcity by 2025 (Jeevan Kasula (2012). Furthermore, he concluded that only 27 percent of the population could access safely managed water and 62 percent could access basic sanitation services. Due to the pollution of both groundwater and surface water and the overall increased demand for water resources owing to population growth, many communities are approaching the limits of their traditional water resources (Nepal Water for Health 2012). Therefore, each country has begun to resort to alternative or 'new' resources like Rainwater harvesting. It has become a valuable alternative or supplementary water source (Celeste, Novak, Giesen, & Debusk, 2014). Rapid population growth and urbanization have demanded a greater water volume in Nepal.

Additionally, people's awareness of sustainable development along with the Millennium Development Goals is still poor in Nepal (Nepal Water for Health 2012). Therefore, excessive groundwater is environmentally unfavourable and a future threat to sustainable development (Avis & Avis, 2018). Water management is critical to any economy's

growth and development, particularly in growing economies like Nepal. However, the resource is currently under stress due to excessive groundwater exploitation in socioeconomic development and to meet the increased needs of the growing population (Adugna et al. 2018). As a result, we should use this valuable resource while conserving it (Umapathi, Pezzaniti, Beecham, Whaley, & Sharma 2019). The primary goal of this study is to give a broad review of rainwater collecting systems and groundwater and their uses in everyday life. Many countries have implemented rainwater harvesting as a long-term strategy to complement public water supplies. Rainwater harvesting systems have overcome many water-related issues. Another source of water that can be counted on is groundwater (Chao-Hsien, En-Hao & Yie-Ru, 2014).

Rainwater harvesting is the best option in areas with inadequate groundwater or surface water supply. Rainwater harvesting is the deposit of rainwater to reuse on-site, rather than runoff, which helps using overloads to water treatment plants. It prevents runoff from going to the drainage system, effectively utilizing the rainwater (Adugna et al. 2018). Similarly, it helps recharge water into aquifers and improves groundwater quality, preventing runoff from going to the drainage system and effectively using the rainwater. Similarly, it helps restoring moisture into aquifers and improves groundwater quality through dilution. (Mouli 2017; Whittington & Xun Wu, 2020). harvested rainwater has fewer pathogens than unprotected surface water.

Rainwater Harvesting Capacity Centre was established in 2006 and promoted the technology of Rainwater Harvesting in Nepal. It provides long-term access to use safe water for vulnerable communities, primarily in 'Type 3 areas. People have no access to surface water, have no alternative sources such as boreholes or spring potential, and suffer from restrictions due to poor water quality (Lalwani, 2022). Some parts of Nepal have been following rooftop rainwater harvesting. It is a cheap process compared to surface runoff. The harvesting system consists of a catchment roof, conveyance pipes, and a storage jar (reservoirs). The pipes include a gutter system made from longitudinally split polyethylene pipe, which has a flushing system that allows the system to be flushed clean periodically. Therefore, people can save hundreds of dollars a year instead of buying the popular yet questionable quality water available in jars in the market from USD 0.35 to 1.3 per 20 liters and save between USD 51- 85 each year (Mambretti &

Melgarejo 2019). The general objective of the research was to evaluate the possibility of promoting rooftop rainwater harvesting to address future water scarcity at Oxford College of Engineering and Management. in Nawalparasi district. Evaluation of users' willingness to adapt rooftop rainwater harvesting and its potential in domestic and institutional buildings were the specific objectives for obtaining the primary goal. This study implication would be beneficial to the development of the metrology department, risk disaster management, agriculture (crop development), NARK, and future researchers in foregrounding the need for rainwater harvesting systems and conducting the primary experimental research in the Nepalese context. We are bachelor's students of the Engineering Department at Oxford College of Engineering and Management (OCEM), Gaidakot, Nepal.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This review is embedded in the search for roof rainwater harvesting systems to meet the current water demand. Our study is based on journal articles, books, online documents, magazines, and conference papers. This review has analyzed fifteen published journal articles focusing on rainwater harvesting systems and tried to find the research gaps in the reviewed articles.

Rainwater Harvesting System Components

The roof, ground, and rock catchments are three common systems to collect water for domestic Use. Check and sand dams are mainly used for irrigation (See Figure 1) (Mouli 2017).

Figure 1. Catchments surfaces of roof rainwater

The roof of a building or a house is an obvious choice for a catchment installation. One can build an open-sided barn—called a rain barn or a pole barn to accommodate additional capacity. Barns can store water tanks, pumps, filters, vehicles, and tools (Celeste et al., 2014). Rooftop rainwater systems are popular at the household and community levels, as the water can be readily used for domestic purposes. An added advantage is that users own, maintain, and control their systems, reducing reliance on other community members (see Figure 2). Water quality in these systems is related to the roof material, climatic conditions, and the surrounding environmental conditions (Al-Houri, Abu-Hadba & Hamdan 2014). Rock and ground catchments Rooftop water tends to be of higher quality and is therefore preferred for human consumption. Where water quality is of less concern, such as small-scale irrigation for food production, livestock, tree nurseries, brickmaking, etc., the livelihood approach promotes the Use of runoff water. Runoff can be stored in ponds; however, loss due to evaporation makes small, underground storage tanks a better option. Rainwater on rock surfaces can be diverted to storage tanks using bunds and gutters (Saeid Eslamian & Faezeh Eslamian, 2020) (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Roof catchments of roof rainwater

Delivery System components

Several types of delivery systems are used to transport water from catchments to Gutters and are installed to capture rainwater running off the eaves of a building. Some gutter installers provide continuous or seamless gutters. Lead cannot be used as gutter solder for potable water systems, as is sometimes the case in older metal gutters (Aniruddha Bhalchandra Pandit & Jyoti Kishen Kumar, 2019) (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Delivery System component

Gutter Sizing and Installation

Roofs are often built with one or more roof valleys with different slopes—an important consideration in constructing rooftop catchment systems. Roof valleys are the point at which two roof planes meet. The size of roof areas ending in a roof valley, the roof slope, and the rainfall intensity affect the ability of the drainpipe to capture the water (Avis & Avis, 2018). If these factors are not adequately accounted for, spillage or overrunning may result. Other factors that may result in overrunning include inadequate downspouts, excessively long distances from ridge to eave, steep roof slopes, and inadequate gutter maintenance. These variables make it difficult to apply standard rules for drainpipe sizing. Specialized engineers can provide specific guidance on strategies to mitigate

overrunning and improve catchment efficiency (Adhikari, Timisina & Lamichhane 2018).

Table 1. Summary of the previous study on rooftop rainwater harvesting systems

Topics	Authors and publication year	Objective	Name of journal	Methods used	Findings
<p>a. Assessing the Potential for Rooftop Rainwater Harvesting from Large Public Institutions</p> <p>b. The Potential of Roof Top Rainwater Harvesting as a Water Resource in Jordan: Featuring Two Application Case Studies</p> <p>c. Design of Rooftop Rainwater Harvesting Structure on a University Campus</p> <p>d. Rooftop Rainwater Harvesting (R.R.W.H.) At Spsv Campus</p> <p>e. Domestic Rainwater Harvesting System: A Model for Rural Development</p>	<p>Dangnachew Adunga, Marina Bergen Jensen, Brook Lemma and Geremew Sahilu Gebrie (2018); Zain M. Al-Houri, Oday K. Abu-Hadba, Khaled A. Hamdan (2014); S. Sangita Mishra, Shruti B.K. and H. Jeevan Rao (2020); (Patel et al.(2014); Panhalkar (2011)</p>	<p>This study assessed the resource potential of rooftop rainwater gathering in Jordan.</p>	<p>a. international journal of environmental research and public health.</p> <p>b. Rural Extension & Innovation Systems Journal.</p> <p>c. International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering.</p> <p>d. International Journal of Research in Engineering and Technology</p> <p>e. International Journal of Science and Nature</p>	<p>a. A. survey method</p> <p>b. A case studies method</p> <p>c. Review method</p> <p>d. Qualitative and rational method</p> <p>e. Case study</p>	<p>The results indicate that a particular volume of water can be harvested in specific areas to address the scarcity of water in cities</p>
<p>a. Rainwater Harvesting</p> <p>b. Design of a Rainwater Collection System and Possible Use of Harvested Water in a Kindergarten Building: A Case Study in Tirana City, Albania</p> <p>c. The potential of rainwater harvesting in Nepal: a case study</p>	<p>Akther (2014); Blerina Beqaj, Oltion Marko, Entela Cobani and Drican Proska (2022); Gautam (2016)</p>	<p>The primary objective of the research was to determine each family's capacity on various parcels of land by analyzing and interpreting the collected rainwater and household catchment area.</p>	<p>a. JUICE Press Conference Paper</p> <p>b. European Journal and Technology Research</p> <p>c. Norwegian University of Life Sciences</p>	<p>a. A Survey Survey</p> <p>b. Case study method</p>	<p>The study's finding concludes that harvested rainwater can be used for different household purposes</p>

Topics	Authors and publication year	Objective	Name of journal	Methods used	Findings
Adoption and impact of rainwater harvesting technology on rural livelihoods: The case of Makwanpur district, Nepal	Surya P. Adhikari, Krishna p. Timsina and Jeevan Lamichhane (2018)	This case study's main objective was to identify factors that incite the adoption decision of Rainwater harvesting technology.	Rural Extension and Innovation System Journal	A case study method	The finding indicates that the main factors influencing the adoption of R.W.H. technology were the number of years of education, the total value of physical assets, and the organizational membership of household members
Rainwater Harvesting, a Review	Jain, Chandrakar & Yadav (2022).	The main objective of this study was to provide a thorough overview of groundwater and rainfall collection systems and their potential applications in daily life.	Indian Journal of Applied Research	A literature review method	As a long-term plan, rainwater harvesting can be used to supplement the public water supply as well as many water-related problems have been resolved with the Use of R.W.H. systems.
Performance of a large building rainwater harvesting system	Sarah Ward, Fayyaz Ali Memon and David Butler (2012)	This paper aimed to evaluate the performance of a non-domestic R.W.H. system in a British office building empirically.	Journal of Water Research	The intermediate (simple calculations) and detailed (simulation-based) approaches.	The study concludes that the office-based R.W.H. system had an average water-saving effectiveness of 87% over eight months. Also, using a smaller tank rather than a larger one may have produced results of a similar caliber.

Topics	Authors and publication year	Objective	Name of journal	Methods used	Findings
Sustainability of rainwater harvesting systems in multistorey residential buildings	Rahman et al (2010)	This study aimed to investigate alternative water	American Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences	A water balance model was developed to calculate water savings for multiple scenarios	The results discovered that a larger roof area offers better financial and water-saving advantages. It was shown that a higher roof area is preferable in terms of water savings and economic benefits.
Potential of rooftop rainwater harvesting to meet outdoor water demand in arid regions	Kazi Tamaddun, Ajay Kalra and Sajjad Ahmad (2018)	The main objective of this study was to evaluate the effects of the selected model parameters on the efficiency of rooftop rainwater harvesting	Journal of Water Research	The intermediate (simple calculations) and detailed (simulation-based) approaches	The results indicated that the suggested storage tanks of 1-2m ³ rainwater barrels can hold about 80% of the monthly collected rooftop rainwater in Arizona and that there was a variation of 37.5% in the amount of rainfall potential between the expected dry and wet climate conditions
Potential of rainwater harvesting in urban Zambia	Lubinga Handia and Caroline Mwiindwa (2003)	The study aimed to determine whether rainwater collection could be used in urban Zambia.	Journal of Physics and Chemistry of the Earth, Parts A/B/C	Qualitative, rational method	The results indicate that a storage tank with a 10m ³ capacity has been chosen, and the construction of 5 systems is in progress.

The findings show that a certain amount of water can be gathered in places (Adugna et al.2014). Similarly, the study concludes that harvested rainwater can be used for different household purposes (Akther 2014; Beqaj, Marko, Çobani & Profka 2022;

Gautam 2016). Likewise, the finding also indicates that establishing the rainwater harvesting system requires a series of years of study along with the total value of physical assets and the organizational membership of household members (Akther 2014; Beqaj, Marko, Çobani & Profka 2022; Gautam 2016). Furthermore, the study concludes that rainwater harvesting devices have been used to solve numerous water-related issues and can be used to supplement the public water supply (Jain, Chandrakar & Yadav 2022). Correspondingly The study found that one effective way to lessen water scarcity is to establish a small rainwater collection system that might collect enough water to meet family needs. A surrounding area's groundwater table can also be maintained for an extended period by using abandoned wells that have been turned into percolation wells (Akther 2014).

Uniformly, the study's findings show office-based rainwater harvesting for eight months. The system had an average water-saving efficiency of 87%. Additionally, the study concludes employing a smaller tank instead of a larger one might have led to outcomes of comparable quality (Ward, Memon & Butler 2012). A bigger roof area was identified to provide higher financial and water-saving benefits. A higher roof area has been demonstrated to be more advantageous regarding water conservation and economic benefits (Rahman 2010).

Similarly, this study discovered that the 1-2 m³ rainwater barrels recommended for storage could contain roughly 80% of the monthly rooftop rainwater collected in Arizona. The difference in rainfall potential between the predicted dry and wet climate conditions is 37.5% (Tamaddun, Kazi, & .2018). Furthermore, this study suggests that a storage tank with a 10m³ capacity has been chosen, and the construction of 5 systems is in progress (Handia Lubinga, Tembo Madalisto James, Mwiindwa & Caroline 2003). Likewise, according to the study's findings, the kindergarten building, which has a 370 m² catchment area, is responsible for collecting the water used for the school's regular operations, such as flushing the restrooms and washing clothes (Beqaj, Marko, Çobani & Profka 2022).

3. METHODS AND MATERIALS

Our study has followed both primary and secondary data collection procedures during our research. The secondary data for this study came from various literature gathered and evaluated to achieve the study's objectives. We fulfilled all ethical issues of the primary and secondary data collection. We have taken the reference at OCEM, with a catchment area of 3246.86 sqm. We clearly came to know all the advantages which can draw out by implementing this small but highly efficient technique in the periphery of campus. Thus, to increase the potential benefits of this system and draw maximum advantages from it, we need to have larger rooftop areas that will act as catchment areas. The greater the catchment area, the more surface runoff and, thus, the amount of water harvested. To obtain primary data for the research with the help of a letter on (date) from Oxford College of Engineering and Management, we approached the Agriculture Forestry University (A.F.U.) Office. This study has included and considered all the major buildings and larger rooftop areas as much as possible for the primary data collection. Hence study areas include all five blocks (Engineering/B.C.A., administrative. Infirmiry+ HM) and all other areas such as the Basketball court, water tap, canteen, parking, storeroom, stationery guard room, and toilet. Plans and maps of the study area were obtained from the respective authorities without further ado to meet 1st objective. Accepted methods and maps were analyzed by AutoCAD software; manual measurement was done with measuring tape since some parts were missing.

A rain gauge was used to collect the rainfall data, but it was unfavourable to place a rain gauge in our study area. The nearest rain gauge station was located at Agriculture Forestry University (A.F.U.), Rampur, Chitwan, Nepal. The rainfall data obtained from the office include 2000-2021. After the competition of the data collection, we then tabulated the linear projection for the upcoming five years. With this area's runoff coefficient and the litres per person, we assumed from our textbook that this study calculated our demand for our catchment. Then we calculated the amount of water that could be harvested from our catchment. After the final calculation of the water volume harvested, we planned the area in which the harvested water could be used. The processes of rainfall harvesting are also addressed in this study (see Figure 1). The methodological review was also based on the secondary data on rainfall.

Hydrological Analysis

Table 2. Data Analysis and calculation

S.N.	Type of area	Value of k		
		Flat land with 0-5% slope	Rolling land 5-10% slope	Hilly land 10-30%
1	Urban areas	0.6	0.65	-
2	Single-family residence	0.3	0.6	0.72
3	Cultivated areas	0.5	0.4	0.42
4	Pastures	0.3	0.4	0.50
5	Wooden land or forested areas	0.3		

The volume of water received from the catchment can be calculated by multiplying the catchment's area, the amount of rainfall and the runoff coefficient. **Harvesting potential or volume of water received () = area of catchment ()Amount of rainfall () Runoff coefficient.**

The runoff coefficient for any catchment is the ratio of the volume of water that runs off a surface to the importance of rainfall that falls on the surface. The runoff coefficient accounts for losses due to spillage, leakage, infiltration, catchment surface wetting, and evaporation, all contributing to reducing the runoff. The runoff coefficient varies from 0.5 to 1.0. in the present problem statement, the runoff coefficient equals one, as the rooftop area is fully waterproof. (Garg) Eco-climate conditions (i.e., Rainfall quantity and rainfall pattern) and the catchment characteristics are the key factors affecting rainwater potential. The table given below shows the value of the runoff coefficient concerning types of surface areas.

Water demand calculation:

The total number of students in our college is 2260, the Total number of staff is 165, the Water demand for one person for one day is 10 litres per person (per capita) per day (lpcd), the total water demand per day is $2425 \times 10 = 24250$ lpcd and the Total water demand per year = 5820000 litres, per year (we have considered eight months) (see Table 2)

4. RESULTS

Some techniques transform the data as real-life time series data, usually appearing nonstationary, into a stationary sequence. The basic distributional features of the time series data were analyzed after establishing constant mean and variance and checking for the presence of non-normality. The focus of time series analysis is shifted to empirically investigating the autocorrelation structure of the observations. This study has completed the necessary steps of time series analysis, primarily three steps to forecast the A.R.I.M.A. Model (Brownlee, 2017). The results show that the secondary data were checked to determine whether they were stationary. The results showed the rainfall data were stationary (see Figure 1).

4.1 Status of rainfall around the catchment area

Here, the rainfall data is presented along with the year and projected annual rainfall.

Table 3. Year-wise projected rainfall data.

Year	Projected annual rainfall
2022	1558.14
2023	1581.57
2024	1548.63
2025	1598.14
2026	1570.64

The above table shows the annual rainfall for the upcoming 5 years, obtained with the help of linear projection of data acquired from A.F.U. (2000-2021). This projection shows that the maximum amount of rainfall could be in 2025; likewise, the minimum amount of rainfall could be seen in 2024. Following 2023 has the 2nd maximum projected rainfall; 2026 and 2022 have the 3rd and 4th highest rainfall, respectively. The graphical analysis of these data reveals maximum fluctuation in the past 20 years, whereas the predicted 5 years has the least rainfall fluctuation.

Figure 4 Projected rainfall

The results confirm that there will be a fluctuation in rainfall during the prediction period, indicating 2025 will have more rainfall than 2030 (see Figure 4)

4.2 Fulfilled water demand:

The total volume of water for the projected year 2025 = 5188946.58 litres

Percentage of water demand fulfilled = $(\text{total volume projected} / \text{total water demand}) \times 100 = 89.15 \%$. So, with our project study, we realized that we could fulfil 89.15 % of the water demand for various purposes.

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This discussion aims to foreground more about using rainwater harvesting as a substitute for water sources and can minimize the water scarcity that might arise shortly in the forthcoming years in Nepal. By analyzing our study as evidence, we were able to show that rainwater can be gathered even in small areas, allowing us to efficiently manage the water supply by fulfilling the demand to some extent of water scarcity. This study result is like Anchan and Prasad (2020). They found the water scarcity issue could be resolved with the help of rooftop rainwater harvesting. The government and private institutions also initiated its establishment to manage the water sustainably.

Similarly, while reviewing the Dual-Mode system for harvesting rooftops for non-potable Use, we learned that rooftop rainwater was harvested at a storage tank and distributed for nonportable uses with the help of a pump (Appan,2018). Furthermore, the rainwater harvesting system directly or indirectly helps improve the local people's socioeconomic condition and the public water supply system (Sturm et al. 2009). The water collected at the catchment area is conveyed with the help of a pipeline system in the world context to the storage tank. The selection of a storage tank, capacity, and the type of tank (sedimentation or reservoir tank) are considered (Das & Choudhary, 2021). The level of purification of stored water is determined as per user requirements; for example, if water is used for domestic purposes, simple screening or sedimentation is enough, but if it is used for drinking purposes, high-level purification and treatment are required. Our result differs from the study of Sharma et al. (2021). They highlighted that recent data from the Department of Water Supply and Sewerage Management (D.W.S.S.M.) in 2019 reported that only 51.69% of the population had piped water coverage and the remaining 48.31% relied on un-piped locally and privately managed systems like private tube-wells. Even if Nepal achieved the water supply-related M.D.G. goals, when analyzed by facility type, non-piped coverage has increased from 36% in 2000 to 44% in 2017. The results of the A.R.I.M.A. forecasting model show that the closest model is (1,0,1) (see Figure 4). The results show that the value of R Square is .631 and the p-value is insignificant, which is a better-fit value for the forecasting model (see Table 2).

Main findings

The results show that the highest area (995.90 m²) and volume of rainwater (1591.58 M3) was found in the Engineering Block of OCEM following the lowest area (11.85 m²), and the lowest volume of rainfall water (18.93 m³) was Stationery+ Guardroom (see Appendix 1). The results show that the Engineering Building has the highest area (995.90 m²), the stationery and guard room has the smallest area (11.85 m²) accompanying the highest volume of water (1591.58 m³) and the lowest volume of water (18.93 m³) respectively that can be harvested. We also projected the data for the upcoming 5 years, from which we took the highest annual rainfall (1598.14 mm) for our further calculation. Afterwards, we calculated the demand, 5820000 liters/year then

we calculated the percentage of water demand fulfilled, which was 89.15% (see table 4). Our study projected the rainfall for five years from 2022 to 2026, indicating the lowest rainfall in 2024 and the highest rainfall in 2025, respectively (see Appendix 2).

The results indicate that a particular volume of water can be harvested in specific cities as the best method to address water scarcity (Adugna et al. 2018; Al-Houri, Abu-Hadba & Hamdan.2014; Mishra, & Rao; Jeevan.2020; Patel, Nandsingh, Satpalsingh & Raval 2014; Panhalkar 2011). The study by Chao-Hsien, En-Hao & Yie-Ru 2014) supported the current study's findings. They found rainwater harvesting was one of the best methods to manage water scarcity in the city. They further disclosed that rainfall harvesting from rooftops could increase the water supply for various uses such as constructing new infrastructure buildings, gardening and artificial groundwater recharge.

The results showed that rooftop R.W.H.S are technically feasible regarding monthly average rainfall, catchment area and non-potable water demand in Rampur Chitwan. However, systems cannot meet all of the non-potable demand throughout the year; this only happens during July and August. The research has also shown that rooftop R.W.H.S. offers a feasible solution to provide additional water resources when combined with an existing water supply system. However, it should be noted that these systems are not suited to older housing properties in the lower middle- and middle-class areas. This is due to a lack of relative catchment area and space for storage tanks. On the other hand, R.W.H.S. provides a good option for large catchment areas such as those provided in private housing schemes.

The results show that the rainfall was in the mean average; however, the highest was in 2007 B.S.

Table 6. Monthly average rainfall statistics of Rampur

Average monthly rainfall	
Months	Average Rainfall
January	24.10
February	29.05
March	21.05
April	15.86
May	57.86
June	254.76
July	523.62
August	463.81
September	213.14
October	49.33
November	1.95
December	6.81
Total	138.44

The results indicate that July had the most rainfall (523.62mm), while November saw the least amount (1.95mm). Following that, with an average rainfall of about 254.76 mm, June comes in third place, followed by August, with an average rainfall of 463.81 mm and September, with an average rainfall of 213.14 mm. While October has about 49.33mm of rain, May has approximately 57.86mm. The second-lowest rainfall, 6.81mm, was recorded in December, followed by 15.86mm in April, 29.05mm on average in February, 24.10mm in January month, and 21.05mm in March, with a total average rainfall of 139.44mm in 2021 (see Table 1). The results of the forecasting model show that the closest model is (1,0,1) (see Figure 4). The results show that the value of R Square is .631 and the p-value is insignificant, which is a better-fit value for the forecasting model (see Table 2). The secondary data are presented (see Appendix 3).

Review reflection

The major cities of Nepal rely primarily on groundwater resources for domestic purposes. However, groundwater supplies are being over-exploited, and every year, about ten thousand new tube wells are installed to help meet the water demand. In

particular, cities such as Kathmandu, the largest metropolitan area in Nepal, have poor access to appropriate water supply systems (Kasula, 2012). To help cope with this situation and to help mitigate this increasingly- challenging water crisis, the research reported herein examines the extent to which rooftop R.W.H.S. can offer either a full or partial solution. About 50% of the water used in Kathmandu is derived from groundwater. Groundwater availability is more limited in populated hill regions because of the lower permeability of the indurated and crystalline rock types. Despite abundant rainfall, agricultural development is restricted by the limited development of irrigation (Das & Choudhary 2021). Although all major cities in Nepal face massive water shortages, when considering the possibility of rooftop R.W.H.S. for any area, it is necessary to first look at the local rainfall data to help identify which regions exhibit the highest potential. It has been shown that it varies significantly across the country, with the general trend of wetter conditions in the east (Taplejung, 1768 m altitude, receives an annual average rainfall of 2024mm) and drier in the west (Baitadi, 1635 m, receives 1037 mm). The average rainfall in Nepal is about 1600 mm, with about 80% falling between June and September (above 5500 m, this falls as snow). It is indicated that the southern slopes of the Himalayas receive the highest rainfall (3477 mm in Pokhara, 850 m). Similarly, 5550 mm in Lumle, 1642 m), whilst the trans-Himalaya lands north of the main Himalayan range (Mustang, Dolpa, Manang and Jumla) are in a rain shadow with a desert-like barren tundra, barely getting 250 mm of annual rainfall (e.g., Jomsom, 2650m, receives 255-295 mm).

Future recommendation

- Our study recommends conducting primary research on the possibility of rainwater harvesting systems in the study area.
- Our study recommends covering the larger area of investigation to find the actual water supply scarcity and an alternative way of rainwater harvesting systems in Nepal.
- Our study recommends applying integrated experimental methods to forecast rainwater in the future in the study area.
- Our study recommends investing the rainwater volume in heavy rainfall areas and working in cooperation with the Water Supply Department to forecasting future

rainfall so that future predictions could be actual to meet the demand of water scarcity.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We want to express our gratitude and appreciation to all those who allowed us to complete the proposal. We thank the Department of Civil Engineering of Oxford College of Engineering and Management. They gave us the excellent opportunity to do this wonderful project on the topic "Study the potential and practices of rooftop rainwater harvesting system in OCEM", which helped us do a lot of research. We came to know about so many new things as well as we would like to express our heartfelt gratitude and respect to Er. Aashish Poudel for his counsel, guidance, sustained encouragement, and constructive comments throughout our research, along with the continuous support of the Research Management Cell of Oxford College of Engineering and Management.

REFERENCES

- Adhikari, S. P., Timisina, K. P., & Lamichhane, J. (2018). Adoption and impact of rainwater harvesting technology on rural livelihoods: The case of Makwanpur district, Nepal. *Rural Extension and Innovation Systems Journal*, 14(1). Retrieved <https://search.informit.org/doi/epdf/10.3316/informit.563360644027139>. Accessed on 6 Nov. 2022.
- Adugna, D., Jensen, M., Lemma, B., & Gebrie, G. (2018). Assessing the Potential for Rooftop Rainwater Harvesting from Large Public Institutions. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 15(2), 336. Retrieved <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph15020336>. Accessed on 6 Nov.
- Akther, M. S. R. (2014, August). Rainwater Harvesting. JUICE Press Conference, University of Jaffna. Retrieved <https://www.researchgate.net>. Accessed on 6 Nov. 2022.
- Al-Houri, Z. M., Abu-Hadba, O. K., & Hamdan, K. A. (2014). The Potential of Roof Top Rainwater Harvesting as a Water Resource in Jordan: Featuring Two Application Case Studies. ResearchGate; World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology. Retrieved <https://www.researchgate.net>. Accessed on 3 Nov. 2022.

- Ali, S., Ma, X., Jia, Q., Ahmad, I., Ahmad, S., Sha, Z., Yun, B., Muhammad, A., Ren, X., shah, S., Akbar, H., Cai, T., Zhang, J., & Jia, Z. (2019). Supplemental irrigation strategy for improving grain filling, economic return, and production in winter wheat under the ridge and furrow rainwater harvesting system. *Agricultural Water Management*, 226, 105842.
- Aniruddha Bhalchandra Pandit, & Jyoti Kishen Kumar. (2019). *Drinking water treatment for developing countries: physical, chemical and biological pollutants*. Royal Society of Chemistry.
- Avis, R., & Avis, M. (2018). *Essential Rainwater Harvesting*. London. New Society Publishers.
- Ban, J. K. (2010). Rainwater Harvesting (R.W.H.) in Nepal: A case study on social acceptability and performance evaluation of R.W.H. schemes implemented in Syangja and Tanahun districts. ResearchGate; ResearchGate. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication>
- Beqaj, B., Marko, O., Çobani, E., & Profka, D. (2022). Design of a Rainwater Collection System and Possible Use of Harvested Water in a Kindergarten Building: A Case Study in Tirana City, Albania. *European Journal of Engineering and Technology Research*, 7(5), 22–26.
- Bittharia, M. (2021). Design of Rooftop Rainwater Harvesting: A Case Study on Township in Gwalior. *International Journal for Research in Applied Science and Engineering Technology*, 9(5), 1389–1396.
- Celeste Allen Novak, Eddie Van Giesen, & Debusk, K. M. (2014). *Designing rainwater harvesting systems: integrating rainwater into building systems*. New York. Wiley.
- Chao-Hsien, L., En-Hao, H., & Yie-Ru, C. (2014). Designing a rainwater harvesting system for urban green roof irrigation. *Water Science and Technology: Water Supply*, 15(2), 271–277.
- Das, B. D., & Choudhary, S. K. (2021). Application of Water Quality Index (W.Q.I.) for groundwater quality assessment of Biratnagar, Nepal. *Our Nature*, 19(1), 54–61.
- Gautam, R. (2016). Potential of rainwater harvesting in Nepal: a case study. Norwegian University of Life Sciences. Retrieved <https://nmbu.brage.unit.no/nmbu-xmlui/handle/11250/2398815>. Accessed on 6 Nov. 2022.

- Handia Lubinga, Tembo Madalisto James, Mwiindwa Caroline. "Potential of Rainwater Harvesting in Urban Zambia." *Physics and Chemistry of the Earth, Parts A/B/C*, vol. 28, no. 20, 1 Jan. 2003, 893–896, Retrieved www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1474706503001694. Accessed on 6 Nov. 2022.
- Handia, Lubinga, et al. "Potential of Rainwater Harvesting in Urban Zambia." *Physics and Chemistry of the Earth, Parts A/B/C*, vol. 28, no. 20, 1 Jan. 2003, 893–896, Retrieved www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1474706503001694. Accessed on 6 Nov. 2022.
- Harvesting Potential. *International Journal of Agriculture Environment and Biotechnology*, 1 (1).
- Jain, L., Chandrakar, V., & Yadav, S. (2022). Rainwater Harvesting, A Review. *Indian Journal of Applied Research*, 24–25. Retrieved <https://doi.org/10.36106/ijar/3114395>. Accessed on 6 Nov. 2022.
- Lalwani, A. (2022). *Rainwater Harvesting. The U.S.A.* Retrieved from springer.com/article/10.1007/s40333-017-0110-7. Accessed on 6 Nov. 2022.
- Mambretti, S & Melgarejo, J. (2019). *Water Resources Management X. W.I.T. Press*
- Mishra, S. S., B.K, S., & Rao, H. Jeevan. (2020). *Design of Rooftop Rainwater Harvesting Structure on a University Campus. International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering*, 8(5), 3591–3595.
- Mouli. T (2017). Urban Rooftop Area Assessment for Estimation of Rooftop Rainwater Harvesting Potential. *International Journal of Agriculture Environment and Biotechnology*, 1 (13) 3-25
- Mouli. T (2017). Urban Rooftop Area Assessment for Estimation of Rooftop Rainwater
- N Ka Patel, Prof. A., Nandsingh, P. P., Satpalsingh, P. V., & Raval, P. (2020). Model of Rainwater Harvesting System. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Science, Engineering and Technology*, 253–268. Retrieved <https://doi.org/10.32628/ijrsrset207268>. Accessed on 6 Nov. 2022.
- Narain, V., Gooch, C. G., Chourey, J., & Prakash, A. (2018). *Globalization of Water Governance in South Asia*. London. Routledge.
- Nepal Water of Health. (2012). Rain Water Harvesting. Retrieved from <https://newah.org.np/uploads/resources/files/Rainwater%20Harvesting%20NEWAH%20document%20for%20website.pdf>.

- Panhalkar, S. (2011). Domestic Rainwater Harvesting System: A Model for Rural Development. *International Journal of Science and Nature*, 2(3), 861–867. Retrieved https://www.researchgate.net/publication/267385617_DOMESTIC_RAIN_WATER_HARVESTING_SYSTEM_A_MODEL_FOR_RURAL_DEVELOPMENT. Accessed on 6 Nov. 2022.
- Rahman. (2010). Sustainability of Rainwater Harvesting Systems in Multistorey Residential Buildings. *American Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences*, 3(1), 73–82.
- Saeid Eslamian, & Faezeh Eslamian. (2020). *Handbook of Water Harvesting and Conservation*. New York. John Wiley & Sons.
- Saeid Eslamian, & Faezeh Eslamian. (2020). *Handbook of Water Harvesting and Conservation*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Saeid Eslamian, & Faezeh Eslamian. (2020). *Handbook of Water Harvesting and Conservation*. John Wiley & Sons.
- SalāmahI., ShutaywīM., & Al Ragged, M. (2018). *Water resources of Jordan: political, social and economic implications of scarce water resources*. Springer.
- Sharma, S., Baidya, M., Poudel, P., Panthi, S. R., Pote-Shrestha, R. R., Ghimire, A., & Pradhan, S. P. (2021). Drinking water status in Nepal: an overview of climate change. *Journal of Water, Sanitation and Hygiene for Development*, 11(6), 859–866.
- Tamaddun, Kazi, Ahmad. (2018) "Potential of Rooftop Rainwater Harvesting to Meet Outdoor Water Demand in Arid Regions." *Journal of Arid Land*, vol. 10, no. 1, 5 Jan. 2018, pp. 68–83,
- Umapathi, Pezzaniti, Beecham, Whaley, & Sharma. (2019). Sizing of Domestic Rainwater Harvesting Systems Using Economic Performance Indicators to Support Water Supply Systems. *Water*, 11(4), 783.
- Ward, S., Memon, F. A., & Butler, D. (2012). Performance of a large building rainwater harvesting system. *Water Research*, 46(16), 5127–5134.
- Whittington, D., & Xun Wu. (2020). *Improving water governance in Kathmandu: insights from systems thinking and behavioural science*. Iwa Publishing.
- Worm, J., Tim Van Hattum, Catharina De Kat-Reynen, & Al, E. (2006). *Rainwater harvesting for domestic Use*. Agromisa; Wageningen.

APPENDIX 1. Experimental design of rainfall harvesting

Serial no	Building name	Rooftop area ()	Volume ()
1	Engineering block	995.90	1591.58
2	BBA/BCA block	447.77	715.59
3	Administrative block	144.81	231.42
4	Basketball court	837.27	1338.07
5	Infirmery+ HM block	62.41	99.73
6	Water Tap	23.70	37.88
7	Canteen	501.70	801.78
8	Parking	119.83	191.51
9	Stationery+ Guard room	11.85	18.93
10	Storeroom	33.12	52.93
11	Toilet	68.33	109.20

APPENDIX 2. Rainfall prediction

S.No	Year	Volume ()
1	2022	5059.05
2	2023	5135.14
3	2024	5028.16
4	2025	5188.94
5	2026	5099.68

APPENDIX 3. Rampur rainfall data

Year	Annual rainfall data (mm)	Year	Annual rainfall data (mm)
2000	1955.6	2011	1460.1
2001	2037.5	2012	1327.3
2002	1383.5	2013	1617.5
2003	2219.6	2014	1901.9
2004	1342.8	2015	1912.0
2005	1227.8	2016	1683.3
2006	1261.5	2017	1660.2
2007	2405.1	2018	1433.0
2008	2048.1	2019	1209.3
2009	1518.8	2020	1811.7
2010	1470.7	2021	1548.7